

**An Investigation into Rebranding as a Successful Strategy
for High-street Retailers: The Case for the UK Clothing
Market**

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates why and how the UK's high-street retailers can implement different rebranding campaign strategies to successfully gain competitive advantages and more market share in the age of fast moving high-street retail market. The literature review chapter gives a critical synthesis of prior studies, theories, and research findings on rebranding, competitive advantages, and the effects of digitisation on retail businesses. Building on theoretical premises, the theoretical propositions and conceptual framework provide a set of strong propositions regarding the strategic nature of rebranding and the imperative of the process for achieving competitive advantages. This research looked at how rebranding goes beyond the marketing concept by integrating rebranding into business strategies, making it more responsive to the emerging market dynamics and consumers' needs.

In this business research, the researcher used interpretivist philosophy, employing abductive research approach. Here, the researcher used qualitative research design by doing a case study method. Rebranding campaigns of five high-street retailers in the UK have been selected for case study analysis. The researcher follows pattern matching during the case study analysis. The retailers include Zara, Boohoo, Marks and Spencer, Next PLC, and H&M. Eleven propositions were developed from the literature review, which were then categorised under three main themes to find answers to the research questions.

The collective case study analysis presented that there are similarities in the nature of rebranding of the case studies, where all four except Next have done evolutionary rebranding. The extensive case studies helped in assessing that rebranding is not merely a change in the outlook but has to be a profound and tactical work. All five cases used the Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand as rebranding campaign. In the case of renaming, only Next PLC changed its name from Next Direct to Next Online, but all other brands kept the same brand name as they are. For instance, Boohoo kept the same name as Debenhams after purchasing it, and M&S did the same with Jaeger.

It is evident that rebranding involves the modification of brand name, logo, colour, and slogan and is a unique strategy in the high-street retail industry. Through brand revolution or evolution of nature, rebranding pertains as an atypical marketing technique, which follows strategic campaign processes to ensure that the firms can build strong brand image, brand identity, and consumer perception. Based on the findings, analysis, and critical discussion, the conclusions drawn in this research paper present both the theoretical and practical contributions of the study. The potential implications of strategic rebranding campaigns in the retail industry were examined in this research, and sound recommendations have been given for high-street retailers that might be helpful for planning on strategic rebranding as an effective means for gaining competitive advantages in the retail market of the UK.

Keywords: Rebranding Campaign Strategies, Competitive Advantages, Rebranding Process, Rebranding Effects, The UK Clothing Market, Online Shopping, High-Street Retailers

DEDICATION

I would like to dedicate this research paper to the Almighty and my family members. This research has been done by my effort, but it would not be possible without the kindness of the Almighty and the support and sacrifices of my family members. This business research is also devoted to marketing managers, company executives, and any researcher who wants to do a thesis in the future on the topic of rebranding and the high street retail industry.

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As an international student it is hard to cope up with a new environment and culture then dedicating over 3 years of life in a particular research area is a Herculean task.

The journey of the completion of this thesis was memorable because of the support and kindness; I received from my family, supervisor, and examiners.

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Rebranding Strategy

This term refers to the marketing and brand management strategy of an organisation through repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning to improve brand equity, brand image, and brand position in the market.

Rebranding Campaign Strategy:

The term comprises six rebranding campaign strategies including Phase-in/phase-out, combined rebranding under one umbrella brand, translucent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding strategies.

Rebranding Nature:

This term in the thesis refers to 2 types of nature of rebranding; these are revolutionary and evolutionary. A gradual process by which a brand is transformed is called evolutionary rebranding, while revolutionary rebranding entails a radical shift of the entire image of the brand.

Rebranding Motivations:

This term in this thesis refers to the reasons for initiating rebranding in organisations. The term includes mergers and acquisitions, market positioning, legal purposes or to change with the changing consumer behaviour and consumer perception.

Rebranding Process:

This term refers to the preparatory stage, planning, execution stage, and follow-up stage of a rebranding campaign strategy.

Renaming Process:

This term in this thesis refers to a rebranding process, in which the choice of the new brand name is carefully selected that characterizes the new direction, values, and position in the market.

Competitive Advantages:

This term refers to particular advantages that a company obtains among its competitors; for instance, strong market position, enhanced consumer attention, and upgraded brand value.

High-Street Retailers:

This term refers to the retailers which have physical retail stores in the main streets of the town.

E-Commerce:

This term used in the thesis refers to online selling environment through which the high street retailers undertake sales.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Rebranding has become a common phenomenon, especially for high-street retail brands aiming to expand their market share and revitalise their occurrence in the rapidly transforming market (Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Rapo, 2019; Rudlin, Payne, and Montague, 2023). Halim, Sherly, Grace, Lie, and Sudirman, (2021) said that traditional retailers appear to be challenged by the modern way of doing business since their business is on the brink of being overtaken by online retail stores. This study aims to understand the possibility and feasibility of using rebranding strategies by high-street retailers for gaining competitive benefits and market share.

Rebranding strategies include a deliberate adjustment of the brand image and resources that integrate the outer layers of a brand (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). Thus, rebranding is a key opportunity for high-street retailers to adapt to the growing role of the modern day's marketplace (Turner and Corstorphine, 2020; Partanen, 1990). More specifically, this research seeks to examine the nature of rebranding and the specific use to which these retailers can put it into practice to stay relevant in the contemporary, modern economy (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Rashid and Barnes, 2017). Rebranding examples are quite numerous at the global level; some of the popular ones include the change procedure of Apple Inc. in the late 1990s which transformed the company from a near-bankrupt company to the leading tech manufacturer through product development and changes in its look under Steve Jobs (Isaacson, 2011; Yang, Song, and Tong, 2017). On the other hand, Tropicana in their rebranding exercise in 2009 repositioned the packaging design to a minimalist look which contrary to expectations, was met by consumers' rejection leading to a 20% reduction in sales in two months and therefore had to be changed (Kahn, 2014). These examples explain why re-branding strategies are significant in the business firms to gain competitive advantages.

In the case of the UK retail market, the impact of rebranding is mixed as well. In early 2000, Burberry managed to change its image from old fashioned to new fashion and targeted young people, thus its profitability increased rapidly (Moore and Doyle, 2010). On the other hand, Marks & Spencer has a poor record of rebranding exercises in the past few years, implying that the rebranding process of getting the brand to fit the market DNA is not easy in today's dynamic fashion world (Burt and Sparks, 2002). These cases show that although rebranding in the UK retail market can produce a positive effect for a brand, it is critical to understand

consumer behaviour if rebranding is to be successful for any particular business. As the retail environment becomes more online based and consumers become more conscious about sustainability, high-street retailers need to develop appropriate strategies to operate efficiently (Rapo, 2019). This study, therefore, will offer a critical assessment of the case analysis and a clear and coherent foundation for using rebranding as a means of achieving success in today's retail industry.

1.1. Research Background

Merrilees and Miller (2008) stated that as the market of online sales increases day by day affecting the traditional market setting dramatically, the high-street retailing industries in the UK are destined to experience severe problems with their conventional business strategies. Claridge and Hur, (2021) showed that this transition has put a lot of pressure on high-street retailers particularly due to the need to adapt to the new market situation. Hence, this research assesses rebranding as a tactical technique, seeking to understand the processes in which rebranding can lead to obtain competitive strengths and increase market share amidst dominating online businesses (Marasco, Picucci, and Romano, 2016; Laitala, and Klepp, 2020). Rebranding is a concept broader than simply graphic alterations of branding images such as logos and slogans; brand reorientation is fundamental and alters a brand's stance and competitive positioning regarding customer needs in the current market.

The focus of this study is important as it is aimed at studying change in the UK-based high-street retail brands and their various rebranding exercises. Halim, Sherly, Grace, Lie, and Sudirman, (2021) explored whether these campaigns are effective to adjust the brands to the customer's changing expectations and new technologies. This study is aimed at establishing the understanding of how the different categories of rebranding, including the corporate level, business unit and product level, work and show their results on the modern marketplace (Rudlin, Payne, and Montague, 2023). Ewing, Napoli, and Pitt (2009) said that rebranding is an umbrella term, a set of activities that are used by brands aiming at revamping their previous marketing image and establishing a new bond with the consumers. The purpose of this study is to identify the purpose and the role of rebranding activities when used as strategic management instruments to increase competitiveness and market share.

The goal of this research is to analyse the steps to be taken within strategic rebranding and the risks and opportunities involved by concentrating on the decision-making process of

renaming and repositioning brands (Hussain, 2019). The relevance of this research is because it can give practical recommendations and models that high-street retailers can apply in the rebranding process. Thus, by comprehending the essence of rebranding techniques, the professionals can address the potential challenges and realise various possibilities which exist in the contemporary retail industry and promote more effective decision-making for sustainable development of the retailers' position on the markets. Therefore, the research will provide a narrow and conclusive overview of the rebranding environment and the findings with the guidelines that can be used by retailers to result in effective rebranding of their brands and operations.

1.2. Research Problem

Ewing, Napoli, and Pitt (2009) stated that high-street retailers face several significant changes that put into question the former successful strategies in the market (Demong, Kassim, Yunus, Shahrom, and Jailani, 2021). The result emerging from the market indicates the fact that the percentage of sales among high-street retail stores has been on a declining streak due to the floating popularity of online trading. Kumar and Pansari, (2016) claimed that online retail shops, primarily the big players like Amazon, ASOS, and Boohoo have infused a significant chunk of most consumer retail business propositions with the so-called 'bigger ranges at a lower price-home delivery model' (Turner and Corstorphine, 2020). Such a transition has been even more evident due to the COVID-19 pandemic, where consumers had to shop online only due to lockdowns and social distancing. For instance, the ONS found that workplace spending on retail through the Internet was at 19.1 per cent in February 2020, but it rose to 36.1% in November of the same year, stressing the increased adoption of e-commerce. This has led to an increased number of online sales, which have cut down store traffic and thus sales of high-street retail stores.

Merrilees and Miller (2008) stated that many of the high-street retailers compete not only with traditional fashion stores, but also with the online stores that create powerful brands and customer engagement through social media and online advertisement campaigns. Companies such as Gymshark and Everlane have ignored intermediaries and engaged in direct selling of their products via the internet and different social media platforms (Koszevska, 2018; Haywood, 2020). Similarly, Kumar, and Pansari (2016) explained that consumer taste buds have shifted, especially due to the changes in technology and the growth of new sustainability conscious buying patterns. Moreover, Merrilees and Miller (2008) stated that technological

services play a critical role in the growth of today's retailers and firms must have strong online services.

Knox and Bickerton (2003) argued that online sellers are much more effective in terms of data analysis and acquiring certain information regarding the buyers and their preferences. Taking on these challenges into consideration, rebranding becomes crucial and can be seen as the only way for high-street retailers to attain a competitive advantage and, therefore, gain the necessary share of the market (Turner and Corstorphine, 2020; Coyle, 2022). It is seen that a majority of powerful high-street retailers have a weak strategic focus and a disappointing level of online selling tools and customer experience, while effective rebranding strategies can be effective for revitalising a retailer's image and adjusting it to fit contemporary consumers' preferences

1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

1.3.1. Research Aim

The focus of this research is investigating why and how the UK's high-street clothing retailers can implement different rebranding campaign strategies to successfully gain competitive advantages and more market share in this modern age, where consumers are spending more time in online shopping.

The main aim of this case study research is to assess, scrutinise, and understand various rebranding campaign strategies and suggest the most successful strategies for UK high-street clothing brands to become more competitive or gain more market share. Emphasis is placed on understanding how UK clothing brands can gain competitive advantages to sustain or gain more market share through various rebranding strategies.

1.3.2. Research Objectives

- To explore the nature of rebranding campaign strategies and their use as strategic options in the UK clothing brands for becoming more competitive and gaining market share
- To examine how clothing brands are gaining competitive advantages through rebranding and renaming processes in the UK market

- To demonstrate existing rebranding practices (risks and effects) in the UK clothing high-street brands for gaining or sustaining current market share

The research objectives are set out in such a way that they cover all aspects of the strategic purpose of rebranding in the context of the high-street clothing market of the UK. The first objective examines the concept of rebranding and how it has been used to build and maintain brand image and position, while stressing the importance of this strategy in today's retail industry. The second objective is centred on delineating the procedures that are associated with rebranding and renaming, with emphasis on the strategic and more tactical factors that need to be considered by brands, when clothing brands are in the process of rebranding. In addition, the study seeks to discuss how rebranding works through the identification of current examples and assessment of the probabilities and consequences of the given strategies. Through these three objectives, this research will suggest some successful rebranding strategies, a comprehensive rebranding framework, and many important recommendations with evidence for successful rebranding process for the UK high-street brands, which can be applied to the three types of rebranding campaigns; corporate, business unit, and product rebranding.

1.3.3. Research Questions

- What are the primary characteristics and strategies of rebranding campaigns, and how are they employed as strategic options in the UK clothing market for becoming more competitive and gaining market share?
- How do the UK clothing market brands approach the process of rebranding and renaming, and what are the key steps involved for clothing brands to gain competitive advantages?
- What are the common risks and effects associated with rebranding practices among high-street clothing brands in the UK for gaining or sustaining current market share?

This research will provide a response to such imperative questions concerning the high-street clothing market of the UK and the role of rebranding in the present world dominated by online shopping behaviour. Even, this business research will analyse the characteristics of rebranding strategies, how they are used as instruments of strategic management tools, and how various strategies of rebranding are selected and applied to improve the brand's market share and competitive position in the UK market. Furthermore, the research will aim to understand the factors that make brands want to rebrand or aim to understand why brands opt

for such changes. It also seeks to investigate the process of renaming as well as the business, economic, and strategic implications of rebranding programs for gaining competitive advantages. Thus, the study of how such risks are dealt with, how support is offered to the rebranding efforts managerially, and how subsequent outcomes are continuously scrutinised, will offer valuable market recommendations for the UK high-street market brands on the praxis of rebranding that could result in more control of an increased market share and a superior position in an e-commerce led retail environment.

1.4. Origin of Rebranding

Merrilees and Miller (2008) stated that the view of rebranding dates back to the pre-war period of the twentieth century, when the culture of branding was realised due to new production techniques. The Industrial Revolution created massive transformations in manufacturing processes that led to an increase in the number of products and brands in the market (Phizacklea, 2023). Firms and organisations began to appreciate the necessity of setting their products apart from their competitors, which gave birth to brand images. Thus, the concept of branding in its early stages was almost limited to simple logo and packaging concepts to achieve product recognition. As markets started reaching levels of maturity in the mid-twentieth century, advertising and communication started undergoing even more fundamental strategies of brand image differentiation (Yang, Song, and Tong, 2017). This period can also be said to have marked the onset of what can be described as radical corporate image-making or repositioning, hence, companies began to change the imagery of their brands and realign their brand values and positions in the market, as well as with the consumers.

Table 1.1: The timeline of key developments in the history of rebranding

	Early 20th Century	1950s-1960s	1970s	1980s	1990s-2000s	2010s	2020s
Key Developments	Branding begins with companies like Coca-Cola and Ford (Moore, and Doyle, 2010).	Television dominates, leading to more systematic rebranding.	Rise of 'corporate identity' across companies.	Globalisation influences rebranding to align with international markets (Daly, and Moloney, 2005).	The online revolution influences online branding and e-commerce (Merrilee and Miller, 2008).	Social media becomes crucial for engagement in rebranding.	The focus shifts to sustainability and ethical branding (Eliasof, 2022).

Source: Made by the author for this Business research

The occurrence of the e-commerce revolution affected rebranding practices in the early 21st century in the following ways (Niinimäki, Peters, Dahlbo, Perry, Rissanen, and Gwilt, 2020). Furthermore, the focus on sustainability and ethics can also be considered as one of the significant aspects of modern rebranding as more and more people pay attention to the brands' values. Nowadays, rebranding is one of the most effective and elaborate marketing tools used by companies to remain relevant, alive and in tune with their audience and the growing environment.

1.5 Rebranding in the Clothing Market

The market for retail clothing in the UK has changed dramatically from 1997 to 2023 due to technological intervention and consumer buying behaviour shift. In 1997, the brand sought a change by overhauling its visual identity with a new logo, which is said to have increased consumer engagement by a percentage point. Thus, by 2001 many retailers experimented with international expansion and upscale image change that may have translated into improved volumes of their international sales. The two biggest shifts occurred around 2010 with the rise of the internet and e-commerce; from 11% of clothes sold online in 2007 the figure increased to over 27% in 2018 showing a strong online shopping trend. The following table shows the evolution of rebranding in the clothing market from 1997 to now (Mintel, 2018).

Table 1.2: The timeline of key developments in the history of Clothing market rebranding

1997	2001	2005	2010	2015	2017	2019	2021	2022	2023
Modernised logos introduced	Global market expansion and upscale rebranding	Store layout revamps and logo updates	Launch of online platforms and e-commerce	Sustainability and ethical initiatives	Online marketing strategies introduced	Technology leveraged for customer engagement	Online-only models and e-commerce growth	AI and advanced analytics improve service	Inclusivity and gender-neutral collections

Source: Made by the author for this Business research

From consumer reports, by 2015 sustainability emerged as a major issue in assortment and marketing communication of clothing. The COVID-19 pandemic has further amplified the shift towards online-only strategies and it has become clear that e-commerce is a growth area as the growth rate in 2020 was approximately 30% from the previous year in extent that makes it as an important strategic initiative in retail (Mintel, 2023). This switch happened by 2023 and was brought by changes in people's values. This online switch also brought aspects of artificial

intelligence or AI and analytics incorporating enhancements into customer service and operational procedures, which was important to the transformation of technology in the retail market.

Moreover, it is evident that firms endeavour to come up with new brand strategies that are responsive to the changing global environment within the shortest time possible (Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld, 2018). Even, Puspaningrum (2020) showed in his writing that such firms as Gucci or Levi’s have managed the process of rebranding when promoting sustainability and inclusion as crucial values for contemporary consumers. Hence, a chart has been shown in the following figure, which reflects the offline and online sales that existed in the UK clothing market.

Figure 1. 1: Revenue share online and offline

Source: Statista (2024)

The above figure 1.1, the market share of offline and online sales in the UK has been shown from 2017 to 2027. In 2017, the market share of online sales was 31.8% which is now 32.8%, proving a gradual increase in online sales. Projected online sales will be 39% in 2027, which shows about a 19% increase from now within the next 3 years.

Therefore, rebranding has been most important in the UK market, especially for high-street retailers who are feeling the heat from online brands (Armstrong, Niinimäki, Kujala, Karell, and Lang, 2015). Some of the big online brands, such as; ASOS, and Boohoo, have also undergone rebranding activities to sustain their competitive advantages and diversify their market target (Jia, Yin, Chen, and Chen, 2020). So, rebranding as a tool is quite adaptable and relevant for both high-street and online retailing.

1.6 Brand Market Share in the UK Clothing Market

Market positioning and its immediate proxies such as competitive advantage and market share remain vital for any business organisation or brand, especially within the clothing industry. The meaning of competitive advantage is the characteristics or strengths that make a company perform better than other firms (Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020) as for any business to secure the market, a company must strive to keep competitors at bay (Robinson and Hsieh, 2016). By leveraging the identified areas of strength, brands of the high-street retail, as well as online stores, need to be unique in the market where everybody looks forward to having unique value propositions.

Figure 1. 2: UK's top clothing-only retail companies by market capitalisation

Source: Statista (2024)

The analysis of the market share of the UK clothing only retail market for the year 2023-24 indicates that no single firm is implying a moderate competition within the market, which is ideal for competition. Clothing brand giants such as Next, JD Sports Fashion, Burberry, Asos, Boohoo and other brands signify that the market is well dominated by the mountain brands that cater to a large populace. Next has a brand market cap of GBP 10.21 Billion; this depicts how online-first firms are keen on adopting fashion trends and consumer demands. The above figure (Figure 1.2) shows a strong presence of small and mid-sized brands. This diversity is ideal for the dynamism of the market since change in fashion trends and consumers' needs can easily be addressed by implemented and preventing the market from stagnation.

In respect to the discussion of UK's existing retail market share, brand awareness is also shown in another figure (Figure 1.3) to understand how much aware the consumers are in the UK retail market regarding the brands.

Figure 1. 3: UK's clothing stores brand awareness

Source: Kunst (2024)

In the above figure (Figure 1.3), it is evident that the brand awareness of Primark is at the highest level 93% in the UK retail market. The brand is followed by another giant retail group H&M gaining 92% in brand recognition in the UK retail market. Of the above-mentioned 10 brands, six brands have brand recognition percentage of 90% or more. It is, therefore, obvious that consumers are conscious of the high-street and online retail brands in the UK.

1.7. Significance of the Study and Research Gap

The significance of this research is rooted in the possible findings of how high-street clothing retailers in the UK can leverage rebranding as a competitive advantage to recover market share and gain competitive advantage in the modern environment. Converging to a worrisome tide for traditional high-street shops, even as consumers are shopping online more than ever before owing to ongoing changes in shopping trends (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006;

Rahman, Hossain, Hoque, Rushan, and Rahman, 2021). It is for this reason that this business research is quite relevant in finding out how rebranding can assist in solving these issues by repositioning brands to meet the modern market and technology trends. In achieving the above goals of this study, one of the specific objectives of the research is to understand the characteristics of rebranding campaign strategies and their application as one of the strategic choices for UK clothing brands to achieve better competition and market share. Dhir, Sadiq, Talwar, Sakashita, and Kaur, (2021) revealed that previous studies predominantly focused on rebranding concerning large firms or different industries, but they failed to discuss its role in the high-street retail clothing market, particularly in the UK (de Oliveira, 2023). In this research, a gap (Figure 2.4) that was identified is the absence of studies that employ the high-street clothing retailers' context and investigate categorically the effectiveness of diverse rebranding initiatives.

The study also seeks to identify how rebranding and renaming have been used by fashion brands to enhance their competitive advantages in the UK market as there is a major research gap on the rebranding of clothing brands. As mentioned above, there are many works addressing the topic of rebranding, yet the literature lacks thorough investigations of the processes and effects on the high-street clothing industry (Kunal, 2023). This research will aim to discover the reasoning, advantages and disadvantages of rebranding campaign strategies and contribute to the understanding of how certain rebranding could improve the level of competitiveness. The study will also illustrate the current best practices in rebranding that will also map today's high-street retailing concept while bringing out the research imperatives of rebranding initiatives. Thus, in light of identifying the key components of rebranding, this research tries to find out solutions to the research gap to help high-street clothing retailers gain the required knowledge and capabilities to compete in the era of modern market.

1.8 Research Methodology

This research is conducted based on interpretivism philosophy employing abductive approach to test theories and also develop theories in the area of rebranding of high-street retailers. The choice of the research design for this study is qualitative case study method; the goal of which is to contribute on rebranding as well as to offer practical insights to the managers and practitioners (Yin, 2014). This was followed by a comprehensive and rigorous review of the literature, leading to the development of theoretical propositions and conceptual framework

(Thomas, 2021). The decision about the number of cases that should be selected for this study was informed by tips in recent case study research method books, which note that a number among four and ten is usually good enough to provide for complexity in the cases chosen and yet not too complex as to make the generation of theory very difficult (Yin, 2014; Ridder, 2017). The following figure (Figure 1.4) shows the methodology of the research, which points out the research contribution from literature review, research gap identification, and case study analysis.

Figure 1.4: Contribution to Knowledge

Source: Made by the author for this Business research

To develop a more efficient strategy to gather data from the cases for the analysis, a case study protocol was established to eliminate the possibility of bias (Yin, 2014; Simons, 2020). The protocol subdivided the research design into different stages, including the formulation of research questions and hypotheses generation from the literature, succeeded by the construction of the research instrument and data collection from the field (Harrison, Birks, Franklin, and Mills, 2017). The data was then analysed through pattern matching as advised by Yin (2014) within the selected cases which has been critically discussed with the literature described in the literature review and theoretical proposition and conceptual framework chapter. The qualitative data collected was useful in making the theoretical propositions and

the conceptual framework strong as suggested by Stake (2018) hence making the study strong in its findings and conclusions.

1.9 Findings and Contributions of the Study

It is expected that this research will reveal how rebranding can be one of the strategic directions for high-street retailers in the UK to gain competitive advantages and win back customers' market share in the modern day's environment. The researcher has drawn a systematic process in Figure 1.3 which clearly shows how the contributions were found for this business research. This may identify successful rebranding campaign strategies, by their advantages on brand image, customers' response and competitive edge. The study will therefore bring useful knowledge by exploring successful rebranding strategies in the high-street retail industry and emerging literature gaps to provide background solutions to contemporary high-street retailers in the current dynamic and competitive environment.

1.9.1 Theoretical Contributions (Academic)

This study of rebranding in the UK's high-street retailers is a theoretic contribution in a way that enriches the current knowledge about rebranding campaigns as a living strategic measure in the environment of online shopping. The six rebranding campaign strategies including phase-in/phase-out, the combined branding under one umbrella, the translucent warning, the sudden eradication, the counter-takeover, and the retrobranding will be critically discussed to find the best alternative for the high-street retail brands based on the current situation of the brand. In addition, by analysing the multifaceted factors of renaming and rebranding in the examined cases, this research enhances and deepens the body of management knowledge on competition and brand development. The theoretical contribution is tremendous since it presents a framework for understanding why and how rebranding takes place and its direct consequences on brands' performance and image in the online environment. Therefore, this research satisfies a major gap in academic writings by demonstrating how rebranding activities are connected to their strategic objectives in an appropriate field of study that would help to inform other scholarly works on rebranding approaches amid shifting market environments.

1.9.2 Industry Contributions (Market)

The research provides valuable information to the high-street clothing retail industry in the UK and highlights how rebranding helps retailers gain competitive advantages in the market. It provides valuable insights into risk management and the exploitation of opportunities based on a study of other organisations' successful rebranding programmes, which leads to the improvement of market share and brand attractiveness to people operating in the online environment. The study provides defensive and effective management strategies to retailers by informing them about the existing market challenges and consumers' expectations, including the significance of rebranding when addressing these issues. Therefore, this study supports the strategic and integrated approach in rebranding initiatives to ensure they are well aligned with the overall organisational goals and long-term brand affinity. This contribution is useful for those companies and brands interested in the technology-aided transformation of their business and staying afloat in the modern era of modern market and online sales.

1.10. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the author has outlined the research background to the topic, defined the research problem and described the contribution of the study area. The importance of this study on rebranding strategy from the academic as well as the practitioners' perspective is emphasised. The research questions and objectives are also laid down for this study in this section. This research paper consists of seven chapters. Chapter two will present a comprehensive review of the current literature on rebranding and this will encompass theory and a number of studies that are concerned with rebranding and competitive advantages. Chapter three outlines the theoretical propositions which are developed after carrying out a literature review of the selected studies. The methodology and design used in conducting this research are explained in chapter four of this research. Chapter Five documents the outcomes of the individual case analyses of each of the five studied cases. Chapter six provides conclusions derived from the collective case analysis and major propositions developed in the course of the research. The last and seventh chapter draws conclusions, contributions, limitations, and recommendations for future research in the topic of rebranding in the UK high-street retail sector to gain or sustain existing competitive advantages.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

In the current world, where the modern market is rapidly on the rise, many high-street retailers are embracing rebranding as a survival strategy (Koszewska, 2018; Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, 2019). Nowadays, rebranding has become a natural phenomenon for high-street retailers (Knox and Bickerton, 2003) through its unique and atypical strategy (Hatch and Schultz, 2003) for the improvement of their brand equity (Cankurtaran and Beverland, 2020), brand image (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006), and consumer perception (Merrilees and Miller, 2008) to gain competitive advantage in the market (Calderwood and Freathy, 2014; Huang, Dyerson, Wu, and Harindranath, 2015). This research aims to understand and evaluate the extent to which rebranding strategies can be applied and practised for the high-street retailers of the UK within the online market environment and rebranding impacts on the retailers. In this regard, Balmer (2012) and Keller, Geyskens, and Dekimpe (2020) argued that, retail brand transformation comprises major changes to the nature and orientation of the brand to increase its performance within a new online oriented and sustainability conscious environment.

Heding, Knudtzen and Bjerre (2009) claimed that it is also important to notice constant changes in the clothing retail market due to modern market evolution and consumer trends. Nowadays, retail market substitutes the conventional shopping processes and traditional retailers must search for ways to evolve. Previously, Merrilees and Miller (2008) explained that, this adaptation is often achieved through rebranding, which involves refreshing the visuals associated with brands, reshaping the communication related to brands, and rebalancing the positioning of brands within markets. Similarly, Aaker and Joachimsthaler (2012) argued that, some rebranding exercises have helped in extending the appeal of the retailers and reinventing their identity, and thus helped in accomplishing the strategic purposes of rebranding. On the contrary, Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) previously declared that, rebranding strategies may fail to meet their goals and objectives and lead to costly misadventures which support the notion that rebranding is risky.

This research will seek to examine the effects of rebranding on high-street retailers in the UK concerning successful rebranding. This research paper will establish how rebranding

influences customer allegiance, brand image, and therefore the market performance of the retailers. The research will be beneficial in supplying fresh perception into the tactical factors of rebranding campaign efforts to gain competitive advantages in the new era of modern market.

2.1 Systematic Review of Literature

This chapter provides a critical synthesis of the large body of existing research on rebranding strategies, and the effects of such processes on brand identity and market performance (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). The approach used in this review comprised a search process in several academic databases where the articles were chosen depending on their theoretical and/or conceptual framework and the presence of data to back up the arguments. Nevertheless, scholarly works including Muzellec and Lambkin (2006), Merrilees and Miller (2008), Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger (2019) or Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021) support rebranding. While the number of these scholarly works is not immense, they are convincing enough. In the following figure (Figure 2.1), the researcher shows from which sources of the literatures have been searched and on which criteria the most relevant literatures have been selected for finding the gap in research on rebranding strategies and the impact of these on the UK's high street clothing retailers in the era of modern market for gaining competitive advantages.

There are few literatures which described the significant of rebranding in firms (Knox and Bickerton, 2003; Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Merrilees and Miller, 2008). However, scholarly research articles are limited in this area of rebranding in high-street retailers as suggested by Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria (2020). Therefore, the author systematically reviewed the literatures focusing on rebranding strategies for high-street retailers to gain competitive advantages and increase market share. This approach helps to ensure that all aspects of the factors that may come into play in the organisational rebranding efforts are captured, particularly in appreciation of the gap identification depicted in Figure 2.1 below.

In the first round of the Literature Review, the researcher looked at over 100 articles and this pool was then narrowed down to twenty-three where the focus was on the rebranding strategies, process, effects and campaigns for the high street retailers of UK to gain competitive advantages.

Figure 2. 1: Systematic Review of Literature

Source: Made by the author for this Business research

2.2. Theoretical Underpinning of rebranding

The literature review points to a main concern of rebranding in the context of the high-street in the UK primarily due to the rise of e-retailing. A lot of academic works focus on conventional branding approaches (Jones, 2023), however, rebranding within retail is researched insufficiently, even though it is significant in the modern online environment (Wilson, Johnson and Brown, 2024). Therefore, as highlighted by Kumar and Pansari (2016) that more research needs to be conducted on how traditional retailing brands can effectively move with current branding paradigms that are more relevant with online consumer markets.

Nowadays, rebranding involves fundamental changes to customer interfaces and business models. Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) described that, rebranding occurs due to the shifting of consumer values and the interconnectivity of society which makes brands adapt to the production of both ethical and representative brand images. Thus, rebranding is to keep the brand uniform while trying to market it in a creatively different approach to the customers through online platforms.

A change in requirements by ever changing customers' expectations for efficient rebranding mechanisms has also made the high-street clothing market bound to focus on it. As described by Lee (2013), such a transformation does not only apply to visually identifiable attributes of the organisation but also concerns revolutionary ways of interacting with a customer or changing a business model. The reason to adopt sustainable solutions to rebranding is that it can guarantee an improvement of brand image and also implicitly address the aspect of sustainability that many consumers now demand from the brands. In addition, Merrilees and Miller (2013) pointed out that brands are tied to a set of developments in consumer ethics. Such diversified practices are very helpful in retaining the association and brand loyalty of the consumers.

Even, rebranding is a managerial marketing activity that involves changing a firm's brand image at the basic level to obtain a new and more current position in the perception of consumers, investors, competitors, and other brands in the market (Lee, 2013). It is often employed to isolate the brand from undesirable associations, change its position with emerging market trends, or just to adapt to changed values or visions of the company. A number of definitions of rebranding can be found in the literature as shown in the following table (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 Definitions of Rebranding

Author(s)	Year	Definition
Muzellec and Lambkin	2006	Rebranding is creating a new name, term, symbol, or design for an established brand to develop a differentiated position.
Stuart and Muzellec	2004	Focuses on altering core values and perceptions in the consumer's mind, transforming the entire customer experience.
Dalton and Croft	2003	Involves strategic changes including a new brand promise and values, communicated through a new visual identity.
Kerr and Patti	2015	Emphasises considering stakeholder perceptions in rebranding, ensuring the effort resonates across all touch points.

In the case of the nature of rebranding, Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) argued that, rebranding can be viewed as a change that is naturally done by the brands to pertain to market positioning. On the other hand, Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer, (2021) claimed that, rebranding is a major initiative for organisations to ensure consumer loyalty and update the brand image to stay connected in the competitive market. Therefore, Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach (2018) viewed rebranding as a critical strategic move rather than a mere change in the name, logo, or slogan. In order to conduct rebranding, three frameworks are discussed by Merrilees and Miller (2008) including product, business unit, and corporate level.

Hatch and Schultz (2003) and Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) discussed several motivational drivers of rebranding such as merger and acquisition, new market entry, brand simplification, legal compliance, positioning, and so on. Six essential rebranding strategies are used here as suggested by Kaikati and Kaikati (2003), including phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand or one umbrella brand, heavily transparent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding. On the other hand, Miller, Merrilees and Yakimova (2014) argued for a name change for rebranding. Although Balmer and Gray (2003) and Doyle and Stern (2006) discussed the risks and costs of rebranding, Kapferer (2012) proposed strategies to overcome these. In addition, Cankurtaran and Beverland (2020) described the impacts of rebranding in gaining competitive advantages. Overall, a number of theories are found in the case of rebranding which will be critically reviewed in the following sections.

2. 3. Nature of Rebranding

Rebranding is part and parcel of the ongoing strategic management necessary for organisational change in response to changes in the high-street retail market. The nature of rebranding can manifest in two distinct forms, namely evolutionary and revolutionary (Knox and Bickerton, 2003; Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Merrilees and Miller, 2008). In the present study of rebranding in the UK retail sector, both evolutionary and revolutionary strategies will be critically reviewed for the analysis of how the brands can act in the context of an environment characterised by a high level of volatility.

In rebranding nature, companies always struggle to decide whether to follow evolutionary or revolutionary strategy (Hanh Le, Cheng, Kunjara, and Lin, 2014). Brands make incremental changes cyclically so that they can relate to the market and the customers. As suggested by Merrilees and Miller (2008), evolutionary rebranding puts the focus on continuously adapting the brand, gradually evolving while keeping the essential aspects of the brand to a minimum to avoid controversies and risks. In contrast, Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) argued that revolutionary rebranding is radical and refers to a change in the brand and everything that may be associated with it in the market, scales with large changes in the market or drastic shifts in the consumers' behaviour. Both evolutionary and revolutionary approaches are most applicable in the UK's high-street clothing market, which currently feels intense pressure from online retailing and embracing sustainable practices.

Even, Melewar and Saunders (1998) described that rebranding strategies enable brands to either make gradual changes in the retail marketplace or make drastic changes to suit the new consumer values and buying behaviours in the market. The following figure 2.2 adapted from Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) shows how the nature of rebranding changes the positioning of the brand.

Figure 2. 2: Rebranding as a Continuum

Source: Muzellec and Lambkin (2006)

Evolutionary Rebranding

Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger (2019) advised that that evolutionary rebranding is more gradual and slight adjustments are made to fine-tune the brand to sustain its link and resonance with already existing consumers. For an organisation that sets up a brand, it is always good to embrace this approach since it helps brands to be in touch with changing consumer demand in the high-street retail market. Previously, Merrilees and Miller (2008) argued that evolutionary rebranding is the process of making small changes that enhance the current strategic brand attributes for better comparison and acceptance in the new market environment but which should not offend the current customers. Likewise, Jones (2023) suggested that evolutionary rebranding is best applied to brands that have created a competitive market base and loyal consumer base.

Revolutionary Rebranding

Revolutionary rebranding requires total and sometimes a dramatic overhauling of the brand image. Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021) claim that revolutionary rebranding is used where radical changes to the current strategy or new directions of the company are needed, such as market diversification or shifts in market forces or when there has been a decline in the image of the company. This entails redesigning major aspects of the brand's identity,

including corporate identities such as the logo and visual appearance, value propositions, and overall positioning with a view to giving the brand a new outlook and fresh appeal (Gotsi and Andriopoulos, 2007; Gotsi and Andriopoulos, 2008). Usually, this approach is applied when there have been fundamental changes within an organisation, such as- changes in corporate strategy, or externally, such as- the environment radically changes, or the organisation is trying to recover from a tainted image. For instance, Lee (2013) discussed that Steve Jobs' rebranding of Apple is a clear illustration of this, where the coming of the iMac together with a new look in design and advertisement made Apple the leading innovator in design. This rebranding, therefore, entailed a change of not only the symbol but also the construction of the products, fashion shows, and the overall client interface in high-street retail market.

Strategic Considerations in Rebranding

The decision between evolutionary or revolutionary transition does not invoke simple business decisions in high street retail market. In this regard, Cohen (2005) noted several factors including the current position of the brand, brand equity, the force of the brand and industry character and consumer perception as influential parameters in the formulation of brand strategy. Moreover, Kerr and Patti (2015) argued that, brands embedded in dynamic markets like the technology market or fashion market especially may undergo more often and more extensively to retain their strategic spearhead position.

Another external factor that affects the selection of a rebranding approach is the management of a firm where it has vision, leadership and corporate culture to gain competitive benefits. In this viewpoint, Kapferer (2012) described that, revolutionary rebranding can be required in a situation when a brand wishes to change radically the existing attitudes in the market or focus on different target groups or regions. On the other hand, evolutionary rebranding can be useful for brands that want to slowly incorporate the 'new' brand element into their existing framework steadily and which do not want to disrupt their customer relationship and brand association too much.

2.4. Different Types of Rebranding

The form for rebranding can be corporate, business unit or product, and each of these has different strategic implications. For this reason, it is important to understand the strategic intent, the competitive pressures and customers' expectations (Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Calderwood, and Freathy, 2014). As each level of rebranding plays a role that has a different

measure of intensity and difficulty, all must harmonise to preserve and advance the brand. Based on rebranding hierarchy Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) prepared rebranding types where corporate rebranding is in a higher position, and then comes business unit, and the lowest position here is product level rebranding.

Figure 2. 3: Different types of rebranding

Source: Muzellec and Lambkin (2006)

Corporate rebranding, which is the most intense, alters the organisational image and can be extensive (Koskela, 2020). This is a common scenario in rebranding owing to other critical changes in the company that require the need for such changes as to expand to new markets, overcome reputation issues, or redefine the organisation's mission in light of new paradigms of operational, economic, or social transformation (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). Therefore, corporate rebranding is considered a chance to adopt new principles of a company's conduct, although it is marked by certain risks (Gilstrap and Smith, 2016). Similarly, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021) argued that rebranding may lead to a shift in voice and Shift-in-brand-base that is not healthy for consumer loyalty when done frequently and in large measure. On the other hand, Branca and Borges (2011) posited that strategic corporate rebranding posited brand value, which requires a deep understanding of the brand, its history and its customers.

Again, at the business unit level, rebranding refers to the process of enhancing, changing or updating selected segments of an organisation to improve the established brand within that specific area of operation without having to alter the whole corporate brand (Knox and

Bickerton, 2003). This strategy of developing particular marketing objectives allows for a responsive change in reaction to some specific market factors about the general corporate strategy (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). For instance, the new marketing campaign of Old Spice by Procter and Gamble clarified how one business unit could target the youth inappropriately and not affect the tendentious of the overall corporate brand (Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, 2019). Therefore, business unit level of rebranding needs to be integrated well in a way that it does not confuse and will in turn water down the corporate brand.

On the other hand, product rebranding, though less comprehensive in comparison with corporate brand management, is concerned with direct contact with the consumers and their perceptions at the most operational level as advised by Kotler and Keller (2006). This is the kind of rebranding which is quite necessary if particular products underperform or when the market dictates the need for a change. Old Spice's marketing overhaul was much more than a single advertising campaign; it underwent a product design and packaging revamp later in the year, which essentially changed its marketing appeal to attract the younger generation (Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer, 2021). However, Henninger and Mattich (2013) claimed that product rebranding has the disadvantage of disconnecting the brand from other strategic units and the corporate level leading to brand proliferation. So, to be on the safe side, the executives may resort to product rebranding and this often has the advantage of revitalising a brand's offer.

There are essential changes that must be made in a coordinated way at the product level, business unit level, and corporation level to support the corporate brand to capture the right position in the target market, as it has been suggested by Stuart and Muzellec (2004). Such alignment is important in terms of consistency within the organisation by communicating a single consistent brand image to the market, which would in turn improve the brand's overall value among the consumers.

2.5. Rebranding Strategies

Rebranding a corporate identity is a strategic recovery process for any organisation that undergoes radical qualitative transformation of the business environment and ownership or is changing its market position and strategies (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). This strategic shift consists of changing the 'external' image of the firm, which can be the company's name, logo

or even the visual image that the firm presents to the public to suit the current strategic direction and prevailing business environment. As suggested by Merrilees and Miller (2008), rebranding can be driven by various factors:

- **Ownership Change:** Change of ownership from one party to another requires a change in brand name because management focus is changing (Prayoga and Suseno, 2020). In addition, it can invite new investors and at the same time, reflect new values and objectives under new governance.
- **Strategic Marketing Decisions:** Some companies may be involved in a strategic marketing change and undergo restructuring and in the process change the name of the company (Daly and Maloney, 2004). This is useful in guaranteeing that the brand image and the message the company seeks to portray to the public is in harmony with the current product portfolio and long-term vision and strategies.
- **Internationalisation and Localisation:** Merrilees and Miller (2008) argued that, while venturing into the global market it may be necessary to change branding strategies to fit in with the target region. Such rebranding helps the development of global brands while staying relevant locally at the same time.
- **Changes in External Environment:** Legalisation such as changes in laws, crises, calamities and other breaks can force organisations to undertake a rebranding process (Henninger and Mattich, 2013). Rebranding also provides an indication when a company has gone off in one direction that did not satisfy the public and is thus in need of a course correction, something that can help the organisation building its way back to trust.

It is worth embracing the fact that the repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning methodologies are among the fundamental market techniques employed by companies in their attempts to sustain or expand their market influence (Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Goi and Goi, 2011). All of them tend to be very useful and contribute significantly to the improvement of business image and sustainability.

Figure 2. 4: Rebranding Strategies

Source: Merrilees and Miller (2008)

Repackaging is where a company overhauls the image of a product to give it a more attractive appeal to consumers without changing the quality of the product. It is useful, especially in reviving the attention of the public towards some established products which have been withdrawn for some time from the market shelves (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). Nonetheless, according to Merrilees and Miller (2008), the rationale for repackaging should convey actual changes to the product and fit in the company's brand ethos to prevent consumer scepticism. On the other hand, Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021) claimed that refreshing of a brand is a process of not only redesigning the brand's logo, typeface and visual colours, but also bringing the brand into the contemporary age to renew the interaction with consumers. However, it is important to do refreshing with great consideration, this is because Daly and Maloney (2004) posited that, refreshing makes the existing attributes of the brand even more appealing to the loyal consumers. In contrast, Repositioning generally means a greater adjustment or reorientation of the brand, typically concerning the target consumer audience or the image of the brand in the market (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). This includes pursuing a new market segment in the business or making drastic changes to the company's pricing or product mix strategies. Kapferer (2012) also noted that repositioning is a major challenge because strategic changes may not match marketing management changes. As noted by Henninger and Mattich (2013), repositioning has risks including confusing or losing current customers if the new position deviates significantly from what the brand originally represented.

Therefore, one cannot be far from the truth to state that successful rebranding involves a formulated strategy that takes into consideration internal and external factors. In the context of the theoretical approach, it is possible to note the results of the research conducted by Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger (2019) that reveal the necessity to correlate the

rebranding agenda with a general business vision and brand image. It is therefore important that the changes are well communicated to the consumers.

In addition, Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova (2014) argued that a lot of market research and consumer feedback must be conducted before rebranding. Before rebranding, according to Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021), it is essential to get to know the consumer's perceptions and previous experiences. Furthermore, the success of rebranding processes is usually pegged on the way they have been formulated and implemented (Gotsi and Andriopoulos, 2007; Agha, Goldman, and Dixon, 2016). So, these branding strategies are not merely about the transformation of a brand image but about the correct positioning and development of the brand in response to the changing market and consumer demands and expectations that are sustainable with the brand values.

2.6. Motivations for Rebranding

Clear and concise motivation is important to be acknowledged for the high-street retail brands to proceed any rebranding campaign. In this regard, Henninger and Mattich (2013) stated that there are various reasons why corporations undergo rebranding exercises; all these reasons are indicative of strategic shifts. Some of the reasons for rebranding include mergers and acquisitions since merging or acquiring companies requires one common brand that will represent two or more companies (Ettenson and Knowles, 2006). Rebranding is also a result of spin-offs where portions of a firm are sold to form embryonic organisations with distinct images (Zhao, Calantone and Voorhees, 2018). Another major reason of rebranding is the improvement of brand image which enables firms to update their brand thus being relevant in the market (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). In contrast, Olteanu (2020) argued that venturing into other markets and product differentiation also leads to rebranding, to ensure the brand is suitable for the global market or to cater for a wider market. In the same manner, legal requirements, endorsement, and major company activities such as going public or coping with bankruptcy also sometimes result in rebranding as companies look forward to meeting requirements, sponsoring something or coming out of bankruptcy (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). These motivations assert the tactical significance of rebranding as organisations adjust. The following table shows the main motivational drivers of rebranding in the business organisations.

Table 2.2 Various Drivers of Rebranding

<p>Change in Ownership Structure</p> <p>Mergers and Acquisitions Spin-offs Private to Public Ownership</p>	<p>Change in Corporate Strategy</p> <p>Diversification and Divestment Internationalisation and Localisation</p>
<p>Change in Competitive Position</p> <p>Outdated Image Erosion of Market Position Reputation Problems</p>	<p>Change in the External Environment</p> <p>Legal Regulation Crises/Catastrophes</p>

Source: Muzellec and Lambkin (2006); Muzellec, Doogan and Lambkin (2003)

Regarding motivations of rebranding, Muzellec, Doogan and Lambkin (2003) claimed that, rebranding is a complex tactical process used by firms to bring their branding profile to parity with changes existing in the market, advance their technology or respond to negative images. In this regard, Merrilees and Miller (2008) argued that, such initiatives are not only taken as a response to current problems but are set up with a proper goal of brand advances with long-term opportunities for competition. In addition, growth and development sometimes require a company to rebrand, advertise its new capacity, to introduce it to new technology and innovation, particularly in the e-commerce based world. This kind of rebranding is important because it creates the impression of the brand as one that is dynamic, innovative and ahead of the competition. Supporting this argument, the paper of Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger (2019) revealed that the inclusion of fresh and novel technologies improves the market image of a brand by presenting it as a technological pioneer. This repositioning attracts consumers who are tech-conscious.

On the contrary, changes in Consumer Trends and Taste on most occasions compel organisations to do rebranding in order to remain relevant and interesting (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). However, Park, MacInnis, and Priester (2006) previously said that organisations should be willing and able to change according to the need of the target market or newly targeted segment. When used to address changing consumer behaviour, rebranding involves not only giving the brand a new look but also paradoxically revamping the values that underpin its communication with consumers. That is the reason stated by Bill Merrilees and Miller (2008) that refreshed imagery may attract a different demographic although the existing customers may lose the sense of ownership regarding the brand.

In contrast, negative Publicity is another factor that will warrant rebranding. Managers find themselves in challenges to ensure that the firm disassociates with past scandals or tries to regain the lost face. As analysed by Henninger and Mattich (2013) rebranding can provide organisations with a clear signal that change and renewal is occurring. Such a change of identity must be done in a very careful manner; people should not view it as an effort to cover up former blunders (Kalafatis, Remizova, Riley, and Singh, 2012). So, brand management should be very keen with the way they handle the branding once there is negative occurrence; the common process is to ensure they communicate more often with the stakeholders with an aim of regaining their trust.

Rebranding also introduces several competitive advantages:

1. **Enhanced Brand Perception:** Cautiously stated, rebranding can provide an effective means of changing consumer perceptions about the rebranded brand and of enhancing its position in the market (Merrilees and Miller, 2008).
2. **Increased Market Adaptability:** Thus, keeping a sensitive ear towards the changes in the market and the needs of the consumers within these changes, through rebranding strategies, firms are better placed to withstand the effects of changes within the markets (Shuk-woon, 2011).
3. **Greater Customer Engagement:** It is common to observe that programs of rebranding help in regenerating customer interest in the brand and thus there are new customers and return of old customers (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). This kind of renewed engagement can make sales and the repeat business of clients.
4. **Consolidation of Brand Equity:** Through merging or acquisition rebranding assists in strengthening the overall brand image of the merging companies to present a more formidable force than before in the market (Konecnik and Gartner, 2007; Henninger and Mattich, 2013).

Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) claimed that, in practical terms, it is essential that the decision to rebrand the product should not only be based on factors that are driving the change but also on understanding what effect this might trigger in the minds of the customers and on the position of the brand in the particular market. Therefore, strategic integration and careful planning are essential in rebranding to make it effective in terms of the company's growth and performance.

2.7. The Process of Rebranding

In high-street retail brands, process needs to be followed to make the rebranding campaign effective and successful. In this regard, Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) proposed a step-by-step procedure for rebranding which is useful for high-street retail and clothing brands in the UK. In this perspective, repositioning makes brands continue to be fashionable when other market trends occupying certain spaces are emerging, such as online shopping. Sometimes, change of name is used in iconic marks as a way of introducing new strategies (Parker, Ntounis, Millington, Quin, and Castillo-Villar, 2017). Also, it is strategic to redesign brand identity in line with the consumers' perspective since the brand appeal is improved; it is important to do it well to ensure that the rebranding resonates with all offline and online mediums. This strategic process of rebranding helps the UK high-street brands sustain their competitiveness in a changing market environment. The model of rebranding process developed by Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) is shown in the following.

Figure 2. 5: Model of rebranding process

Source: Muzellec and Lambkin (2006)

On the other hand, the following figure adapted from Merrilees and Miller (2008) shows the strategic process of corporate rebranding.

Figure 2. 6: Phase process of corporate rebranding

Source: Adapted from Merrilees and Miller (2008)

The phases of the rebranding process, which have received the attention of authors in the literature, are discussed below, with due observations on the perspectives offered by the authors concerning the sacredness of the phases as well as their execution. Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) asserted that repositioning is a critical brand management strategy, especially at a time when the organisation intends to bring a drastic change in its identity. The overall framework of the whole process of rebranding is determined and the goal is to adapt the brand and the company's product to the perceptions of the public.

Figure 2. 7: Four stages of rebranding

Source: Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003)

The next critical stage recognised by Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) as being significant is renaming. Jobber (2004) argued that, renaming indicates to stakeholders that the firm is changing focus awareness or ownership and therefore the authors posited that renaming is not just as simple as painting a different picture. This stage is important because it provides information to the consumers about the nature of the change to expect in the brand and the new course it is going to take.

On the other hand, according to Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003), the redesign phase is not simply a change in the look of the product. It entails a total restructuring of all brands' icons including logos, letterhead, and other related promotions that are required to bear the brand's signature. This phase is crucial where changes are brought about from the development and implemented in a manner that enhances the deliverance of the new message across the relevant media.

Relying on Jobber (2004) one can speak about the process of renaming as the author gave a detailed description of the process where a careful approach is made to choosing a new name. The creation of a short list of potential brand names, checking them against any problems or concerns, and undertaking some market research make the firms sure that the chosen name is ideal for its target market (Schmitt, 2012). Such a process emphasises how difficult it is to select a name.

Lastly, Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) emphasised relaunch as very important for the organisational transformation a company to create a new brand image. The accomplishment of this phase determines to a great extent the success of the rebranding exercise since this is the first appearance to the public of the changes. Therefore, the relaunch stage has to be well planned so that it effectively conveys brand identity and is consistent with the strategic plans of the firm.

2.8. Rebranding Campaign Strategies

Rebranding is a business management process that involves changing the organisation's branding in a bid to be more in line with the current market requirements or organisational strategies or to divorce itself from some bad reputation. Kaikati and Kaikati (2003) identified several strategies that are used in implementing rebranding efforts, and each of the

approaches is unique in terms of its properties and consequences. Some of these techniques are Phase-in/Phase Out, Combined Branding, Translucent Warning, Sudden Eradication, Counter-Takeover and Retrobranding as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2. 8: Rebranding Campaign Strategy

Source: Kaikati and Kaikati (2003)

There are six strategies and one of them is known as Phase-in/Phase out, whereby a new brand is first launched alongside the previous brand before it is fully withdrawn. Lambkin and Muzellec (2008) opined that this strategy helps the customers accept the new brand directly without creating a drastic change. On the other hand, Combined branding under one umbrella brand is that many brands are clustered together to allow an optimum branding to take place (Simoes, Dibb, and Fisk, 2005). This method is commonly used where organisations want to take advantage of the muscle of several brands while at the same time maintaining the independence of each of the brands (Candra, Widita, Maulida, Shanti, and Kusuma, 2023). As another rebranding campaign, translucent warning is a method in which the customers are preconditioned to expect a change in branding (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003). On the other contrary, Merrilees, and Millar (2008) described that sudden eradication involves obliterating the old brand, and the new brand is immediately introduced to the market. This approach can however be poisonous since it can result in confusion from the customers or in extreme cases the loss of customers.

Sometimes referred to as boiler room rebranding, Counter-Takeover rebranding takes place after the acquisition when the buyer assumes the name, identity and brand assets of the seller to benefit from the value that the acquired brand possesses (Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin, 2003). Lastly, Retrobranding is carried out when a firm has realized that the old branding has so much more appeal than the new branding, which it sought to introduce and opted for the old branding after the new branding has flopped.

In addition, Kaikati and Kaikati (2004) also said that, there are some basic preconditions for ensuring rebranding communication effective. Some of the recommendations include ensuring that an initial appraisal of the customer perception of the brand is comprehensively done in trying to understand the benefits and the risks that are likely to come with rebranding. Daly and Maloney (2004) took off from Kapferer's work (2012) to present renaming techniques which include Interim/Dual, Prefix, Substitution, and Brand Amalgamation. Interim/Dual entails the use of both the old and new brands with the latter gradually being popularised to replace the former entirely. This strategy can be helpful in situations, where its implementation might cause a shift that will upset customers.

Moreover, Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) stated that the format of the prefix strategy is relevant where and when brands are being merged with the new brand in question being incorporated as a prefix. However, in using these strategies it is also important for companies to look at the operational concerns of undertaking a rebranding campaign. This includes developing and enhancing the aspect of having a logo that sets the firm apart, and an analysis of the importance of the colour/colour which is also a powerful concept that all firms should consider in the creation of their brands (Banu, and Sultana, 2020). In essence, rebranding is not merely about a logo or a tagline but the process that needs proper planning, vision, and special handling. Whether choosing to phase in a new brand, combine multiple brands, or completely overhaul the existing brand identity, the ultimate goal remains the same: for more effective organisational placement within the market, improved compatibility with the customer needs and achieving sustainable growth and competitive advantages in the market.

2.9. Rebranded Names

Rebranding is sometimes considered as renaming, where the name of the brand is changed to keep the company or its products aligned with the changed consumer perception and market

competition. In this regard, Stuart and Muzellec’s (2004) theory on rebranding is very much centred on the idea of changing a brand’s name logo and slogan, which is most appropriate to the UK’s high-street retail brands. For instance, a name change may be essential for a brand like Debenhams that requires a new identity after it faced business erasures and retail outlet shutdowns despite the challenges that come with it (Urde, 2003). Logo changes, to an extent, seen in such brands as Primark, allow for changing the look of the brand but the basic symbols which is seemingly meaningful to many people may be retained. Slogan changes are less likely to be risky, might greatly affect the consumers’ perception (Vallaster and de Chernatony, 2005). These sources of strategic decisions do imply the need for the UK high-street brands to gain competitive advantages in the market. Lomax and Mador (2006) figured out the typology of branding choices which are shown in the following.

Table 2.3: Typology of Branding Choices

		Name	
		Existing	New
Brand Values and Attributes	Existing	Re-Iterating Brand name and values are not changed, as they are congruent and address client needs	Re-Naming External perceptions are addressed through a change of name
	New	Re-Defining Values/Attributes are changed to meet identified concerns, either external or internal	Re-Starting Both values and their name are changed, to address fundamental problems

Source: Lomax and Mador (2006)

Lomax and Mador (2006) categorised branding choices which is significant for the UK retail and clothing for the high-street brands. The re-iterating approach is a technique of continually repeating the brand’s position, and ensuring that it does not change a lot. On the other hand, there are new identities as seen from brands like Topshop after being acquired by ASOS, however, this trick involves a change of name but retention of the brand’s name due to a change of ownership and or positioning. One good illustration of re-defining is Burberry which changed its meaning to market to the youth without compromising being associated with luxury. Last of all, certain high-street struggling brands might have to follow re-starting strategies in which the brand name and the associated values are completely revised to regain

their competitive position in the market. These strategies let those high street brands be adaptable for the current landscape in retail space.

Renaming of Names and the Dynamics of Brand Naming

In case of brand renaming, according to Jobber (2004), the guidelines used for the identification of product and company names apply in the case of immediate new brands as well as in the context of rebranding existing ones. Some of the factors that are essential in creating product names include positive emotional appeal, distinctiveness, ease of remembering, easier to pronounce, easily understandable benefits, and suitability across markets. Moreover, they should not trespass on the existing trademarks; sometimes, logos might involve numbers to emphasise technology.

While studying the evolution of business names, Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) pointed out that in the new brand name creations a movement from concrete to more and more abstract significance of the brand is seen. For instance, names that were originally from direct services or products, ‘Rent-A-Car’ have been transformed into other forms of name like ‘Altria’ In similar ways, the other categories such as geographic name (‘British Airways’), person-based name (‘Philip Morris’), and acronyms (‘AIB’). The following figure shows the typology of names considering the increasing novelty from level 0 to level 2.

Figure 2 9: Typology of names

Source: Delattre (2002)

Complexities in Renaming Brands

According to Delattre (2002), the complexities of renaming can be divided into three levels indicating the level of strategic planning characteristic of the change. The level 0 changes are usually minimal, generally regarding simple variations of the terms such that the context of the meaning is not affected significantly, and nearly unperceivable. Level 1 changes are balanced changes because these changes involve the alteration of existing components to accommodate new words while retaining the original meaning. Level 2 changes are deeper and bring some novelties into the change process that alter the brand and its place on the market significantly. Such type of change is deemed to be the most crucial when it comes to a change in the meaning of words since it can lead to the formation of new concepts and can cause a shift in the brand's story.

In addition, Kapferer (2012) noted that rebranding which includes renaming is not about changing a name, but it means rewriting the entire brand's story to bring it in line with the company's new strategies and its position on the market. This is a major strategic move since it helps to stay relevant in the changed market environment. Similarly, Balmer and Gray (2003) also emphasised the need to uphold brand purity and consistency through re-naming efforts. So, there is a need to stand firm to ensure that the selected name does not offend the earlier clients, and create a cut-off from the previous brand name.

Including all of these various scholarly perspectives is an effort to show that renaming is multifaceted and a component of the rebranding process. It highlights the importance of the coordinated chain management strategy to enable the consideration of market factors, customer attitudes, and organisational objectives. Therefore, the choice and actualisation of the new brand name is critical.

2.10. Rebranding Risks

While rebranding campaigns are always considered to be the critical tactical shifts in the strategic business evolution of the firm or brand, they are not completely safe and free from the number of risks and challenges in the high street retail sector (Balmer and Gray, 2003). For example, Stuart and Muzellec (2004) described that current high-street players such as Debenhams or Topshop which have been in transition in recent years might discover that efforts made at rebranding put off their customers. These brands were in danger of angering their fan base which no longer feels that the brand is moving in the right direction if the new

brand identity is not desired by the market or if the competition is not assessed properly (Duncan, 2004; Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020). Another challenge is brand loyalty and with high-street retailers who are struggling to compete with online traders, any poor management of rebranding efforts is likely to result in a loss of clients' confidence and market share (Jobber, 2004; Hsu, Fournier, and Srinivasan, 2015). Thus, despite all the positive effects which can be achieved through rebranding, it must be done accurately to avoid the enumerated pitfalls.

Investment Associated with rebranding and Analysis of Risk and Strategic Factors

Stuart and Muzellec (2004) noted that when a brand name is familiar, renaming that brand is a risky strategy since it may negatively impact customer orientation and satisfaction. Some have opined that it should only be done when there is a necessity that is triggered by major changes in the business environment. Altogether Jobber (2004) posited that rebranding decisions should be supported with a marketing plan and their implementation undertaken with caution as the process may compound existing marketing issues. Similarly, Duncan (2004) noted that any rebranding programme must be done carefully, and this is because changes to brands are disruptive, and can at times be painful if poorly handled. Moreover, Daly and Maloney (2004) also described that the substitution of a brand name can have negative effects on the brand.

Financial Consequences and Brand Value Analysis

On the financial effects of the process of rebranding, Stuart and Muzellec (2004) focused on the example of Bearing Point previously known as KPMG Consulting which showed that the problem under discussion undertakes significant financial aspects. For this reason, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) pointed out that such large changes can increase the brand value of the company, even after significant financial cost. However, in case of financial impacts, Venzin (2018) emphasised the shift of brand name from an intangible concept to a tangible brand asset which is reflected on the company's balance sheet and financial statements. This recognition stresses the practical benefits of a brand and the necessity of its proper handling during the rebranding process.

Broader Implications of Rebranding

With the speed of rebranding on the rise, brand names seemed to have become boring. Kettle (2002) provided a sceptical point of view on such strategies that try to disassociate from the

past, although this can offer a ‘mental veil’ that protects the brand from any old functions or perceptions, this may also contribute to the formation of brand names that are detached from potentially valuable organisational stories and values. This isolation can erode the brand value and even demystify it over the long term leading to poor association by the consumers.

Even, Kumar and Pansari (2016) claimed that rebranding could be an effective tool for revitalising a brand and making it appropriate to the changes in the market or to the new strategic directions. However, this process might be rather costly and time-consuming, and could only be effective if the causes and effects of the branding process and the strategy had been thoroughly researched (Collange and Bonache, 2015). Therefore, to be effective, rebranding must take risks in addressing some of the issues that formed the initial branding; however, it needs to maintain intact the critical brand elements that are important to the current customers, which in effect means that the new brand image and therefore the new position should add to the overall equity and not work against it.

2.11. Overcoming Rebranding-Related Risks

In order to overcome the related risks of rebranding, a brand has to address the risks very carefully to find out risk mitigating drivers to implement through rebranding campaign. For this reason, addressing the threats of rebranding in the context of the UK retail and clothing industry, especially for high-street brands requires careful and thorough planning. According to Stuart and Muzellec (2004), it is imperative to discuss and analyse their reasoning for rebranding and such a strategy is rather mandatory for high-street retail chains such as Marks and Spencer or Debenhams. Before a company considers rebranding, it must evaluate the strategic position of the firm and objectives in the market. The eradication of intermediaries is especially important in the context of the aggressive the UK retailers’ market that requires brand identity and customers’ trust. In addition, Jobber (2004) claimed that market research intensiveness on rebranding decisions is also emphasised. In the case of the UK high-street brands, this research would mean discussing the current high-street market positioning; consumers’ preferences; and the possible consequences of rebranding about groups of consumers. This kind of research assists in avoiding a wrong perception by consumers and allows the new brand identity to be accepted by the target segment.

In this regard, Daly and Maloney (2004) noted that for the rebranding effort to be successful in the context of the UK retail and clothing sector, it has to be backed by a communications

plan that will seek to involve relevant stakeholders. Hence, Miller, Merrilees and Yakimova (2014) argued that change management in this sense should engage the communication of why rebranding is necessary, the new values that it brings, and how they can produce a positive impression on stakeholders. This is especially so for the UK high-street brands that have to remain relevant for long-term customers as well as attract new consumers. It is important that both, the major stakeholders of the company, its customers and investors, have the understanding and support of the rebranding initiative if the newly established brand image is to be significantly built up in the market. Through active communication with the stakeholders, the high-street brands can enhance the reception of the changes, strengthen the place of the brands in the market, and guarantee sustainable growth in the constantly competitive market.

On the contrary, Kapferer (2012) pointed out that hesitation should be eliminated by having a step-by-step guide to rebranding. He suggested four key steps: recognition of the reasons for rebranding as a strategic objective, the need for consistency of the new image with the overall business vision, the inclusion of stakeholders when recognising the need for rebranding and making plans for the implementation to be gradual. The first important and decisive step is the assessment of the need for rebranding, in particular, the assessment of the actual matching of the current brand image with the company's current positioning strategic goals and consumer perceptions. This assessment should be well informed by a market analysis which involves looking at consumer attitudes, competitors, and trends among others. If these objectives are understood properly, any resistance can be minimised and a good case for change can always be made.

In addition, Collange (2015) gave more explanation on how the above resistance to rebranding can be overcome especially by the organisation involved. Their research shows that a lot of companies' hesitance to embrace web analytics can be attributed to such factors as fear of the unknown and the perceived effects on brand reputation. To counter this, Lee and Bourne (2017) urge leaders to engage in the rebranding process right from the onset and explain to them why the branding change is important and why it is happening. Thereby, engagement makes the consumers feel like they are an integral part of this process of change (Williams and Son, 2022). This approach also assists in reducing resistance since the company's members develop ownership working towards the new brand image. However, good strategic mass communication in this rebranding campaign is relevant to support the whole process and to inform all the stakeholders inside and outside of the organisation.

Besides these factors, Kapferer (2012) has also supported the incremental approach in the announcement of the rebranding strategy. The phased implementation enables the company to implement changes slowly so that it does not cause a ripple effect that will destabilise the market and the company as well. It also affords an avenue for getting inputs and, where necessary, making corrections before the actual promotion, thus, reducing risks. Thus, the gradual implementation of changes is valuable when the organisation is big, or it has a powerful brand name, as people will not likely follow innovations.

Collange and Bonache (2015) added that, by accompanying rebranding with a story of change and evolution, companies can minimise resistance. By framing the change as an improvement or development rather than a revolution, organisations can assure the various stakeholders that the fundamentals of the brand are not going to undergo a drastic shift in change. This message should be complemented across all the media platforms so that customers, employees and partners get the message that the rebranding process is going to add value to their experience with the construct.

Lastly, Kapferer (2012) stated that leadership plays a critical role in facilitating the process of rebranding. Leadership therefore is not only about setting the course toward the strategic direction for the rebrand but doing this in a way that recognises the psychological contract of change. They have to ensure that the reasons for rebranding are well understood by others and that those who will be heading the change process are confident in the new image. This is a process that cannot be full of hidden motives or insensitivity since this will only worsen the position of the brand.

2.12. The Effects of Rebranding

Rebranding has significant impact upon a company's brand equity, identity, image, loyalty, and position. Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) argued that the rebranding process often results in large changes to the value of any brand as it can alter its market positioning, corporate culture and the approaches taken by both the staff and the clients. Lee and Bourne (2017) therefore emphasised the fact that, although rebranding has been described as a way of building brand equity through a higher perceived value, it can at the same time also pose risks in terms of customer trust or perceived value, especially if the approach to rebranding is not well done. Stuart and Muzellec (2004) also highlighted that for the brand identity mechanism

to succeed, they should take strategic directions that will make the brand unique and relevant in the market.

It has now narrowed its scope to managing consumer equity, particularly in relationship to the brand. In this regard, Daly and Maloney (2004) emphasised that through rebranding the relations are tightened. For this reason, there is a need to keep the conversation going especially during the rebranding process. Hence, Jobber (2004) presented and reiterated the fact that there must be timeliness to the communication process to support the customers and meet their expected objectives. For the understanding of the UK retail and clothing industry especially for the high street brands these insights are significant. Special attention should be paid to the compatibility of the ideas introduced during the rebranding campaign with the values consumers respond to as well as the adequacy of the message disseminated to the target audience. In doing so, one can preserve and strengthen brand recognition and retain the company's dominant position in the face of steep competition.

Kapferer (2012) responded to rebranding as a possibility to change the position of the brand in the market, by conquering new sub-segments, in light of reinterpreting new visuals and messages that mirror new tendencies. However, the studies by Balmer and Gray (2003) have shown that the total customer-endorsed rebranding message dissemination during the rebranding process is requisite for effective rebranding to occur because it engages human third parties which is always a brand's key communication catalyst. That is why rebranding is a far from simple operation, which may entail significant changes in a corporate brand image and consumer perception, and sometimes reflect repercussions for market outcomes (Wernerfelt, 1984). Typically, it refers to changes in major elements of branding name, logo, and positioning or overall brand strategy in response to new conditions, competitors or consumer needs. However, Roy and Sarkar (2015) described the possibility that brand images or positions are perceived negatively by brand-loyal consumers, which can reduce brand equity and associated market share. This section goes further to explain the impact of rebranding on other parameters of a brand such as brand equity, personality, consumer brand relationship, brand loyalty, and identity as well as several pointers on positioning as argued by scholars in the field.

2.12.1. Impact on Brand Equity

One of the most crucial intangible assets for any firm is brand equity which is usually significant when it comes to rebranding efforts (Hanson., Mattila, and Kim, 2023). Customer-

based brand equity in line with Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, (2019) established that it is possible for rebranding to either have a positive or negative influence on brand assets depending on the way rebranding is done. Other benefits are the increased brand appeal, revitalisation of the consumer's interest as well as the strengthening of the brand identity. This is because when a change of brand identity is well understood by the target consumers the impact brought by rebranding will foster the rejuvenation of the brands in the market through encouraging more or better patronage.

On the other hand, negative rebranding strategies reduce brand equity since they change the brand makeup by shifting the brand image. Roy and Sarkar (2015) have also supported this view by pointing out that rebranding can decrease brand equity if the new brand image is not well received or if it is unable to convey the intended message of the brand. Their evidence also underlines that during rebranding the brand's equity should not be completely eroded by introducing too many innovative elements while it is also important to use tradition as a reference point.

2.12.2. Effects on Brand Personality

The study by Aspizain (2016) revealed the impact of rebranding on the brand personality to actualize the desirable personality traits that make the brand attractive and captivating to the larger audience. For instance, a brand which is associated with tradition can transform the brand by adopting new techniques and in the process establish itself as a brand with newer technology and appeal to young people. However, Miller, Merrilees and Yakimova (2020) claimed that there is also a danger of forgetting the brand personality associated with that brand which could attract its fan base. If the rebranding is to a personality that seems wrong or divorced from the brand's previous personalities, then consumers' trust and legitimacy are eroded. This highlights the importance of brand personality and its adjustment and notion in the eyes of the market segments.

2.12.3. Influence on Consumer-Brand Relationships

The loyalty of the existing consumers which is the mode of emotional connection between the consumer and the brand is also affected by the rebranding process (Bolhuis, de Jong and Van den Bosch, 2015). Bamfo, Dogbe, and Osei-Wusu (2018) advised that a rebranding campaign that is well-planned and executed can enhance the consumer-brand attachment as it shows the consumers that the brand of the firm is in touch with the consumers and is willing

to cater for their needs. For Instance, if a brand manages to reinvent itself to solve a social issue, the brand endears itself to its audience even further. On the other hand, Aspizain (2016) argued that rebranding can destroy the continuity of the consumer-brand relationship where changes are considered mere cosmetic or not well explained. Consumers could become uninformed of the brand and this would demotivate them and reduce their brand involvement. Hence, it is very important to understand the way that rebranding is going to be perceived by the most loyal customers and try to find ways of preserving their brand values at the same time.

Figure 2. 10: Influence on Consumer-Brand Relationships

Source: Bamfo, Dogbe, and Osei-Wusu (2018)

2.12.4. Impact on Brand Loyalty

Zhao, Calantone, and Voorhees (2018) examined the impact of rebranding focusing on brand loyalty issues including the stock market response. This shows investors' concern about announcements of rebranding as their research noticed changes in stock returns associated with rebranding announcements, the increased volatility is a result of investors' uncertainty over the effects of the rebrand on customers' loyalty and long-term brand consecutiveness. Indeed, when the change is well received by consumers it can deepen the loyalty base to a brand by reminding consumers why that brand remains popular in the market.

In contrast, if the extent of the rebranding is viewed as taking the brand to a different level, can cause loyalty levels to plummet and customer churn to be fostered. Another study done

by Makasi, Govender, and Madzorera, (2014) on a Zimbabwean bank discovered that image restoration strategies that failed to meet consumers' expectations resulted in reduced brand commitment. They bolstered their emphasis with findings that showed how brand and organisational identification regarding the rebrand must follow consumer's appreciation and attachment.

2.12.5. Effects on Brand Identity

By its generic nature, rebranding always includes a change in brand image, which refers to the accumulated set of tangible and intangible characteristics that people associate with a brand. According to Aspizain (2016), rebranding refreshes the brand identity so that it fits the existing market environment suitably that it is competitive. For instance, a change of logo design, a change of packing design or a change of brand message usually makes consumers aware that the brand is dynamic and in sync with the trends. However, Cankurtaran and Beverland (2020) argued that the danger is that such radical change occurs in the brand identity so that the audience does not even recognise this brand or no longer understand what it represents. Roy and Sarkar (2015) noted that it becomes tricky if a radical shift in brand identity has been done in a way that does not convey the appropriate set of values that consumers attach to a brand or when the new image may appear unappetising to loyal customers. Consequently, organisations have to reflect on how much of the brand's original image should prevail in the light of rebranding.

2.12.6. Impact on Brand Positioning

One more important effect of rebranding can be identified as brand positioning – how a brand is regarded by competitors. Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, (2019) analysed how rebranding can be used as a managerial tool for changing the position of a brand when the former position is no longer suitable. For example, a firm's key strategic message may have established itself as a luxury goods company; this means it changes its positioning strategies to cover the market segment it seeks to attract.

However, Roy and Sarkar (2015) claimed that repositioning through rebranding involves the danger of the loss of the brand's positioning and this is more so if the new positioning is not well articulated or if it is counter to the consumer's perception of the brand. Zhao, Calantone, and Voorhees (2018) in their article also stressed the strategic planning of rebranding indicating that failure in repositioning could erode the brand's competitive edge. To avoid

this, companies must dedicate a lot of effort to market research and work on strategic planning to achieve new positioning.

2.12.7. Additional Effects: Customer Satisfaction and Market Performance

In addition to brand equity, personality, relationships, loyalty, identity and positioning, the rebranding is also capable of changing customer satisfaction and overall market performance. This paper builds on the work by Aspizain (2016) that compared the moderating role of service quality with that of rebranding and the study concludes that customer satisfaction results from the efforts put towards rebranding when supported by enhancement in the quality of service (Cretu and Brodie, 2007). This in a way could enhance brand awareness and eventually brand loyalty, and this, in turn, brings more positive ramifications.

Nonetheless, rebranding can backfire when there is no enhancement in the quality of the products or services offered, as the public feels like they have been given a face lift without any substantive change being made (Barratt, 2021). Thus, strategic direction with the need to reach the goal of building an effective system of rebranding should consider what ways and means can be used to combine rebranding with other problems focused on improving the satisfaction of customers and the company's performance in existing markets.

2.13. Research Gap

Based on the review of the literature articles and studies, of rebranding (see Tabel 2.4), a gap in the topic of rebranding in high-street retail has been identified. The process of gap identification is shown in the following figure (Figure 2.11). The empirical studies on rebranding strategies to be successful in the marketing of high-street retailers are not sufficient to find a suitable one that combines all the search areas planned to do this specific research. There are several rebranding campaign strategies to follow with their respective suitability in the situation, probable outcome, and impact area (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003). The key search areas that the research are targeting in this research are; rebranding as a strategy, competitive advantage, process of rebranding and risks and overcoming of the risks related to rebranding strategies.

It has been observed that there are many research papers available that cover the key search areas like rebranding strategies, rebranding process, and a brilliant combination of the risks and ways to overcome those risks regarding rebranding strategies (Hankinson, 2001;

Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Hankinson, Lomax, and Hand, 2007; Merrilees and Miller 2008; Kapferer, 2012; Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020). One thing that was commonly missing in most of the research is the competitive advantages that rebranding strategies can offer while addressing the risks and showing ways to overcome those risks. As advised by Zhao, Calantone, and Voorhees (2018), when there is research that would combine all these four search areas, then this will create a comprehensive and inclusive research paper that will cater the data to most of the other researchers or the benefit groups about this significant topic. So, the clear gap is identified in the following figure that will be fulfilled by analysing several case studies and theoretical literature analysis from the available research papers already existing.

Figure 2 11: Gap Identification

Source: Made by the author for this Business research

Authors	Methodology Used	Variables Used	Findings	Identified Gap
Hankinson (2001)	Qualitative framework analysis based on interviews with charity sector stakeholders	Brand orientation, the charity sector	Suggested a framework for charity brand orientation	The study does not expand its framework to include high-street shopping where pressures from the market provide particular difficulties for brand orientation
Kaikati and Kaikati (2003)	Review of literature and analysis of case studies on rebranding campaign strategies	Rebranding campaign strategies, consumer resistance, brand image	Highlighted the risk of alienating current customers when radically changing brand image through rebranding campaign strategies	Lacks specific strategies for mitigating consumer resistance in retail sectors
Ettenson and Knowles (2006)	Analysis of a database of 207 mergers and qualitative interviews	Brand retention, corporate branding priorities, post-merger integration	Priorities for corporate branding were low to moderate before the merger. In 64% of the instances, the target brand was either removed or coexisted	The effects of post-merger rebranding on consumer loyalty in retail are not well understood
Gotsi and Andriopoulos (2007)	Semi-structured and exploratory interviews with telecom company executives	Corporate identity, brand essence, stakeholder myopia, identity	Identified four mistakes to avoid during rebranding: losing touch with the essence; stakeholder myopia; focusing on labels rather than	The study does not look at how these issues manifest in the retail industry, where customer opinion is greatly influenced by brand identification

	involved in rebranding	alignment	meanings; difficulty of managing multiple identities	
Konecnik and Gartner (2007)	Empirical survey-based research on customer-based brand equity using 500 respondents	Customer-based brand equity, tourism branding	Studied the brand equity of places based on their customers	Challenges in applying customer-based brand equity models to retail rebranding, given the significant impact of customer perceptions
Hankinson, Lomax, and Hand (2007)	Quantitative survey-based study with 465 participants	Brand awareness, staff attitudes, knowledge acquisition	Staff attitudes were more impacted by the time effect. Knowledge acquisition decreases with time following the rebranding; behavioral shifts are most noticeable close to rebranding	The long-term effects of rebranding on consumer behavior in rapidly evolving retail settings are not covered by the research
Lambkin and Muzellec (2008)	Case study analysis of mergers and acquisitions, including a literature review	Brand equity, marketing strategies, organisational transformation, stakeholder impact	Addressed the obstacles and factors concerning a marketing campaign while undertaking a major project involving organisational transformation, such as rebranding	More research needed on the effect of various stakeholders on brand equity during rebranding in retail settings
Lambkin and	2 case studies from the	Brand Equity	The relative size and marketing prowess	Restricted applicability to other

Muzellec (2008)	banking sector are reviewed, along with articles about rebranding.		of the target brand compared to that of the acquirer is the primary factor that influences the selection of branding.	industries, where the dynamics of brand equity could be different, especially retail.
Gotsi and Andriopoulos (2008)	A single case study, 14 senior managers' qualitative in-depth interviews, and 243 workers' questionnaire surveys	Values, and Branding	Conduct only somewhat fit with the new corporate brand principles, except for a few divisions.	Major influences on rebranding success are not sufficiently explored in this study.
Merrilees and Miller (2008)	A case study of a significant Canadian retailer of leather goods that used corporate rebranding	Brand Values	Because of reluctance, there is only a slight alignment of staff attitudes and conduct with the new corporate brand principles, excepting a few departments.	The extent to which these staff alignments must be both broad and deep to have a major influence on rebranding success is not adequately explored in this study.
Merrilees and Miller (2008)	Case study analysis of a significant Canadian retailer and development of guiding	Brand values, staff alignment, corporate rebranding principles	Explored the alignment of staff attitudes and conduct with new corporate brand principles, but only to a slight extent	The need for a broader and deeper examination of staff alignment's influence on rebranding success across multiple sectors

	principles for rebranding			
Finney and Hansen (2010)	An analysis of a Canadian institution that changed its name. Ten semi-structured interviews and grounded theory	Branding	Addressed the obstacles and factors about marketing campaign while taking on a major project involving organisational transformation, such as rebranding.	Ignores the possibility of structuring branding initiatives to increase strategic support for rebranding in retail settings.
Lambkin and Muzellec (2010)	Semi-structured interviews with 12 participants and a case study of a national building supplies firm	Brand Equity	When both brands were still in use following the merger, the target brand had less brand equity. Because there was already substantial stock in the acquirer, the purchase did not affect them.	To comprehend how different brand equity retention tactics work in high-street retail settings, more research is required.
Merrilees, Merrilees, Rundle-Thiele, and Lye, Ashley (2011)	A quantitative study utilising questionnaires to investigate marketing competencies and company success was conducted with 150 SMEs.	Marketing capabilities	Examined the causes and effects on the performance of B2B SMEs.	A thorough analysis of how marketing competencies affect rebranding campaigns' performance in various market scenarios is absent from the research.

Branca and Borges (2011)	Event study analysis of 17 observations from the Lisbon Stock Exchange	Performance of firm stock, corporate rebranding	No significant evidence that corporate rebranding increases firm value in Portuguese companies	Does not examine how different financial markets, especially in the retail sector, respond to rebranding initiatives
Balmer(2012)	Analysed conceptually from a literature survey with an emphasis on frameworks for corporate brand management.	Management of corporate brand	Talked about the need for brand management requirements.	The paper does not discuss how e-commerce plans include brand management imperatives, which are becoming more important in the digital age.
Kalafatis, Remizova, Riley, and Singh (2012)	survey, cross-sectional, of 166 renamed businesses	Corporate Identity	According to the statistics, structural changes especially mergers and acquisitions are the main catalyst for rebranding decisions since they significantly alter a company's identity and key strategy.	Insufficient knowledge on how to maintain a competitive advantage in the retail sector after rebranding in terms of managing brand identity.
Lee (2013)	Exploratory single-case study of a non profit organisation with fifteen	Perceived Brand Image and Organisational Identity	Three points of stress were noted. 1. B/w picture and identification 2. Discussions and access with several	A thorough review of how retail businesses might handle these conflicts during rebranding is absent from the report.

	semi-structured interviews		stakeholders 3. Maintaining corporate identity while balancing marketing requirements	
Miller and Merrilees (2013)	Action Research	Total Stakeholder Buy-in	Non-Profit Sector: Complete stakeholder buy-in was achieved by full stakeholder engagement, including management, clients, and employees in rebranding activities.	The study offers no insights into the strategies used to sustain stakeholder support after rebranding, particularly in retail industries where retaining customers is essential.
Hanh Le, Cheng, Kunjara, and Lin, (2014)	Two-by-two factorial experimental setup. A sample of 120 Taiwanese undergraduate students was taken.	Product expertise, brand preference, and brand attitude as moderators	When customers have a positive attitude towards the original brand name, using evolutionary rebranding tactics is better in increasing consumer preference for the brand; when consumers have a negative attitude, using revolutionary strategies is better.	There is little data on the effectiveness of revolutionary and evolutionary rebranding tactics in various retail industries.
Collange (2015)	Quantitative research involving 320 consumers and	Brand name modification, perceived service	Found that customer evaluation of the service drastically decreased following	The study does not explore how retail companies can mitigate the negative

	eight fictitious brand name modifications	quality	a brand name change	impact of brand name changes on consumer perceptions
Roy and Sarkar (2015)	Design experiments 2x2 and 2x3.	Consumer-Based Brand Equity	Customers are more concerned with revolutionary rebranding than evolutionary rebranding and their CBBE decreases with rebranding news for an established company while increasing it for a less established one.	The long-term impacts of revolutionary rebranding on consumer loyalty in retail industries are not fully understood.
Bolhuis, de Jong and Van den Bosch (2015)	Customer and staff surveys of four organisations	Corporate Image, Responses from Workers and Customers	Rebranding has impact on consumer's choice.	Changes in company visual identity and their effects on long-term customer loyalty in retail are not examined in this study.
Gilstrap and Smith (2016)	An investigation of the corporate rebranding of a non-profit group.	Perceptions of Organisational Identity and Organisational Identity	NGO administrators showed satisfaction with their organisation, annoyance at the lack of public knowledge about them, and a deeper bond with the NGO identity. Managers	Further investigation is required to examine the effects of identity modifications on consumer morale in the retail industry during rebranding initiatives.

			<p>have a stronger sense of identification with their organisation when it upholds its mission objectives and promotes inclusivity among stakeholders.</p> <p>Conversely, when an organisation undergoes a rebranding or when transparency and inclusivity are thought to be compromised, managers feel a weaker sense of identification.</p>	
Lee and Bourne (2017)	16 interviews, qualitative single case study	Corporate identity, organisational identity, Customers identity.	Utilitarian and identification narratives were divided into two categories. Based on the two identities and the possible motivations for their acceptance, four different rebranding methods were developed.	The influence of these storylines on brand equity during rebranding is not well covered in the study.
Zhao, Calantone	215 rebranding announcement	Performance of Firm	Rebranding choices are generally linked	Little research has been done on how

and Voorhees (2018)	s from 101 sectors were sampled in an event analysis.	Stocks, Acquisitions, and Mergers	to positive anomalous stock returns.	stakeholder views shift in retail settings after rebranding.
Hsu, Fournier, and Srinivasan (2015)	Cross-sectional survey of 200 retail consumers post-rebranding	Customer Satisfaction, Brand Loyalty, Purchase Intention	Positive rebranding experiences can increase purchase intentions if aligned with customer expectations.	The study does not examine the long-term effects of rebranding on customer satisfaction in rapidly evolving retail.
Hanson., Mattila, and Kim (2023)	Longitudinal study of hotel rebranding efforts over 10 years	Brand Equity, Customer Loyalty	Hotels that maintained consistent branding experienced higher customer retention.	The study lacks insights into the role of digital channels in maintaining brand consistency in retail.
Sharma and Singh (2023)	Cross-sectional survey of retail consumers	Brand Recall, Brand Perception, Visual Identity	Minor changes in visual identity during rebranding can significantly affect brand recall and perception.	Further research is needed to explore how these changes impact long-term consumer loyalty in retail settings.

Table 2.4: Literature Review Gaps

2.14. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, a systematic and thorough review of the literary articles on rebranding has been done. Here, the author identified several research studies which worked on the impact of the implementation of rebranding on companies. This research work therefore presented a conceptual approach to the analysis of the consequences and effects of rebranding efforts and reviewed literature and case studies that captured antecedents to ‘gain’ as well as ‘losses’ inherent in rebranding strategies. However, not enough research was found on the effects of rebranding on high-street retailer clothing brands.

Following a systematic search, it is revealed that the clothing sector of the UK market, rebranding acts as one of the major tools for retailers to increase the significance and position of the company in the constantly shifting shopping landscape, where the Internet plays an ever-increasing role. A few scholars such as Keller, Geyskens, and Dekimpe (2020) and Balmer (2012) provided an argument about the fact that rebranding can dramatically enhance the customer's outlook and possess the capacity to change enough to ensure that high-street retailers remain relevant in comparison to purely e-tail competitors. However, a few studies, such as Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) and Merrilees and Miller (2008), investigated that for rebranding efforts to be impactful and effective, they should recapitalise the existing brand and provide new associations with key market trends and dimensions, to improve customer loyalty as well as brand value. On the other hand, the failure in rebranding, according to the study Heding, Knudtzen, and Bjerre (2009) can result in a decrease in brand loyalty and consumer ambiguity and finally affect its position in the market and its financial performance. However, the researcher here found limited studies on rebranding strategies and the impact of these on high-street retailers, especially clothing. Therefore, in the last section of this chapter, the researcher investigated the research gap from the key literatures and research articles. The next chapter will develop the theoretical propositions and conceptual framework of this research.

CHAPTER THREE: THEORITICAL PROPOSITION AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents propositions based on the review of chapter two's literature and the gaps mentioned in Table 2.4 regarding rebranding. A total of 11 propositions are developed here as presented in the conceptual framework (see figure 3.1) based on the research evidence to construct aspects of rebranding including the reasons for the rebranding campaigns, effective strategies for its application, and the impacts of rebranding campaigns in the fast fashion and clothing retail market. Such propositions provide meaningful connection among theoretical concepts that underpin this research and the practical aspects that are applied to rebranding to gain competitive advantages. In the following, the theoretical propositions are demonstrated.

3.1 Theoretical Propositions

It is expected to develop theories based on the analysis of prior pieces of literature before data collection of any case study research, as it paves the way for data collection, findings generalisation, and data analysis (Yin, 2014). This viewpoint of the case study research makes it different from other qualitative research methods including grounded theory and ethnography (Corbin and Strauss, 2008).

The following propositions are made in this research to address the literature gaps found in the literature review chapter. This chapter summarises the theoretical propositions regarding rebranding as an elaborate strategic tool of a tactical nature, which is designed to determine the strategies for developing competitive advantages. The theoretical propositions of rebranding within the retail industry are segmented into four key areas: Rebranding as Strategy, Rebranding Process, Rebranding Practices, and Competitive Advantages. These propositions are demonstrated in the following.

3.1.1. The nature of Rebranding strategies and competitive advantages

Empirical studies of rebranding found that rebranding strategies play a significant role in achieving higher market share and business dominance. For example, Merrilees and Miller (2008) conducted a study of 20 firms that embarked on rebranding and only explored the results of the brand identity and market performance. Another important study by Ewing, Napoli, and Pitt (2009) also compared the shareholders' wealth effect of rebranding-related announcements and its impact on the stock price of the 15 sampled companies asserting rebranding as a value-creating activity.

Regarding revolutionary and evolutionary strategies of rebranding, Knox and Bickerton (2003) argued that even a slight change in branding attributes like colour, logo and slogan, through brand evolution, may greatly affect brand perception and brand equity. On the other hand, Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) opined that rebranding should be a revolutionary change as it affects the market positioning of the brand. This type of strategic rebranding is crucial for companies needing to adapt rapidly to shifts in consumer preferences and competitive dynamics.

Research papers suggest that rebranding is revolutionary rather than evolutionary. Merrilees and Miller (2008) strongly advocate for this perspective, arguing that rebranding must be transformative to effectively reposition a brand within the marketplace. They emphasised that such changes go beyond simple adjustments and require a deep, strategic renovation that can significantly influence consumer perception and brand loyalty. Calderwood and Freathy (2013) expanded on this viewpoint by discussing the impact of rebranding on a brand's competitive stance. Their research highlighted how rebranding can serve as a critical strategy for brands to maintain relevance in an ever-evolving market landscape, where merely updating visual elements is insufficient. They argued that rebranding involves a comprehensive shift in the brand's market communication and positioning strategies, making it a fundamental tool for achieving competitive advantages.

This revolutionary approach to rebranding, underscored by both Merrilees and Miller (2008) and Calderwood and Freathy (2013), entails not only a change in the brand's aesthetic but also a redefinition of its value and market proposition. Rebranding, as discussed in key literature, underscores its importance as a strategic move aimed at securing competitive advantages through comprehensive and impactful changes to the brand identity. Hence a

proposition is formed here to find out whether rebranding is revolutionary or evolutionary to get competitive advantages.

P1: Rebranding is a revolutionary change to the brand name, which is different from other forms of change to the branding attributes like; colour, logo, and slogan changes to get competitive advantages

3.1.2. Rebranding Use as a Unique Strategy and Competitive Advantages

Even though the term ‘rebranding’ is often misunderstood as improvements in the graphic design or visual image of an organisation, rebranding is a deep and vast strategic transformation that can alter the company and the position it occupies in the market. A similar concept was established in the study of Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) who described that rebranding is not a simple change of a logo or brand name; rather, it is a business process that can result in a transformation of brand value as well as the position on the market.

Indeed, rebranding can be implemented with great success and in a strategic way that delivers considerable competitive benefits as found in the study of Kapferer (2012). The author explained that rebranding can serve to revive the attractiveness of the brand in a given market to make it relevant for current consumers. This research supported the study of Brockdorff and Kernstock (2001), which exclaimed that rebranding can also be a tool of crisis management which aims to change the public perception and regain consumers' trust. In their study, Burberry's from a traditional British company to a luxurious brand showed that strategic rebranding can provide a spectacular turnaround in the luck, size and shape of the brand which in turn can improve the share of the market and profitability.

As per the research by Goi and Goi (2011), it is seen that rebranding efforts can rejuvenate a brand and positively act to meet new challenges that proactively place the brand in a stronger position to compete effectively in the digital retail environment. Here, rebranding transcends typical marketing activities such as repackaging or refreshing by fundamentally altering a brand's perception in the competitive marketplace. In addition to this viewpoint, the research of Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer (2021) pointed out that rebranding cannot be overestimated as it fundamentally alters customers' perceptions of a brand and their loyalty to it, which is why it is a pivotal initiative for organisations those seeking to update their brand image and stand out from the competition. For example, the Boohoo firm's reinvention of Debenhams into strictly an online retailer demonstrates a clear strategic change not only in

building up the brand image's online presence but in the complete overhaul of the business's operational model. Thus, a proposition is formed here considering that, the intended use of rebranding as a tactical tool enables companies not only to modify the look of their brands but also to reorient their brands' positioning to address current market demands and opportunities for continuous growth and a strong market stand.

P2: Rebranding is a strategy that differentiates from the other types of marketing techniques such as repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning to gain competitive advantages

3.1.3. Using Rebranding as an Atypical Strategy and competitive advantages

The empirical study of Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) discussed that rebranding is a revolutionary process that separates it from other branding activities such as repackaging or repositioning, because it holds an ability that may drastically change the brand value. Agreeing with this opinion, the research of Merrilees and Miller (2008) found that rebranding can help firms change their positioning strategies in markets that are becoming highly competitive. On the other hand, the study of Hatch and Schultz (2003) criticised that the differences among rebranding and other branding activities are often exaggerated. They pointed out that branding activity, including rebranding, can flourish only if it is synchronised with the general strategic management of the company. However, a study by Kapferer (2012) argued that rebranding needs to be treated as a different kind of marketing process to brand building and that treating rebranding the same as other branding activities can be dangerous.

Another study by Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach (2018) stated that, as the implementation of rebranding is considered to require innovative tactics, the approach goes far deeper than mere tactical branding activities to redefine the brand's strategic key points. The research of Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach (2018) also noted that rebranding can aid in achieving digital transformation goals, as the examples of these strategies combined with digital trends contribute to the enhancement of brand awareness and customers' interest in the targeted brand.

For example, H&M's "Transparency in Fashion" campaign illustrated rebranding that linked H&M with new values of sustainable production and ethical narrations. Such a strategic alignment made it possible for H&M to create a competitive advantage based on the inclusion of sustainability within the brand. In addition, the research of Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach (2018) posited that strategic rebranding is vital in leveraging digital media to increase the

degree of openness and consumer appeal while offering a competitive advantage in the ever-growing retail industry. Thus, this kind of rebranding innovation can assist brands create new specific market segments. Hence, a proposition is developed here to consider rebranding as an atypical activity considering other branding activities.

P3: Rebranding is a unique process that can be classified as an atypical activity in comparison with other branding activities to achieve competitive advantages.

3.1.4. Different Types of Rebranding and competitive advantages

The form of rebranding can be corporate, business unit or product, and each of these has different strategic implications. In this regard, the research study of Merrilees and Miller (2008) revealed that decisions to rebrand reveal efforts to match a company's image to its new business model to retain or gain competitive advantages in the market. The study of the above two authors also claimed that corporate rebranding focuses on the company's complete image and might be occasioned by factors such as mergers, acquisitions, or strategic shifts in the market. Another study by Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) pointed out that, business unit rebranding refers to a situation in which rebranding is done selectively to certain sections of the business venture to achieve a new image without disturbing the general corporate image. As advised by Muzellec and Lambkin (2006), this approach can be beneficial when some divisions require making distinct identities to perform better. On the other hand, the investigation of Kapferer (2012) pointed out that rebranding products can go a long way in rejuvenating the life cycle of the product and thus prolonging the product's life in the market. This points to the fact that the different categories of rebranding present distinct routes to the actualisation of competitive advantage.

Several research studies suggested that rebranding entails substantial changes to a company's brand system, consistent with new business perspectives or reviving the company's image to significantly influence the brand's image/label on the consumers. The study by Huang, Dyerson, Wu, and Harindranath, (2015) asserted that, when rebranding is done wisely, it can rejuvenate the overall image and the marketing of products of the brand. The research of the authors also highlighted the shift from temporary to sustainable competitive advantages through strategic innovation. The investigation of Candra, Widita, Maulida, Shanti, and Kusuma (2023) also found similar results that, through the implementation of the new brand,

culture and identity are assimilated into the branding process and greatly improve the appeal of the brand.

As identified in the research of Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, and Frank (2018), business unit rebranding is useful for the resolution of specific operational issues or to meet market needs to enhance efficiency and position in the market. On the other hand, product rebranding entails changes made to specific products that companies produce, in a bid to target the changes and trends of consumers. In this regard, the study by Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) revealed the benefits of accommodating green aggression across product portfolios that honour consumers' environmentally friendly position to increase sales and uphold the brand's corporate responsibility outlook. So, a proposition is established here to find out how corporate, business unit or product rebranding is essential for high-street retailers striving to keep up with their competitors and stay on the market.

P4: There are three kinds of rebranding often noticed; corporate, business unit, and product rebranding to get competitive advantages.

3.1.5. Motivations for Rebranding and competitive advantages

The research of Muzellec and Lambkin, (2006) revealed that rebranding can be prompted by several strategic reasons, all of which act to enhance the pursuit of a competitive edge. Muzellec and Lambkin, (2006) found that the most common driver is mergers and acquisitions, since the consolidation of two companies requires a single, coherent image in terms of the brand. This approach is also supported by the research of Koszewska (2018), which stated that mergers and acquisitions are done in most cases to unite two separate corporations' cultures and customers' demands.

On the contrary, the study by Hatch and Schultz (2003) claimed that standardisation is an important reason whereby firms can sustain brand exposure and image across different countries, which also helps to reduce the complexities of marketing communication campaigns. In their recent article, Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) showed that developing a consistent standard of brand elements across different markets extends operational effectiveness and makes the brand as well as brand personality familiar to customers across the world.

Empirical studies of authors like Merrilees and Miller (2008) explained that, change and diversification are also features of rebranding whereby organisations change the brand theme

to attract other markets or groups thereby gaining a competitive advantage in areas that the competitors have not explored. Another reason for rebranding as identified in the study of Kapferer (2012) is simplification, where a brand undertakes a simple attempt to reduce consumers' confusion and increase brand equity. In addition, legal requirements like trademark issues or shifts in legislation might require a brand to stay legal while continuing business in the market.

As seen in the study of Jia, Yin, Chen, and Chen (2020), rebranding initiatives are associated with sustainability, which helps a brand appeal to customers who are more sensitive to sustainability and innovation as a way to establish the brand's legitimate claims to be environmentally friendly and technologically advanced. On the contrary, diversification strategies are pointed out by Kumar and Pansari (2016), through which venturing into new product lines or markets is done. In each of the cases, reasons for rebranding are closely related to the desire for either gaining or sustaining a competitive edge. Hence, a proposition is developed here in this research to find out the motivational drivers of rebranding to gain competitive advantages.

P5: The necessity of rebranding originates from one or several of the following stimuli: mergers and acquisitions, standardisation, brand image, simplification, repositioning and retargeting, diversification, and legal prerequisite to gain competitive advantages.

3.1.6. Rebranding Campaign Strategies and Competitive Advantages

Kaikati and Kaikati (2003) outlined six key rebranding strategies in their research paper. Phase-In/Phase-Out means the gradual change of the old brand or product to the new one with little disturbance. The research study of Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) stated that this method keeps the brand consistent and immerses itself between both networks (the old brand or the new). The consumer does not have to worry about not getting updates from the previous network with the same brand. Another strategy is One Brand Management, which occurs when unique brands in different divisions or groups of a company are merged under one brand, which is a Combined Rebrand or One Umbrella Brand. This is the case of the one-brand relaunch, which links different items under one brand system. As noted in the study by Candra, Widita, Maulida, Shanti, and Kusuma (2023), this approach assists in not only strengthening the brand image of the brands but also consolidating the diverse product-associative branding into one brand. In other words, consumers find it easier to memorise and relate multiple products with one strong brand image. It also simplifies the marketing

communication and costs can also be cut since all advertisement and promotion activities are covered under a single complete brand image.

On the other hand, the research paper by Kaikati and Kaikati (2003) described that Translucent Warning is more sensitive to consumers as they soften the blow, so to speak, by gradually familiarising consumers with the change. Furthermore, Sudden Eradication is described by the authors as a fast, total brand conversion best employed when the current brand is about to be demolished. Based on the work by Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, and Frank (2018), counter-takeover refers to the use of branding that is in direct opposition to competitors' strategies to occupy their market ground. Thus, Counter-Takeover rebranding helps a brand change its identity in such a way that it cannot be taken over. On the contrary, Retrobranding is the process of reviving a brand identity that has been used by a company in the past to draw the attention of the consumers again.

Tactical approaches to rebranding campaigns are crucial for such enterprises that strive to build new positions and gain competitive advantages. Each of them is applied to definite business circumstances and market requirements. So, a proposition is made here to discuss the rebranding campaigns to gain competitive advantages.

P6: There are six rebranding campaign strategies, such as; Phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand or one umbrella brand, translucent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding strategies to gain competitive advantages.

3.1.7. The Process of Rebranding and competitive advantages

Rebranding is an ongoing and systematic process that involves several key stages: including renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching. As pointed out by Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) in their empirical study, the starting point of rebranding is renaming, whereby the name of the brand is changed to suit a new image or changed strategic orientation. Here, the decision to change the name is made along with the new name that embodies the new brand culture or strategy. This process is very important, as it forms the basis of the rest of the rebranding strategy. The investigative paper of Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) underlined that name choice plays a crucial role in defining the brand's essence and its position on the market stressing that the right name can add a lot to the brand's attractiveness.

The study by Kapferer (2012) claimed for changes that have to be made to the actual graphic of the brand, including the logo, packaging, and the general outlook. It is important to inform the consumers of the new direction that a certain brand is taking. Here, new visual items are designed to harmonise with the new name, including logos, colours, and the appearance of the company's image. Supporting redesign as an effective rebranding process, Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) talked about how these visual changes are crucial in communicating to the consumers and altering their behaviour towards the brand.

On the other hand, the research paper of Merrilees and Miller (2008) disclosed that repositioning is the action phase during which the brand changes its market positioning plan to incorporate different target markets or modify the value proposition. This stage is a good opportunity to modify marketing strategies and segmentation to make sure that the company's new brand image is appealing to clients remaining loyal to the brand and to those who were not its users but might find value in it. In contrast, the study of Merrilees and Miller (2008) also described relaunching which establishes the product in the market, usually through elaborate marketing strategies whose ultimate goal is to create a new market for the product by convincing the consumers to accept the new brand image. In another article, Kumar and Pansari (2016) stated that the period of relaunching is the best time to make a change, create a buzz, and demand customers' attention through engaging and new interactions, as well as offerings.

According to Wigley (2011) assertions, this systematic approach to rebranding not only rejuvenates the brand but also gives the competition an edge by offering a brand which is closer to the market and consumer requirements. Thus, the ongoing process of rebranding enhances market share and consumer loyalty, as supported by Hatch and Schultz (2003). Therefore, the author makes a proposition regarding the ongoing process of rebranding through renaming, redesigning, repositioning, or relaunching to get competitive advantages.

P7: Rebranding is an ongoing process and follows a systematic manner, such as; renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching to achieve competitive advantages.

3.1.8. Rebranding of Names and competitive advantages

The empirical study of Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova (2014) stated that rebranding through the choice of a new brand name is one of the key strategic decisions that can provide

significant competitive advantages. Brand renaming can be, therefore, an important communication act that signals changes in strategy, positioning, or key values. According to the study of Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova (2014), the idea of changing the name is a very important part of the process of rebranding because it enables a company to disassociate itself and escape connection to certain negative or unwanted perceptions in the minds of the consumer. Furthermore, according to the research paper of Doyle and Stern (2006), there is the opinion that a good new brand name can help to enter a new market, including an international one, as it has a higher level of identity recognition among consumers.

A study by Kapferer (2012) mentioned that one of the best uses of renaming is in the simplification of branding portfolios in mergers or acquisitions to facilitate clarity. As a rebranding process, renaming is indeed extremely effective when done right. However, the research paper of Balmer and Gray (2003) disclosed that integrated strategic corporate branding processes must be communicated internally and externally to make the renaming process successful. Thus, in the context of rebranding efforts, the process of renaming can bring several benefits, including better differentiation on the market, increased brand values, and more loyal customers.

The study by Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) asserted that choosing a new brand name is one of the most important steps in the rebranding strategy because it strongly influences the change of a company's position in the market. Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) uncovered that psychological effects linked to a new name play a critical role in consumers' perception. They stated that a rightly chosen and executed new name can give a brand a new and youthful look in the market. Moreover, the study of Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) also investigated how a new name can help a brand to position itself in the context of new trends or consumers' new values important for a choice, for instance, in the field of sustainability or new technologies. On the other hand, the study of Kumar and Pansari (2016) claimed that rebranding is taken by not only name-changing but also implementing other marketing tactics. Therefore, a proposition is established here whether the change of brand name is predominant in branding to achieve competitive advantages.

P8: Rebranding is a form of strategy that suggests the selection of a new brand name to get competitive advantages.

3.1.9. Rebranding Concerned Costs and Risks and competitive advantages

Firms regard rebranding as a costly and risky approach, as a company must invest a lot of money and it carries an obvious risk of failure. The study by Balmer and Gray (2003) noted that rebranding also comes with pitfalls like having to undertake a market survey, having to train employees and customer disenchantment. In addition, according to the research of Doyle and Stern (2006), the problem of risks is especially acute when rebranding does not find enough response from the target consumers, because of which the brand loses its equity and market share. On the other hand, actual costs are connected to the rebranding process in the redesign of logos, packaging, and advertisements.

However, the above challenges can be countered by the following benefits that result from rebranding. According to the research study of Kapferer (2012), rebranding is a powerful way of restoring the organisation's image and bringing it into conformity with the existing trends and consumer wants which can further improve its competitive standing. However, the research of Miller, Merrilees and Yakimova (2014) pointed out that, the success of the rebranding tends to occur only if the management plans and executes the process strategically and communicates the results to all the relevant stakeholders. In particular, if properly carried out, rebranding bears more benefits than costs, and these include loyalty, differentiated competition, and enhanced profitability.

The research paper of Kumar and Pansari (2016) pointed out that, the rebranding process can help to strengthen the connection with the clients and improve their recognition of the brand. Similarly, the study of Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld (2018) claimed that a successful rebranding process can present massive competitive benefits as rebranding can lead a brand to stand out in a crowded market, especially when executed properly. On the other hand, the empirical investigation of Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) discussed that, despite the potential for relaunching brands and re-establishing a firm's market position, management views rebranding as an expensive and potentially risky activity. The costs are relatively high and they include expenses on new promotional items and campaigns, costs for trademark registration, and others. Hence, a proposition is developed here to find out how costly and risky rebranding is.

P9: Rebranding is perceived by firms as a costly and risky strategy to gain competitive advantages.

3.1.10. Overcoming Rebranding Related Risks, Cost Factors and competitive advantages

To offset the risks and costs that accompany rebranding, sufficient market research and communication is crucial, which entails the need for rebranding, risks and costs of the campaign, and strategies to overcome these risks and costs. The study by Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) discussed the research on rebranding needs, risks, costs, and possible competitive advantages through rebranding. They claim that it allows the firms to know whether rebranding will occur at the cost of brand equity (destruction), will occur to transfer equity to a new focal brand, or will create equity entirely. In this topic, the research of Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova (2014) stated that this process needs consumer research which involves the assessment of brand associations, consumers' attitudes towards brands, and brands' positioning.

It is also evident in the empirical research studies that the need for effectively managing communication strategy is important to overcome the associated risks and costs for gaining competitive advantages. In this viewpoint, the research study of Aaker and Joachimsthaler (2012) highlighted that all customers, employees, and other stakeholders must receive the same message of the company's vision and mission. Similarly, the study of Gotsi and Andriopoulos (2007) described that these concerns can be countered through timely and continuous communication strategies to reduce the risks of resistance. Supporting the above, the investigation of Kapferer (2012) proposed that, such strategies can turn the rebranding challenge into an opportunity and paraphrase the company's brand by revitalising its market position and the customers' relationships.

However, according to the study of Collange and Bonache (2015), the application of broad communication programmes can help in the management of organisational resistance during re-branding. The researchers argued that, once changes have been identified to be required and necessary, creating an effective mass communication program is very important. In addition, the research of Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria (2020) explained how effective and efficient communication helps reduce the possibility of stakeholders' loss by improving the brand reputation when the transition is done systematically. Therefore, a proposition has been developed here in this research to avoid potential risks of rebranding, control costs more efficiently, and receive better competitive advantages.

P10: Rebranding cost and risks of name changing can be overcome by, first assessing the need for rebranding and the name change, and following extensive research on overall market situations, as well as a well-planned mass communication strategy for all stakeholders of the name change to achieve competitive advantages.

3.1.11. Various Effects of Rebranding and Competitive Advantages

Rebranding can impact a company's brand in various ways, affecting the brand in terms of brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationships, brand loyalty, brand identity and brand position. The study by Lee and Bourne (2017) posited that successful rebranding can enhance the brand identity and consumers' bond with the brand since it integrates the brand with clients and culture. Equally, the study of Cankurtaran and Beverland (2020) claimed that, rebranding can be a positive force that improves brand equity as it brings the brand new life, makes it contemporary and relevant, or can even raise its 'value' in financial terms.

On the contrary, the research of Miller, Merrilees and Yakimova (2014) initiated that, rebranding can harm brands, confuse customers, and erode trust in the brand if not effectively done. This, in turn, is bad for brand loyalty and brand position since the new changes may leave the consumers detached from the new brand identity. Following the same proposition, the investigation of Roy and Sarkar (2015) pointed out that brand images or positions are perceived negatively by brand-loyal consumers, which can reduce brand equity and associated market share. Even, the research of Roy and Sarkar (2015) also asserted that the consequences that rebranding has to offer include competitive advantages the main principle of rebranding is innovation combined with tradition, so the new brand can reflect the brand values of the brand but also meet the demands of new markets.

To examine the facts about how rebranding affects the brand loyalty of consumers and the element of brand equity, the research of Zahid and Raja (2014) paid attention to bridging variables namely brand loyalty measuring the rebranding and brand equity relationship. Conversely, the study of Roy and Sarkar (2015) pointed out that rebranding has the potential to influence consumers' perceptions and expectations. On the other hand, the empirical study of Nana, Tobias, and Chiliya (2019) focused on how corporate rebranding influences brand equity and the performance of the firm and stated that rebranding can improve brand awareness and brand reputation if well done. Hence, a proposition has been proposed here to

analyse the positive and negative effects of rebranding in a company's brand attributes to get competitive advantages.

P11: Rebranding can negatively or positively affect a company's brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationship, brand loyalty, brand identity, and brand positioning.

A summary of the key references is listed in the following, which are sorted based on the research propositions.

Table 2.5: 11 Case Study Propositions with Key Literatures

Proposition Number	Proposition Description	Key References
P1	Rebranding is a revolutionary change to the brand name, different from other branding attributes like color, logo, and slogan changes to get competitive advantages.	(Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Calderwood and Freathy, 2013)
P2	Rebranding differentiates from other marketing techniques such as repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning to gain competitive advantages.	(Goi and Goi, 2011; Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach, 2018; Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer, 2021)
P3	Rebranding is a unique process classified as atypical compared to other branding activities to achieve competitive advantages.	(Kapferer, 2012; Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach, 2018)
P4	There are three kinds of rebranding often noticed; corporate, business unit, and product rebranding to get competitive advantages.	(Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, and Frank, 2018; Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld, 2018)
P5	The necessity of rebranding originates from one or several of the following stimuli: mergers and acquisitions, standardisation, brand image, simplification, repositioning and retargeting, diversification, and legal prerequisites to gain competitive advantages.	(Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Kapferer, 2012; Kumar and Pansari, 2016)
P6	There are six rebranding campaign strategies, such as; Phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand or one umbrella brand, translucent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding strategies to gain competitive advantages.	(Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003; Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, and Frank, 2018)

P7	Rebranding is an ongoing process and follows a systematic manner, such as; renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching to achieve competitive advantages.	(Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Hatch and Schultz, 2003; Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020)
P8	Rebranding is a form of strategy that suggests the selection of a new brand name to get competitive advantages.	(Doyle and Stern, 2006; Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova, 2014; Jacobs, Petersen, Hörisch, and Battenfeld, 2018)
P9	Rebranding is perceived by firms as a costly and risky strategy to gain competitive advantages.	(Balmer and Gray, 2003; Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020)
P10	Rebranding cost and risks of name changing can be overcome by, first assessing the need for rebranding and the name change, and following extensive research on overall market situations, as well as a well-planned mass communication strategy for all stakeholders of the name change to achieve competitive advantages.	(Aaker and Joachimsthaler, 2012; Gotsi and Andriopoulos, 2007; Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria, 2020)
P11	Rebranding can negatively or positively affect a company's brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationship, brand loyalty, brand identity, and brand positioning to get competitive advantages.	(Lee and Bourne (2017); Cankurtaran and Beverland, 2020; Roy and Sarkar, 2015)

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework shown in Figure 3.1 explains the proposed relations described in the previous theoretical proposition sections. As shown in the figure, the researcher makes the proposition that rebranding strategies are strategic management tools to gain competitive advantages in the high-street retail market. Rebranding processes are essential to mitigate risks, minimise costs, and get the best results from the strategies. From the conceptual framework developed from the reviews of previous articles and research studies, the author of this research also proposes that rebranding can result in the best outcome for high-street retailers if effective consumer research, internal and external process development, and communication can be done to get competitive advantages.

Figure 3. 1: Conceptual Framework

3.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a logical and comprehensive analysis of the theoretical propositions based on an extensive literature review and research gaps found in pieces of literature. Through the discussion of the theoretical propositions including “Rebrand as Strategy,” “Competitive Advantages,” “Rebranding Process,” and “Rebranding Practices,” a solid conceptual framework has been developed here, which introduces the complex interactions of rebranding with competitive advantages. This research will emphasise the demonstration of the propositions with the help of the five empirical case studies.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0. Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodological approach used in the study to examine rebranding campaign patterns among the UK high-street retailers. By adopting the method of an exploratory and descriptive case study, this business research aims to investigate the multifaceted processes and consequences of rebranding in a constantly developing context of modern market environments. Thus, the case study method is selected to explore detailed processes that would help reveal the strategic changes that occur in retail enterprises, even case study method and approach were chosen after the evaluation of other methods (Table 3.1). Following the case study protocol as Yin (2014) advised, this research ensures the study's reliability. Disregarding surveys, questionnaires, and other common research data-collecting tools, this work is based on the collection and analysis of secondary data. The use of secondary data minimises the possibility of having some form of interaction with the participants that might cause bias, hence playing the role of providing an impartial view that uses quality, contextually rich and readily collected data. This research encompasses recorded rebranding campaigns which involve documented evidence, reports from the business market, and academic works that analyse various rebranding strategies used and their impacts on the market.

In the first stage, this chapter declares the philosophical stance of this research. Here in this research, interpretive philosophy is the base. After that, the research approach section comes with the abductive approach chosen for this research. Then, the researcher describes the research method where the qualitative research method is selected. As a qualitative method, the case study method has been described here with a detailed description of the case study protocol and a short explanation of 5 selected case studies including Zara (Case A), Boohoo (Case B), M&S (Case C), Next (Case D), and H&M (Case E). Afterwards, data collection and analysis details of this research have been described. Later, the reliability, validity, trustworthiness, and ethics of the research have been explained; where the researcher discloses how the research maintained trustworthiness and reliability in the data collection and analysis process along with the simultaneous preference of validity and ethical considerations.

4.1 Research Philosophy (Paradigms)

The objective of this section is to verify the philosophical stance of the researcher concerning other paradigms that could have been implemented. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019), research philosophy is meant as a system of assumptions about the establishment of understanding and knowledge. In this regard, Burrell, and Morgan (2016) asserted that the choice of the correct research philosophy is critical in business research since it determines the methodological approach and data collection procedure as well as the interpretation of findings. Creswell and Creswell (2023) state that the common research philosophies in social science include positivism, realism, and interpretivism, each providing different views and methods for analysing human behaviour and organisational phenomena. On the other hand, along with these 3 philosophies, Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis (2019) added 2 more philosophies including postmodernism and pragmatism, which considering ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions. Ontological assumptions reflect reality, epistemological assumptions refer to knowledge, and axiological assumptions relate to the ethics and values of the researcher.

The positivism paradigm, originating from the natural sciences, focuses on quantitative research and uses statistics as a measurement method. In respect to the choice of positivism philosophy, Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) stated that this strategy is useful in cases where hypothesis testing needs to be done using specific and quantitative indicators, enabling predictions to be made out of observed events. In contrast, Gummesson (2005) explored that positivism may prove at times as a rather weak perspective which does not manage to reveal the full picture of people and social groups interacting because it lacks focus on the subjects' feelings and motives.

On the other hand, Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) argue that realism aims at trying to make the gap among objective facts and the perceptions that govern actions and thus is appropriate in any investigation that focuses on the factors that explain something seen to happen. Realism also accepts that there is an external reality like positivism but differs with it on the impact of human perception in ascertaining this reality.

Finally, there is the case of interpretivism which is a reaction, which portrays the qualitative nature of human reality. Flick (2018) viewed that reality is not constant and exists 'out there' but it is constantly being co-created through people's interpersonal communication and

perception. In contrast, interpretivism philosophy prepares for a broader and open investigation of social realities, stressing the significance of the values that people assign to actions within particular contexts. Silverman (2020) showed that interpretivism becomes useful in the business research practice in understanding organisational culture change, consumer behaviour and business strategies; this paradigm enables the researcher to uncover and analyse the contextual and interpretive factors that define these phenomena. Dubois and Gadde (2002) found that interpretivism's strength lies in generating depth in describing various aspects of organisational life. On the other hand, pragmatism philosophy focuses on ideologies as an extension of reality and knowledge (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2016). Here, the values of the researcher set the aim of the research to find practical solutions to the research problems. Another philosophy is postmodernism, which can question the current theories and concepts to expose biased realities (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019). Table 4.1 is made here to compare the philosophies appropriate for this study.

Table 4.1 A Comparison of Research Philosophies

Philosophical Aspect	Critical Realism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
Ontology (Nature of Reality)	Reality is external, independent, and unchanging	Reality is complex, rich, and socially constructed, with a number of interpretations and realities	Reality is complex and external, with different types of perspectives; emphasis on the answers to the research question
Epistemology (Nature of Knowledge)	Knowledge is contextually situated and temporary, with facts which are socially constructed and provide historical underlying details	Emphasises narratives, stories, perceptions, and interpretations	Focuses on practical problem-solving and identifying what is significant; valid theories and knowledge are those that facilitate successful actions
Axiology (Role of Researcher's Values)	Researcher is value-driven, aiming to reduce bias and errors	The researcher's values are significant, with a subjective perspective where interpretations are crucial	Research is driven by values
Data Collection Methods	Methods and data types vary depending on the subject matter	Uses small samples, in-depth investigations, and qualitative case study data	Methods are determined by the research problem, incorporating a mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches

Source: Adapted from Saunders, Thornhill, and Lewis (2019)

In this research, the researcher has chosen interpretivism philosophy. Silverman, (2020) argued that, when it comes to designing the research for this study on rebranding strategies among the UK’s fast fashion retailers, interpretivism perspective is chosen since it is founded deeply in the research goals that seek to reveal the complex and multi-layered phenomena of strategic rebranding. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) stated that interpretivism helps scholars to understand how these retailers develop and organise these rebranding concepts and processes in context to the dynamic consumer environments and the continuous changes in the technological framework of modern market.

Interpretivism philosophy allows the researcher to prepare research questions regarding the issues of the UK fast fashion clothing retail firms that are trying to sustain themselves in a competitive market highly influenced by the digital revolution (Flick, 2018). In addition to deepening the empirical investigation, this work further enriches the theoretical developments by presenting a variety and complex comprehension of the perception and practice of rebranding in the context of the UK retailers which can be elaborate far-reaching theoretical and practical recommendations to the field of marketing and strategic management.

4.2 Research Approach

Robson and McCartan (2023) showed in their paper that in a study of rebranding retail businesses, choosing the right research method is crucial if the objectives of the research need to be met. Saunders, Thornhill, and Lewis (2019) argued for three research approaches including deductive, inductive, and abductive approaches. In this research, the abductive research method amalgamated with the case study approach is adopted with the collection of qualitative data from secondary research, as illustrated by Mulisa (2022). To strive to understand the relevance of this methodological decision, it is necessary to describe the similarities and differences among these approaches and explain why abductive approach, especially if it is combined with the application of case histories, is the most appropriate for this research.

Bryman (2021) argued that deductive research is confirmatory and starts with a hypothesis formulated from theory and confirmed from data. This kind of research is highly systematic and is used where the researcher intends to establish the extent or volume of certain variables or test theories. Burrell, and Morgan (2016) showed that the main strength of deductive research is the nature of the outcomes that can be generalised and underpin theoretical knowledge. However, it is not as flexible as might be expected since it can limit the researcher when viewing details that are not contained in the theories and hypotheses which might be vital in understanding contextual details of the subject in the study.

On the other hand, Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2022) pointed out that, in inductive research, the hypothesis is not postulated at the beginning but is formulated from the observation of data. This method is accepted in qualitative research due to its capacity to reveal trends and theories from the data. Inductive reasoning is more suitable for coming up with hypotheses where the objective of the research is relatively unknown. The disadvantage,

however, consists in its likely rigidity in terms of external validity and the amount of data necessary to construct a coherent argument.

In contrast, Chia (2002) argued that abductive reasoning constitutes the core of the research thinking process that falls between deductive and inductive reasoning. Such an approach enables the sequential activity of theory testing and data analysis and integrates data into theory development. Dubois and Gadde, (2002) found that the abductive approach is especially important for types of research that require the integration of both current theoretical knowledge and new evidence from the market. Robson and McCartan (2023) reinforced that collecting qualitative data from secondary sources strengthens the abduction method by developing a broad yet in-depth understanding of different aspects of the clothing retail industry's rebranding strategies. The following Table 4.2 discusses the comparison of deductive, inductive, and abductive approaches.

Table 4.2: Deductive, Inductive and Abductive Approaches

Approach	Deduction	Induction	Abduction
Logic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rooted in scientific principles - Progresses from theory to data - If the premises (hypotheses) are correct, the conclusions will also be accurate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding the meanings humans attribute to events - Begins with specific observations - Uses known premises to generate new, untested conclusions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Merges deductive and inductive reasoning - Starts with observing an unexpected fact, which serves as a conclusion - A plausible explanation is then developed and tested
Sample Size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires a sufficiently large sample size - Data gathered is used to test hypotheses related to existing theories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smaller sample sizes are sufficient - Data is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes, and construct a conceptual framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data is collected to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, and develop a conceptual framework - This framework is then tested with additional data
Generalisability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moves from general to specific 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attempts to generalise from specific to general 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generalises the interactions between the specific and general
Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theory Testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theory Building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theory Building or Modification

Source: Adapted from Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis (2019)

As this research will critically evaluate the rebranding techniques of the UK fast fashion clothing retailers, based on case studies, an abductive approach is best suited here to test theories and modify theories if needed. Bryman (2021) argued that, this study on rebranding strategies is ideally conducted using an integration of abductive reasoning, case study method, and qualitative secondary data. This research approach is particularly suited for analysing complex patterns in the retail market’s adaptation to digital transitions while grounding the results in theory and formulating recommendations to address contemporary rebranding strategies in the UK fast fashion clothing retail industry.

4.3 Research Design

This research will examine the UK fast fashion clothing retailers’ rebranding approaches uses a qualitative research strategy and adopts the case study research method as advised by Yin (2017). This approach is critically selected with which it enlightens the object under study, capturing the real nature and context of the phenomena in its natural environment. Table 4.3 is shown in the following to describe the 2 different research designs including quantitative and qualitative research methods used in the research work.

Table 4.3: Research Methods

Aspect	Quantitative	Qualitative
Philosophy	Commonly linked with positivism, but can also align with realism and pragmatism	Typically connected with interpretivism, but can also align with realism and pragmatism
Theory Development Approach	Deductive or Inductive	Inductive, Deductive, or Abductive
Key Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigate relationships between variables - Analysed through various statistical and graphical methods - Utilises controls to ensure data validity - Employs probability sampling to ensure generalisability - Can be implemented as a mono-method or multi-method (using two types of quantitative tools to reduce the limitations of a single method) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explores meanings assigned by respondents and the relationships between them - Analysed using a range of analytical procedures to contribute to theoretical development - Data collection is non-standardised - Utilises non-probability sampling, with data collection methods adaptable to the research process - Can be used as a mono-method or multi-method
Research Strategies	Survey Research, Experimental Design, Case Study	Action Research, Case Study, Grounded Theory, Narrative Research, Ethnography

Source: Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, (2019)

Table 4.3 compares qualitative and quantitative research methods applicable to this research. Dubois, and Gadde (2002) found that the qualitative paradigm proves practical for identifying the underlying motives in business developments and consumer tendencies, which are some

of the key fundamental aspects in the perception of rebranding. Being flexible in the use of questions, this method enables diving deeply into the essence of motivation that is concealed by quantitative results, as well as into the results of strategic actions (Patton, 2023). Dubois and Gadde (2002) also argued that the critiques of qualitative research suggest that such a study type is not reliable if it is unable to find details in other similar communities or large populations irrespective of whether the qualitative findings are significant or not. To avoid this, the case study approach in this research focuses on a few unique instances that present observations from a large pool of industries and their rebranding exercises (Babbie, 2020). This selection is aimed at guaranteeing that the results achieved are indeed profound and comprehensive, not only applicable to the cases under consideration but also useful in the study of the issues of rebranding in the context of the UK fast fashion clothing retail sector.

The purpose of adopting a qualitative study approach can also be traced to the ability of the research method to offer a critical, contextual, and consequential method of explaining the evolving function of rebranding strategies (Yin, 2017). The choice of the qualitative study is justified by an optimal applicability of the presented research's goals and objectives where the focus is to investigate the rebranding strategies and discuss the specifics of the rebranding process, which is a rather multifaceted and convoluted business action (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2022). So, based on the research questions, qualitative research design is best suited to find the answers in the research work. Here, a total of 11 theoretical propositions have been developed in this research as described in chapter 3. The qualitative case study design of this research will help the researcher to achieve the objectives of the research.

4.3.1 Case Study Method

In this research, the case study method is used to apply the proposed abductive approach, utilising only qualitative data collected from secondary sources such as business articles, market reports, and analyses. Bryman (2021) clarified that the case study method is particularly valuable in exploring the 'how' and 'why' of rebranding processes, as it provides a comprehensive and contextual overview of specific cases. Burrell, and Morgan (2016) showed that the choice of collective cases for this study was based on the principle of literal replication as in all the cases examined in the study. The next decision made was about the number of cases that were to be used in the study. As for the number of cases: there is no exact number defined by scholars, however, Yin (2017) states that 2-3 cases are appropriate for literal cases, while 4-6 for theoretical cases. Similarly, Neuman, (2023) recommended

choosing among 4 and 10 cases for theory building to have enough richness and support for the theories. Here in this research, five extensive case studies have been selected. The researcher employed the following six components in designing the case study research, as outlined by Yin (2017):

1. Defining the case study question
2. Formulating theoretical propositions
3. Identifying the unit(s) of analysis (defining and delimiting the case)
4. Establishing the case study protocol and collecting data
5. Establishing logical connections among data and propositions
6. Setting criteria for interpreting the findings

This paper shows that a case study is particularly useful in analysing distinctive cases, each of which offers a snapshot of the industry environment (Schoch, 2020). This approach enables the researcher to analyse and understand how these retailers operate in more complex environments (Neuman, 2023). This method is very effective in identifying the assumptions and the heuristics characteristic of senior management decisions that may remain obscure behind substantial numerical evaluations (Hancock, Algozzine, and Lim, 2021). In this regard, Burrell, and Morgan (2016) showed that using case studies as a method of data collection strengthens the research at the qualitative levels. This method allows for a complex analysis of the effects of rebranding projects, by including, any changes in the organisational structure, internal and external consumer responses, and the effect on the company's position among competitors (Coe, Waring, Hedges, and Ashley, 2021). The complexity of the collected data from each case enables the researcher to provide a multi-level analysis of the strategic, operational, and competitive variables of the business environment, which determine the outcome of rebranding efforts. In the following section, the researcher explains the theory development process followed for this research.

Table 4 4: Theory Development Process Followed for this Study

Step	Activity	Purpose
Initiation	Define research questions and theoretical propositions based on existing studies	Provide a solid foundation for theoretical constructs and focus on rebranding research
Case Selection	Use theoretical sampling to choose cases that have undergone rebranding	Ensure the study is centred on cases that contribute to theory development
Instrument Development	Utilise multiple data collection methods including documents, websites, and observations	Facilitate triangulation of findings and enhances research rigour
Fieldwork	Simultaneous data collection and analysis	Refine data collection instruments and aid in identifying emerging themes
Data Analysis	Conduct within-case analysis and cross-case analysis using pattern matching technique	Increase familiarity with data and offers a preliminary insight into theory generation
Theoretical Shaping	Iteratively evaluate and gather evidence for propositions Apply replication logic (both literal and theoretical) across cases Provide evidence for theoretical associations between constructs	Validate and refine initial propositions; Enhance and sharpen the theory and conceptual framework; Strengthen internal validity
Literature Integration	Compare developed theory with existing literature	Reinforce internal validity Refine theory, construct definitions, and theoretical associations

Source: Adapted from Eisenhardt (1989)

As there are five case studies, collective case study diagram needs to be developed here, which in the following figure 4.1.

Figure 4. 1: Design of Collective Case Studies

Source: Developed by the researcher for this study based on (Yin, 2014)

The above figure represents the modified collective case study design for the five case studies used in this research. The process starts with the conduct of a literature review and then goes through the creation of theoretical propositions. Cases are decided, and protocol and data collection are done. The process then splits into five sub-processes (Case A, B, C, D, and E). Each case culminates in an analysis and report before moving on to the collective case analysis and discussion. The design ends with a theoretical modification, a collective case studies report after the identification of some major themes throughout the cases, and the formulation of the managerial implications and recommendations sessions.

4.3.2. Case Study protocol

A similar approach is used by Yin (2017) and is explained as “developing the tools and the protocol”. For this study, since the researcher is conducting the work independently, a

tailored protocol was established to design and execute the case study research as detailed below.

1. Analyse and understand the rationale, aim, and objectives that have characterised each of the rebranding exercises conducted by the cases
2. Collect print and website data, promotional materials, slides, and branding proofs, and record all the collected sources
3. Discuss cases that will correspond to the questions of the study with the theoretical framework and constructs that are going to be used
4. Go through multiple rounds of performing the individual case analysis of each case and the first draft of the respective case study report
5. Finally, collective-case analysis of the findings and prepare the final report simultaneously

The concern of qualitative sampling is to identify cases, which can help the researcher understand the researched phenomenon more profoundly. Qualitative research frequently uses techniques where cases are selected because of convenience and the detail that they can provide (Creswell and Poth, 2018). The sample size in qualitative studies is usually smaller as data are collected and analysed in detail to offer an understanding of issues, but validity questions are raised here since the sample size is usually limited in this kind of study (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016).

The aim of collective case study design is to reach the apex of theoretical repetition where case addition no longer produces much new and novel data. This paper applied a purposive sampling technique to include cases that are most likely to provide useful data. The selection of five cases was also a result of the richness of data that was gathered to reduce the possibility of case redundancy, thereby making the data both reliable and relevant (Tracy, 2020).

Burrell, and Morgan (2016) showed that the case study approach, like any other research technique, has its limitations that need to be acknowledged by the researchers. Confidentiality issues are important, especially where data is collected from case studies (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Further, competition for data and its management among the stakeholders can become a challenge and there are a few specific challenges in the publication process like anonymity

and integrity of researcher interpretation (Yin, 2017). Eisenhardt, and Graebner (2007) stated that the reports of case studies may have complex and hard-to-analyse storylines. Ideally, appropriate control of this issue calls for a clear conceptual framework. On the other hand, Burrell, and Morgan (2016) showed that case studies can be made with the help of different data collection methods, although the need for vast field study is generally not mandatory.

4.4. Data Collection

The case study is often used in rebranding research since the method is highly valuable for elaborating rebranding campaigns. Joseph, Gupta, Wang and Schoefer (2021) employed case study research to bring out the complexity of internal branding by outlining how higher educational institutions dealt with brand internalisation revealing the dynamic relationship among culture, engagement, and identity. On the other hand, Lyppert (2020) used this method to study the relaunch of luxury fashion brands and more specifically how these brands announced their new positioning to younger generations. The detailed descriptions and realistic examples of the case studies let the authors explain how it is possible to balance a strong and well-recognised brand image with efforts focused on demographic shifts as a part of rebranding.

Besides, case studies help in evaluating the effects of rebranding on brand equity and consumers' attitudes toward the brand. Muzellec, Doogan, and Lambkin (2003) underlined the typical value of case studies in explaining consumers' reactions stimulated by long-term rebranding measures and the destiny of brands in the long run. By looking at different cases and assessing the impact of rebranding, researchers can make the use of case studies a useful method when studying rebranding in general. Crotty (1998) showed that in the case study, the uncovering of evidence centred on the use of documentary sources and materials as well as the use of archive records to enhance the chances of conducting a thorough analysis. Additional forms of evidence critically analysed included historical documents as well as prior reports of the organisation in a bid to corroborate findings as well as gain further understanding of the topic under consideration (Yin, 2014). Qualitative data were used in this research and they included articles, organisational reports, and data that were obtained from trusted online databases. These documents were useful in giving the background and overall picture of the case such that no stone was left unturned. All the references used in this research paper are included in the references list and the source of evidence for case studies are in the appendix (See APPENDIX A).

4.4.1. Rationale for choosing the cases and campaigns:

In this section, the researcher describes the rationale and motivation behind the choice and selection of the five case studies. These five rebranding campaigns were conducted in five different clothing retailers of the UK.

4.4.2 CASE A (ZARA)

The researcher has chosen the case of Zara's transformation from fast fashion to luxury in 2022 because of its tactical relevance and the forces affecting the retail industry (Zara, 2020). The rebranding exercise made Zara adopt new product lines, including genuine leather and suede, thus positioning it among luxury labels. This restructuring was not only to augment the profit margin but also to adapt the brand into a new segment of the fashion sector. Deciding to transform into a luxury brand, Zara aimed at capturing the current trend of targeting the consumers interested in luxury products that are affordable and thus, gaining a new perspective that will fit the interests of the customers interested in the value and quality offered by an exclusive product.

4.4.3 CASE B (BOOHOO GROUP PLC.)

The researcher has chosen the 'Debenhams rebranding to Boohoo in 2021' as one of the most crucial and interesting instances because it concerned dramatic shifts in the retail market (Boohoo Group PLC, 2021). Debenhams, which was a prominent British department store chain, had been functioning in the high streets of the United Kingdom for more than 200 years. Purchased in 2020 by Boohoo Group PLC – a company that has a model of online fast fashion – signified a new direction in the way that traditional retail brands could be rejuvenated for the new age. This was not just a change in ownership but a total change of identity from a store-based retailer to a pure-play online fashion business.

4.4.4 CASE C (MARKS AND SPENCER)

These are some changes that Marks and Spencer made when rebranding Jaeger in 2021 to refocus a heritage brand and integrate it into a retail outlet. Luxury British fashion brand Jaeger had faced difficult trading conditions in the years before it was bought. It was clear that if Marks and Spencer acquired Jaeger, they would have a chance to update and revitalise its image and bring it into a new age as a more modern but still loyal companions to the

company's brands. This rebranding exercise was basically about keeping the 'luxury' factor intact in 'Jaeger' while taking it to millions of new consumers through Marks and Spencer's successful retail outlets (Marks and Spencer, 2021).

4.4.5 CASE D (NEXT PLC)

Next PLC changed Next Directory to Next Online in 2018 to capture the growing market of online retail experience. The researcher has chosen this rebranding campaign for investigation because it is a good example of a traditional catalogue-based business that moved into the online environment. As of 2018 these new market trends in the action of e-commerce and the change in customer habits, the company decided to rebrand into 'Next Online' denoting a transition from a print-based catalogue into a more adaptive web-based platform. This rebranding is particularly compelling because when executives think about digital transformation in their retail operations, they need to consider modern market (Next PLC, 2018).

4.4.6 CASE E (H&M)

The researcher decided to focus on the case of H&M's sustainability initiative in 2019 as being a seminal moment for retail organisations. Swedish clothing giant H&M was the first major company to disclose the content of materials and the supply chain at the product level. This push for transparency was part of its sustainability goals, which the company had set to meet consumer demand for ethical and environmentally conscious consumption. This case enables the researcher to examine how the major retailers can incorporate transparency and sustainability as a strategic weapon, thereby impacting brand image and consumer choice (H&M Group, 2019).

4.5. Data Analysis and interpretation

Eisenhardt (1989) said that in qualitative research, data analysis and data interpretation are two fundamental tasks that take place individual case studies among other methodological approaches. These stages entail processes that can guarantee that the findings are credible and well-grounded in data. In this regard, Creswell and Poth (2018) argued that, the data analysis process comprises sorting information into categories and this process is termed categorisation. Categorisation is important because it is the premise of subsequent analysis, in which the findings are aimed at identifying recurring patterns in the material. These categories are deduced from the data and therefore the methodology used in this process is

abductive analysis in which the framework for analysis is developed from the data (Saldaña, 2021). To some extent, this does involve a natural process of sorting out the data, which certainly tends to make it easier to handle and assess.

Even, Crotty (1998) showed that after the data has been classified into various categories, the next step is to look for patterns within the individual categories and indeed across a number of them which is called abstraction. Abstraction means a reduction of detailed categories into agreed lower-level conceptual categories (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2019). This stage raises the level of analysis from mere documentation to more interpretation, whereby the analyst tries to provide meaning and relations to the collected data. This is important to the desire to hone a deeper understanding of the phenomena being researched and to emerge with novel insights and observations.

Regarding the choice of data analysis method, pattern matching was chosen from the set of five techniques presented by Yin (2017). Pattern matching, therefore, involves the evaluation of the actual patterns identified in the data against the expected patterns proffered by theoretical propositions. Pattern matching has been selected for this research because of its capability to integrate propositions from a theory to the evidence. Moreover, Crotty (1998) showed that the model allows for a more accurate comparison this way between what the theory prescribes, and what was seen in the data, thus making the test of the theory stricter. Furthermore, Eisenhardt (1989) said that pattern-matching analysis is followed by the final integration of the results in case study research. It becomes important in qualitative research when it enables the researcher to go beyond description and start putting together a better picture of the phenomena of interest (Bazeley, 2013). So, pattern matching case study analysis is done in this research.

At this stage, it is also necessary to strengthen or operationalise the theoretical propositions derived from the study. This stage entails paying attention to precise observation of data and at the same time expanding from the data to make more general conclusions to enhance theoretical and practical knowledge concerning the phenomena. Interpretation, sometimes in the form of hypothesis (propositions) testing, usually requires other theories to be put into consideration and the results arrived at should be as much supported by evidence as possible (Spiggle, 1994). For this reason, pattern matching was selected as it enabled the direct testing of theoretical propositions and allowed the amendment of the theories if necessary.

4.6. Trustworthiness, Reliability, and Validity

Eisenhardt, and Graebner (2007) stated that in qualitative research, the credibility of the study is important, hence making the research trustworthy, reliable and valid. Despite their connection, each of them provides a different approach to how qualitative research may be assessed for its rigour, more specifically in the case studies. Gill, and Johnson (2002) stated that credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability are the subcategories of trustworthiness which are considered to be equivalent to validity and reliability. However, the application of these criteria in qualitative studies such as case studies is always complicated and more so debatable among researchers in academia.

Eisenhardt and Graebner also (2007) explained that trustworthiness is a very crucial concept in qualitative research aimed at improving the believability of the identified outcomes. Reliability, on the other hand, is concerned with the confidence one has in the true information and the conclusions arising out of the data. To establish credibility in executing this case study, strategies including triangulation, persistent observation and member checks were used. According to Carter, Bryant-Lukosius, DiCenso, Blythe, and Neville (2014) triangulation, which entails the use of various data sources, techniques or theories in sequence or combination with the intent to cross-check details, is a recognised method of checking credibility. However, often, this process is recommended for practice and, like every other technique, it is not without limitations. Gummesson, (2005) explored that the process might be very time-consuming and demanding in terms of the resources used in accessing information from different sources. Researchers have to remember that, although triangulation can prove that certain elements of data are accurate, it might overlook the possibility of biases and inaccuracies (Nowell, Norris, White, Moules, 2017).

Even, Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007) showed that generalisability is another aspect of credibility mentioned earlier as a criterion of trustworthiness and is concerned with the possibility of generalising results across other organisations. In this business research, the approach to transferability was based on the concept of ‘thick description’ where the details about the research context and phenomena under investigation were given (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). On the same note, several scholars have emerged with various criticisms of the idea of transferability. There are some researchers, for instance, who hold that qualitative data are bound by context and are therefore transferable across contexts (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). This form of qualitative research therefore raises some interesting issues of where the

optimum between the provision of detailed contextualising data and the need for wider generalisability might lie.

Gill and Johnson (2002) stated that dependability is similar in principle to the reliability of the research process in qualitative research. Delivering dependability requires documentation of the whole research process, such that it can be replicated or validated by other researchers in the future (Shenton, 2004). It is useful to stress that in this study an extensive audit trail was provided during each stage of the data collection and analysis process. This documentation is relevant to dependability since it enables other people to trace the steps of the researcher to determine the reliability of the results produced. However, there are voices of critique saying that true dependability may be rather difficult to achieve due to the nature of case study analysis (Gibbs, 2007).

Gill and Johnson (2002) claimed that the term ‘conformability’ is used to mean to what extent the results obtained are influenced by the data collected and not by the researcher’s perception or hypothesis. To increase conformability, the following methods can be employed; for instance, a case study database can be developed to store all the raw data, notes and memos to allow for the confirmation of the findings (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2019). In this study, the conformability was enhanced through peer debriefing and the use of reflexivity in that the author of the study consciously considered his or her part in the study and how the assumptions could have an impact on the results obtained (Nowell, Norris, White and Moules, 2017). Although, strictly speaking, it is impossible to be entirely objective in qualitative research, it is not always considered desirable. There is always a filter of interpretation by the researcher through theory; no matter how much one is reflexive, he/she cannot avoid biases.

Gummesson (2005) explored that several types of validity commonly applied in qualitative research are internal validity which is referred to as credibility, external validity, and transferability in qualitative research. Internal validity relates to the degree or extent to which research findings are true, real and accurate portrayals of reality. Internal validity control in this study was enhanced through pattern matching where the researcher was in a position to check the patterns of the data with that of the theoretical framework and find any inconsistencies (Yin, 2017). External validity, also known as generalisability, considers the extent to which the findings can be generalised. Although the qualitative paradigm does not set out to generalise results obtained as variables suggested above, giving detailed contextual

information enables the viewers or readers to determine the precedence of the results disposed of in the study for their setting (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Two issues, thus, arise relevant to the process of validity: It remains a problem how to maintain the closeness to the given context and data specificity inherent in qualitative analysis while staying as generalisable as possible.

In this research focusing on the UK fast fashion clothing retailers' rebranding strategies, it is crucial to consider certain factors that will enhance the credibility of the study. Credibility deals with the reality and relevancy of the research findings and hence, relies on the collection of secondary qualitative data in the form of Annual Reports and Balance Sheets of Companies to offer a profound and valuable understanding of the effects of rebranding. As noted by Anney (2014), care ought to be taken through documentation and timely analysis that external validity of the rebranding processes is achieved, thereby improving the relevance and generalisability of the conclusions made.

Table 4.5: Establishing Trustworthiness in Case Study Research

Criteria	Strategies Applied in This Research Study
Credibility (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019) and Validity (Yin, 2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Triangulating data using various sources - Ensuring care to minimise biases like participant bias and common method bias - Providing a full and transparent account of the data analysis process
Transferability (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019)	- Applying a literal replication logic in selecting and analysing multiple case studies
Dependability (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019) and Reliability (Yin, 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strict adherence to the case study protocol as detailed in 4.3.1.1 (Yin, 2017) - Offering a transparent view of the data analysis
Confirmability (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019)	- Maintaining an evidence chain in conducting case study analysis, the conceptual framework, and annotations/memos leading to the findings and conclusions
Construct Validity (Yin, 2014)	- Establishing constructs and concepts through a comprehensive literature review on rebranding

Source: Developed by the author for this study

Gill and Johnson (2002) argued that reliability and validity should be deemed utterly important in strengthening the academic credibility of the study. Reliability is ensured by the usage of objective and specific data collecting and processing procedures. Qualitative data helps compare datasets and sync the findings with the theoretical branding constructs (Rolfe, 2006). Such procedures increase confidence in the results as well as make the interpretations replicable and fairly solid. Regarding validity, it deals with internal and external aspects of the study. Internal validity is achieved through data triangulation which involves independent sources being reviewed to ensure that findings are rock solid and to reduce biases associated with secondary research (Anney, 2014). Regarding external validity, there is a purposive sampling of a variety of specified cases within the context of the retail environment, which in turn enables the extension of the research outcomes into related retail contexts, thereby expanding the study's applicability and worth within the sphere of rebranding (Rolfe, 2006).

4.6. Ethical Considerations

In the completion of this research on the rebranding of the UK high-street retailers, issues of business ethics as crucial to the research work and as a guarantee for the study's validity could not be overemphasised. Based on the guidelines provided by Arifin (2018), all data collected from secondary data sources such as company reports, market research and financial statements were used responsibly by the author with references to the act of Confidentiality and data protection act (Creswell and Creswell, 2023). The approach also guarantees that any information related to the organisations involved is dealt with a very high level of secrecy, hence protecting the privacy of all the concerned organisations.

Furthermore, and more specifically regarding case study analysis, Cacciattolo (2015) stresses that researchers conducting qualitative research must be clear about the purpose of the research and how case study data will be used. Even though this study relied chiefly on secondary data, wherever necessary all the data-providing entities were made to understand the nature of the research and the utilisation of the data (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). This procedure not only served to reaffirm the ethical commitment of the study but indeed played a role in establishing the rapport with the resources that regulated the research process by ethics to the betterment of the field of rebranding. In addition, to ensure the reliability of the research, the researcher has followed the standard principles along with the research framework of the University (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). Complying with the University's code of ethics, this research avoided all sources or information that may

negatively impact the readers (University of the West of Scotland, 2024). Furthermore, the author will be conscious of the university's ethical regulations. To do so, the researcher declares that there will be no conflict of interest between any group or animal, no irrelevant information, and no manipulation in data collection and analysis.

4.7. Chapter Summary

This chapter gives a comprehensive description of the approach taken in the research work looking at rebranding techniques utilised by the UK high-street retail businesses in the era of retailers. It involves the use of an exploratory and descriptive case study methodology as a means to develop multiple and highly detailed accounts of the processes and consequences of rebranding. Stressing its secondary data approach, the chapter lays out the reasons for the exclusion of such basic data collection methods as surveys or questionnaires. The method used in the chapter is interpretivism to capture the phenomenological view of the strategic rebranding that is influenced by cultural, economic and personal factors. The details of the research philosophy, approach and design are provided systematically in this chapter. This chapter explains how qualitative data from secondary sources was analysed using individual and collective case studies which provided a background on strategic management decisions and their effects on brand and market positions. In general, this chapter on methodology defines the approach to be used in the study of rebranding strategies and offers a significant aid to scholarly literature and practice in the field of the UK clothing retail industry. The next chapter will illustrate the individual case study findings of this research.

CHAPTER FIVE: INDIVIDUAL CASE ANALYSIS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter begins with a closer analysis of the rebranding campaign activities conducted by UK high-street clothing brands onwards with an intention to identify how it is possible to leverage such strategies for gaining competitive advantages and higher market shares while the dominance of online shopping is being felt around the world. Using real examples of the big market retailers, like; Zara, Boohoo, Marks & Spencer, Next PLC, and H&M this chapter aims at providing the reader with the vast practical aspect of rebranding as well as its effects on market positioning and brand image. CASE A is ‘Zara Redefined’ conducted in 2022 employing Zara in the luxury segment by ensuring more quality and sustainability in Zara’s clothing. CASE B is about the purchase of Debenhams online platforms only by Boohoo in 2021 keeping Debenhams as an online only brand. CASE C describes the purchase of Jaeger brand by M&S in 2021 displaying Jaeger items in M&S flagship stores and then more others. CASE D is about Next PLC’s move from ‘Next Direct’ to ‘Next Online’ in 2018 focusing on the online platforms of Next. CASE E illustrates the rebranding campaign of H&M in 2019 emphasising the approach to disclose detailed supplier information to consumers.

The study is well positioned within the overall framework of the research objective to examine a number of rebranding campaigns to understand the workings peculiar to executing these initiatives in a rapidly evolving modern market environment. In this chapter, case study analysis is done in detail, while each case is discussed first under some key points derived from the literature review from section 5.1 to section 5.5. After the findings analysis of each case, all 5 case studies are then analysed based on the eleven propositions developed for this research from section 5.6.1 to 5.6.11.

5.1. CASE A (ZARA)

5.1.1 The Company and Its Market

Zara is a Spanish company that began its operations in 1975 and is part of the Inditex group, which specialises in fast fashion. Soon it gained a large market with a great share, solely because it could offer the latest fashion trends in clothing with an affordable price range. In the past, it built a very efficient supply chain and was undoubtedly better than competitors in faster response to fashion trends. However, in 2022, Zara switched its strategic plan of action from mass-market targeting to luxury-market targeting. Additionally, Zara is the leading brand of Inditex, which is identified as one of the largest fashion retailing conglomerates in the world. Inditex, based in Arteixo, Spain, had a net sales of £30.5 billion in 2023. Currently, Inditex comprises 7292 stores in 96 markets arranging employment of over 165,000 workers, including Zara.

The high-buzz campaign, known as Zara Redefined, started in January 2022 aiming at repositioning Zara and reflect the new wave of consumerism by emphasising eco-friendliness and quality. Moreover, the repositioning plan that has contributed to this corporate rebranding entailed re-designing Zara's logo, restructuring store layouts to transform the store environment into a blend of luxury and elegance, and enforcing sustainable fabrics and processes throughout the supply chain. The company spread these new brand values through various global marketing channels, including media and internet and TV advertisements, as well as word of mouth.

Zara segments its operations into several key areas: design, production, distribution, and selling. This brand has a strong online presence that accounted for £7.7 billion in e-business sales in 2023, up from £6.7 billion recorded in 2022. Zara's 5692 physical stores worldwide also appear to have adopted a sustainable and luxurious feel to boost the customer experience. The rebranding campaign has successfully positioned Zara in the market. Inditex's market capitalisation amounted to about £95 billion by early 2024. Today, Zara remains in the process of increasing its market share by extending the company's brand appeal and taking advantage of the developed brand image.

5.1.2 Rebranding in the Company

In January 2022, Zara started using a massive rebranding known as “Zara Redefined”, caused by the increasing customer awareness of sustainability, the necessity to stand out from competitors, and the increase in the company’s online profile. The rebranding that Zara did in the year 2022 was a Corporate Rebranding. This ambitious program affected Zara’s business at the international level since it changed the general image of the chain, the disposition of stores, communications, and the logistics system to bring about a more appreciable and environment-friendly company. These factors defined the need to make a change in the brand by adopting a new logo. The ideas concerning Zara’s rebranding campaign called “Zara Redefined” were initiated in early 2021, while the rebranding campaign took place in January 2022. Inditex conducted all major strategies or management decisions in its central office in Arteixo, Spain. The process was conducted by Inditex's organisational leaders, including Óscar García Maceiras who became the CEO of Inditex in November. 2021 and Marta Ortega who has been holding the position of the Chairwoman of Inditex since April 2022.

Firstly, the area of quick fashion has been over-grown by competition and hence to compete with others, Zara has started shifting towards the luxury segment. This change not only placed Zara in competition with premium brands, but also fitted into a rising group of consumers who are conscious of their purchases’ impact on social issues, such as labour rights. Secondly, the challenges to the environment have arisen, fashion consumers are now aware of the impact they make on their purchases and where they expect to get materials that are environment-friendly and hazard-free during production. The developments in the market helped Zara integrate sustainable measures into the production and supply chain of its products. Externally, the rebranding entailed extensive changes as it applied to the internal environment of Zara by coming up with a new logo, interior design for its stores, and other arrangements that supported the company’s luxury gimmick. Externally, the aspects of the marketing mix were changed to reflect a new corporate communications strategy dedicated to the company’s focus on quality and sustainability, revealing its activities to a wiser consumer group. While the global initiative was operated from Zara's head office in Arteixo, Spain, it was Inditex's management board that guided Zara's strategic actions.

The above strategic rebranding campaign created chances of risks not to get positive feedback from consumers if the implementation went wrong. Moreover, ensuring quality and supply chain as per commitment was a huge challenge for the brand. Zara was operating in a

highly competitive online environment, wherein it became very difficult to distinguish itself from the younger luxury e-retailers. However, Zara opened itself to a new sensitive segment that has an opportunity to get higher margins and create more loyal customers. On the one hand, it escalated the degree of luxury and sustainability, which, in turn, discarded the primary customer base that initially valued Zara for its efficient and cheap clothing production. Thus, the improvement of the online sales platform was a long-term strategic move as the focus on this type of sale was the right decision to get competitive advantages due to the shift towards online shopping caused by the pandemic and changed consumer behaviour.

5.1.3 Rebranding process

The rebranding process for Zara started in January 2022 and ended in June 2022. This six-month period covered all the five fundamental stages of the rebranding process, guaranteeing a holistic change in the brand. The first stage is strategic planning and stakeholder engagement, an encompassing phase where Zara's management conducts a strategic analysis when communicating luxury positioning goals. This phase was important in all related departments, including design and development, product management, marketing, and supply chain management in readiness for change. In the second stage, product development and supply chain adjustments, involved the development of new competencies. This included modifying the supply chain management to seek sustainable materials and implementing recycling practices as they embrace the new luxury brand image.

The third activity was marketing and brand communication; in this stage, Zara had to advertise all over the world so that people would recognise the new image of the company. This required changing the logo and modifying the design of the stores' layouts as well as the messaging behind the advertisements, which focused on the reborn and luxurious Line. The fourth process, called phased marketing, involved a gradual unveiling of the rebranded Zara in sensitive markets for luxury and sustainability. This approach showed how the firm was capable of realising the consumer feeling and the sales performance as they adjusted their strategies accordingly. In the last stage, evaluation and continuous improvement focused on the constant analysis of the brand's performance in the new market segment through gathering and evaluating the response of the customers and the sales data to make improvements continually.

In Zara's rebranding strategy in the year 2022, categorisation is the Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand. There were various measures that Zara put in place to augment the rebranding effect. These were; partnerships with celebrities to reach large audiences, online engagements to interact with the audience, limited previews to create expectations, and generic promotions that would increase brand recognition. In this way, using the above-mentioned techniques, Zara was able to inform its new values of luxury and sustainability and became a pioneer in the new models of the fast fashion clothing industry.

5.1.4 The Results

Before the rebranding campaign in 2022, Zara was recognised as one of the leading retailers in the fast-fashion segment, offering customers cheap and affordable clothing items to follow any current trend. However, it came under pressure because of environmental issues and changing the customers' attitude towards sustainable production. For instance, at the beginning of the rebranding campaign, the market share of Zara in the luxury sector was much below the desired level and the company required a change to fit into the new market prerequisites. To manage the change, the company allocated a budget of £200m to £300m for marketing activities, changing brand images, redesigning stores, rebranding the logo, improving online interfaces, and incorporating sustainable practices. Managing the change was budgeted at between £200m and £300m for marketing activities, changing the brand image, store redesign, rebranding of the logo, and improving online interfaces as well as incorporating sustainable practices.

Essentially, the rebranding campaign is a holistic process that spans several months and encompasses several stages. The first process was, therefore, Strategic Planning and Stakeholder Engagement, which would entail a detailed analysis of the brand and its objectives. This was succeeded by Product Development and Supply Chain Adjustments in which Zara overhauled its products to focus on quality and sustainability. Marketing and Brand Communication covered activities such as beginning international campaigns and changes to the brand's image. Indeed, the Phased Market Rollout, a crucial process of the strategic rebranding campaign, consisted of an appropriate introduction of the new brand in carefully chosen markets.

This rebranding could not have happened without the implication of major actors such as designers, supply chain managers, and marketing departments. The rebranding attempts reinforced Zara's market stance, mainly in the US, UK, and Spanish markets. Zara, along

with other stores that came under Inditex, launched rebranding strategies in 2022 and the company registered huge financial results. Inditex's consolidated sales reached £30.5 billion in 2023, an increase of 10.4%; Zara's sales were £10.7 billion, up 13.1% from the previous year. The company increased total gross profit by 11.9% to £17.7 billion, resulting in a gross margin of 57.8%. The Operating profit, EBITDA, rose by 13.9% to £8.5 billion and operating profit, EBIT, rose by 23.4% to £5.8 billion. Profit before tax, which is the company's net income, also rose by 30.3% from the previous year to £4.6 billion. Even exclusively in online sales, Zara could increase its sales by 16% reaching £7.7 billion. To be specific, by the early 21st century, Inditex reached a market capitalisation of £95 billion. By the beginning of 2024, Zara had a total of 2,221 stores, which shows that the company intends to minimise the physical stores, aiming for a focus on the omnichannel experience. The shift has helped Zara to remain equal to online competitors such as Shein and Zalora, exhibiting strong signs of revival together with online sales recovery.

5.2. CASE B (BOOHOO GROUP PLC.)

5.2.1 The company and its market

Boohoo Group PLC was established in 2006, in Manchester, UK and through its fast-fashion value proposition, supply chain tactics, and an entirely online selling strategy, the company has become a prominent fast-fashion giant. To build up a wider range of brands, the company swooped in and bought a range of high-street brands that were in very bad shape, including Oasis, Warehouse, and Karen Millen. In January 2021 the Debenhams brand was bought by Boohoo for £55 million to expand its market into beauty, sport, and the home sectors. This became its main approach in operation when it sought to change Debenhams into an online retail store and become a firm rooted in e-commerce operations. The key action has been the rebranding of Debenhams, which was bought in January 2021 for £55 million. Debenhams was included in Boohoo's operations and was an online-only brand that offered only beauty, sport, and homeware products to its consumers, thus enhancing the product line of Boohoo Company. The online sector's acquiring percentage for the fiscal year ending February 28, 2022, was £1,982.8 million with an enhancement of 14% which shows that the rebranding campaign was successful. Thus, the company is utilising the best artificial intelligence

technologies to enhance customer satisfaction, improve production effectiveness, and keep its dominant position in the e-commerce market.

Overall, Boohoo had a solid market position, however, it faced challenges to take new strategies to get competitive advantages in the highly competitive high-street clothing market. Though the company's revenues have remained robust with 41 per cent growth in 2021, Boohoo has had some challenges, including labour relations, working conditions, and sustainability concerns. The company has faced backlash over labour issues such as low wages and other undesirable working conditions at its suppliers. To face the challenges, Boohoo acted to remove the lack of transparency issues and labour relations initiatives like Agenda for Change with Sir Brian Leveson and KPMG to enhance and reform the company governance and ethical standards.

On the other hand, the strengths of Boohoo include well-developed internet accessibility, a diverse range of brands, and the company holding a large market share internationally. It is noted that the majority of sales originate from regions such as the United States and Europe, with around 50% of the company's sales being in these areas. The current market situation is still a kind of mixed picture for Boohoo until the year 2024. After the rebranding campaign, results showed that the company generated an annual figure of £1,982. 8 million in sales by February 2022; further, the market capitalisation worth was roughly £4.2 billion in early 2024.

5.2.2 Rebranding in company

In January 2021, Boohoo Group PLC started a massive rebranding process after they purchased the Debenhams brand for 55 million Pounds spot. The process of rebranding was known as 'Debenhams.com' on June 25, 2021. The form of rebranding applied here is mainly corporate rebranding. In concept, it implies the conversion of Debenhams from a typical retail outlet to solely an internet-based brand that comes under the Boohoo group. The main reason for this was to leverage the already recognised Debenhams brand, huge customer base and significant online presence to expand the Boohoo range into beauty, sport and homeware.

The rebranding process that was carried out here was a radical change on the corporate level due to internal and external modifications. From an internal perspective, Boohoo assimilated Debenhams' brand and customer data into its technological ecosystem, but on the outside,

managed to preserve Debenhams' brand name. At the same time, Boohoo redeployed the online shop front with various new generalist product categories. The process did not entail buying any of Debenhams' actual shops or its employees, which underscored an online focus. The management of this rebranding was taken by the executive management of Boohoo, the chief executive officer John Lyttle and the executive chairman Mahmud Kamani who saw the reasons behind this acquisition as strategically beneficial for growth.

Boohoo's strategy was to acquire Debenhams with the dual approach of making Boohoo the largest online marketplace in the UK. However, the campaign also had notable threats like how it would manage reputation risks related to Boohoo following previous labour issues, or how it ensured that Debenhams' operations did not water down the campaign's brand. To tackle these issues, Boohoo adopted the "Agenda for Change" led by Sir Brian Leveson and supported by KPMG to enhance corporate governance and the substantiality of the supply chain.

5.2.3 Rebranding Process in the company

In January 2021, the Boohoo Group PLC first embarked on a rebranding exercise after it bought Debenhams. The acquisition of Debenhams' brand by Boohoo Group PLC was done in five phases and it normally lasts for about six months. The formal rebranding slogan was conducted online and called 'Debenhams.com', after the firm was acquired in January 2021. This acquisition was crucial for Boohoo because it helped the company tap into the consumers who were previously associated with Debenhams, including older clients, thus diversifying its consumer base and improving its brand assortment.

Over several months, the rebranding campaign was divided into five phases. The first step, therefore, focused on the strategic planning and engagement of stakeholders, mainly entailed the enhancement of the understanding of the various departments' goals. Second, product development and supply chain adjustments emphasised improving the quality of Boohoo products that reflect its new brand reputation. The third phase, known as marketing and brand communication, included the initiation of global campaigns, changes in logos, and the design of stores to match the new luxury look. The fourth step, market penetration with the selective relaunch of the rebranded Debenhams, involved the gradual introduction of Boohoo's rebranded department store in certain pockets to measure the reaction of the consumers.

Eventually, the fifth stage, evaluation and continuous improvement, concentrated on the evaluation of its compliance with demands and its improvements based upon the consumers' feedback and flow of sales and, thereby, the brand's compliance with consumer needs in the market.

Regarding the analysis of Boohoo's acquisition and subsequent rebranding of Debenhams, the strategy adopted is the "Combined Rebranding Strategy via the One Umbrella Brand." Also, this fashion retailer borrowed the use of endorsement and celebrity partnerships, engaging and shareable social media and web content, early access to new products, and product-consistent partnership marketing. These strategies aided in creating awareness of the new brand values and also increased the target market reach, thus promoting Boohoo as a major player in the e-commerce industry. The rebranding campaign was an instance of a corporate-level strategic move approved by Boohoo's Chief Executive Officer John Lyttle, and the Executive Chairman Mahmud Kamani, realising the long-term prospects of the acquisition.

5.2.4 The results

Debenhams seemed to be severely stressed financially before becoming a part of the Boohoo Group PLC. The historic department store had seen changes in administration twice in two years; once in the year 2019 and then in April 2020, due to a slump in sales, as the COVID-19 pandemic led to the shutdown of outlets for non-essential items. Fundamentally, Debenhams' old-world strategy of relying on its huge centralised department stores failed to compete against the growing dominance of online platforms and review was liquidated. It was rather critical, mainly because 118 outlets shut their doors to business and over 12,000 people lost their places of work. For £55 million, Boohoo Group purchased rights for the acquiring of the Debenhams brand, trademarks, and databases of customers, but did not acquire any selling space or the employees of the latter.

The rebranding program was very comprehensive and expensive, even though the exact numbers of the amounts spent have not been released to the public. The post-rebranding scenario also implied serious transformations and the participation of many community members in the absorption of Debenhams within Boohoo's predominantly online environment. Boohoo launched the 'Agenda for Change' program headed by Sir Brian Leveson and KPMG to deal with excellent corporate governance and supply chain issues. This was very important in responding to previous criticisms of the company's labour

relations and improving its image. Following its rebranding, revenues of Boohoo group increased by 14% and recorded £1,982. 8m by the end of February 28, 2022, which signifies that the merging and acquiring of other brands expanded the market share of Boohoo successfully. The rebranding campaign also caused the adoption of artificial intelligence that enabled the firm to enhance client interactions and maximise efficiency to retain competitiveness in the emergent online shopping space.

Boohoo was able to expand the range and enter the beauty, sport, and home segments under the Debenhams name, which attracted customers of any age. When it comes to the data about the markets, Boohoo's market share remains an object of its rebranding in this aspect. By the beginning of 2024, the market capitalisation of Boohoo was £4.2 billion. The company's strategic target is to obtain an adjusted EBITDA margin of 6%-8% in the medium term, compared to the predicted 4%- 4.5% for the year 2023/24. Some of the problems that have been noted are a rise in returns, and issues with supply chains, however, the company is continuously emphasising the implementation of high-quality sales, as well as shedding stocks by 36%. These efforts have kept Boohoo intact in the market to be among the few preferred brands in the online retail business.

5.3. CASE C (MARKS AND SPENCER)

5.3.1 The Company and Its Market

Marks & Spencer, commonly known as M&S, is a retailing giant that originated in the United Kingdom, precisely in Leeds in the year 1884 by Michael Marks and Thomas Spencer. M&S has become popular in the United Kingdom and across the globe, offering quality clothing, homeware, and food. In its many years of business operation, M&S has created a strong position in the market regarding innovation, quality, and the ability to meet customer needs. To diversify its product quality ranges, M&S purchased the brand "Jaeger" in January 2021 for £6 million. Jaeger is also a clothing brand founded in 1884 and is recognised for its fine fabrics and traditional British sensibility. The rebranding campaign for Jaeger, which was officially initiated in October 2021 attempted to retain Jaeger's identity into the brand of M&S by integrating it into the existing brand practices of M&S. Since 2023, the products of Jaeger have been displayed in M&S outlets and supermarkets of M&S. Made in London, superior quality of clothing, recognition of the sterilised English look, and the green approach in production are the key differentiating factors of Jaeger brand.

M&S is established in the UK market, holding more than 7.6% of the total market share of the ready-made garments sector in the UK. In addition, the market share of M&S in the clothing and homeware sub-sector has increased to 1.5% in the year 2023 from the last year. This improvement is believed to be done because of the rebranding of M&S through the acquisition of Jaeger brand, which helped to increase M&S's business among classy and rich customers. E-commerce has also been a key driver, with e-sales amounting to £3,2bn in 2023, up from £2,7bn, resulting in a 17% increase from 2022. Before the acquisition, M&S had to deal with some issues, including high operating costs and the necessity of bringing new ideas to get competitive advantages in the market. To manage challenges, the company focused on acquisitions, brand management, and environmentalism. Currently, M&S sets goals of the use of 100% sustainable cotton by 2025 and the emission of carbon to zero by 2040. The management team headed by Stuart Machin is very positive, focusing on strategy development and implementation through innovation, customer relations, and sustainability in all business activities. By early 2024, the market capitalisation of M&S is £9.5 billion, which shows that the investors still have faith and trust in the company. Thus, organisational moves such as the rebranding campaign of Jaeger expanded business opportunities in existing and new markets for M&S.

5.3.2 Rebranding in the Company

In January 2021, M&S purchased the equity of the brand Jaeger for £6 million. The main rationale for this rebranding was to include a high-quality and traditional brand into the M&S brand list and to attract more affluent clients. The new campaign, referred to as the “Jaeger Relunched” formally kicked off on the 6th of October 2021. This rebranding campaign of revolutionary change was intended to preserve Jaeger’s brand identity while updating the company’s image and making it more compatible with the M&S outlet setting. The rebranding campaign focused on premium fabrics, a clean-cut English image, environment-friendly manufacturing, and essential attributes to modern consumer consciousness to match M&S’s long-term vision.

In the UK, the design of Jaeger products with exclusive raw materials such as silk, wool and cashmere ensures the brand’s quality and elegance. Internally, this rebranding campaign incorporated a new design for the logos as well as new branding items. Externally, the products of Jaeger were displayed in M&S stores initially during the trial period in October

2021 and 2023. The decision-making was organised for Jaeger by the managing director Fiona Lambert in consultation with the top management of M&S including Steve Rowe, the CEO, and Richard Price, the managing director of clothing and home at M&S.

It is also noticed that this rebranding campaign of the acquisition of Jaeger was not easy to implement, as the integration into a big retailer network might diminish the exclusivity of the brand Jaeger. Sometimes, customers might get confused about the quality and ethnicity commitment of the brand Jaeger under the umbrella of M&S. On the other hand, the prospect of this rebranding campaign was to use M&S's well-developed retail network and increase online sales. The rebranding also ensured Jaeger's concern for sustainability through the strategic involvement of M&S. The rebranding of the brand Jaeger was positioned to ensure premium quality clothing through M&S's large scale and operational effectiveness.

5.3.3 Rebranding process in the company

Jaeger brand's rebranding under Marks & Spencer (M&S) took five steps, approximately 2 years and 1 month from January 2021. The 1st phase of this rebranding campaign was strategic planning and stakeholder management, which was composed of formulating the goals and key activities in the various organisational departments of M&S for the integration of Jaeger into M&S's retail context. The second phase of rebranding was product development and design which concentrated on the renovation of Jaeger's product offerings in fabrics and materials symbolising a sophisticated English spirit, while the clothing products were designed and made in London using silk, wool, and cashmere. The third stage of this rebranding campaign was marketing and brand communication from January 2021 through redesigning Jaeger's logo and undertaking a worldwide advertising campaign with an emphasis on quality, sustainability, and British contemporaneity. The phased market rollout, the fourth stage, was initiated in late 2021 as a trial of Jaeger products' display in several M&S high street stores. Within the year 2023, the key stores within M&S, like Bluewater, Camberley, and Marble Arch, were offering a wider range of Jaeger products. This phase ensured that M&S had the opportunity to obtain feedback from the customers to make any necessary changes. The last and fifth stage of this rebranding campaign was evaluation and continuous improvement. From 2023 up to mid-2024, M&S remained cautious about the results of the Jaeger rebranding by tracking consumer responses and sales figures.

The rebranding applied the campaign strategy of combining branding via one umbrella brand. This branding campaign strategy enabled Jaeger to continue with its differentiation strategy, while at the same leveraging on the retail infrastructure and e-commerce platform that M&S had put in place. Thus, using this strategy, M&S planned to rejuvenate Jaeger and, at the same time, strengthen the company's market position based on the brand image of Jaeger. This has been achieved through the implementation of this rebranding strategy in the M&S portfolio. This strategic rebranding also enabled M&S to build a range of premium consumers. The campaign also ensures higher quality and sustainability in clothing, which are relevant to the conscious consumption decisions of consumers worldwide.

5.3.4 The Result

Before M&S acquired Jaeger in January 2021 the company experienced the need for change in its market to get competitive advantages. Considering the utmost necessity of innovation, Jaeger was bought by M&S to bring changes to the company. The rebranding process, spanning more than two years, involved five stages including strategic planning, product development, marketing and brand communication, phases for market entry and subsequent and sustaining change. The key reasons for rebranding stemmed from the desire to retain the classic and iconic image of Jaeger, bringing it into the twenty-first century within the retail environment of M&S. The strategy employed for the rebranding was the 'Combined Rebranding under a Single Umbrella Branding Strategy' that let Jaeger continue with an independent existence while taking advantage of the large formats and client base of M&S.

The Jaeger relaunch officially commenced on the sixth of October 2021. Jaeger products, manufactured in London, offered materials such as silk, wool and cashmere which embodied the exclusive and sophisticated look of the English people. By 2023, the Jaeger products were introduced in M&S stores, although initially tested in flagship stores such as Bluewater, Camberley and Marble Arch. By this rebranding campaign, M&S was able to gather insights from the customers and make some improvements where necessary.

This rebranding campaign of M&S ensured better sales and profitability in the UK. In the fiscal year that ended on 1st April 2023, the revenue of M&S was higher by 9.6% to £11.93 billion from the previous fiscal year. The clothing and home sub-segment had an increase of 11% in business from 2022 to 2023. Other sources of sales also experienced growth; online

sales posted an equal growth with total e-commerce revenues of £3.2 billion in 2023 resulting in a 17% increase in online sales from the previous year. The combination created an increased market share for M&S and improved the company's brand identity by matching modern consumerism attributes of premium quality, sustainability, ethnicity, and differentiation. Thus, the market capitalisation of M&S was raised to around £9.5 billion, which was possible through the continuation of investors' confidence and an effective rebranding exercise that placed Jaeger brand successfully in the portfolio of M&S.

5.4. CASE D (NEXT PLC)

5.4.1 The Company and Its Market

Next PLC is the subsequent multinational retailer based in the UK from the foundation of Joseph Hepworth and his Son in 1864. It has developed into one of the prime retail chains, exclusive for fashion, and homeware requirements, with more than 500 outlets in the UK and Ireland alone and recognised globally. In 2018, the "Next Directory" dropped the word "Directory" from its name and changed its name to "Next Online", in a sign of changing with the times as it sought to properly establish Omni channel strategies. In a bid to simplify its online operations and due to the expansion of the increased online shopping business, the firm did this rebranding campaign. Next PLC's new business-level strategy aligned it into the market and focused on a strong e-commerce site coupled with its large and effective physical store outlets.

Appeal analysis in a brand audit points out several advantages of Next, including the well-developed website of the brand, the large number of types of products it offers, and the brand image in the sphere of quality and reliability it ensures. It also reveals threats like high competition in the online clothing market, and the company has to constantly adapt and reinvent itself. Nevertheless, Next PLC has recorded growth, thus exemplifying each of the challenges below. Next has declared its revenue for the year that ended on January 27, 2024, and it was worth £5.49 billion, which shows a percentage rise of 9.08%. In 2024, the company had its market capitalisation at about £11.75 billion, of which Next PLC exhibited high investors' confidence. The physical as well as that of integrated online shopping experiences employed by Next PLC has been instrumental in sustaining its market position.

Also, Next has been involved in mergers and acquisitions and this has helped to enhance its market position as well as diversify its products.

The Next advancement under the leadership of Chief Executive Officer Lord Wolfson has also worked hard towards sustainable growth and has put much effort in adapting to market developments. The change of its name to Next Online is useful to this company because it experienced its highest profit margins and grew a robust online marketplace for other brands. The above rebranding campaign has enabled Next PLC to survive, some of the Shifts in the retail markets that have been counteracted by this strategic move. Next PLC's current market environment remains competitive with further capital expenditure on e-commerce and sustainability, thus, making Next PLC one of the industry's most updated retail companies.

5.4.2 Rebranding Campaign in the Company

The purpose of this rebranding campaign to rename Next Direct was to fully concentrate on sales in the online platform. Therefore, the company's e-commerce arm was completed at the beginning of the year on January 1, 2018, marking the starting point of the Next Online business. This campaign was called 'Next Online Evolution', which was a major change in focus from a catalogue-based retail business to a more technological and advanced concept of selling online. The key point behind this rebranding campaign here was to achieve efficiency in the group's online operations and sell to the rising online shopping process that was rapidly transforming the retail industry. The campaign, which was initiated in January 2018, wanted to combine the Omni channel organisation and a suitable platform that would complement the huge store network of the company. This particular corporate-level strategy of repositioning aimed at building on Next PLC's core competence but emphasised the company as a provider of online retail.

The branding transformation was internal and external to a great extent. Internally, this involved the incorporation of superior online technologies to boost and develop the user interface, the flow of supplies, and checking inventory. External changes established during the campaign included the alteration of the Next Online logo and changes to all brand communication approaches to correspond to the contemporary, technology-oriented company image. The decision-making process was a result of the decision that came from CEO Lord Simon Wolfson and the top management team comprised Amanda James who is working as the chief financial officer and Richard Papp who is working as the group merchandise and

operations director. He was behind the management of these rebranding exercises from the company's head office in Enderby, United Kingdom.

In this rebranding campaign, the strategic threats were in the form of disruption of the business module of the catalogue customer base, on the other hand, opportunities were identified to be in the form of the expansion of market share on the e-commerce segment, and use of Total Platform in providing third-party brands' complete facility of internet services. This decision was not only beneficial in terms of increasing additional sources of income, but it also helped Next to strengthen its status as a progressive and dynamically developing retail chain. The performance of the current campaign is well illustrated at Next, with the company having a financial growth of 9.08%, and a market capital of £11.75 billion, showing that it is well positioned in the market and well favoured by investors.

5.4.3 Rebranding process

Next Directory was transformed to Next Online formerly known as Next Online Evolution in January 2018 and by the end of the same year, a shift was focused on improving the e-business of Next PLC. This rebranding campaign was successfully implemented through three carefully laid stages, making it easy to synchronise with Next PLC's business processes.

The first stage of this rebranding campaign was the strategic planning and integration stage, in which Next PLC's management team headed by Chief Executive Officer Lord Simon Wolfson developed the specific general plan for such transformation. In this stage, the process of integrating the resources of Next Directory with Next PLC's huge infrastructure consisted of e-commerce operations; the company envisioned existing synergies between the catalogue business model and e-commerce. Subsequently, the second phase, technology upgrade and system optimisation mainly focused on improving the online portal and updating the information technology systems. There were focuses on enhancing the convenience of operations and the performance of online users. Here, the consumers had to go through checkout flaws and to the sales through a mobile application since the trend of using mobiles had been increasing for the purchase of products through the internet. The last stage of the rebranding campaign, named marketing and brand communication, entailed a structural change in the entire brand's interface on the Internet. This comprised the unveiling of a new streamlined logo and the launching of direct marketing online strategies meant to reach out to

a wider internet-based community as a positive way of informing the public that the company is more determined to provide its internet users with a modern shopping portal.

During the entire change of identity, Next Online employed a Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand. This way, the brand not only identified and maintained the customer base, but also successfully evolved its business through a proper combination of the mail-order catalogue system with the flexibility of the web-based platform. Laying down this strategy has contributed to Next PLC's growth in a big way; Next PLC has seen huge jumps in online revenues and market share, which has helped Next to become a dominant retail chain in the UK.

5.4.4 The Result

Before the change of the name from Next Directory to Next Online in early 2018, Next PLC was struggling to adapt to rapid changes in the retail environment, characterised by a shift from print catalogue selling to online selling. This rebranding campaign is characterised by the fact that most consumers switched to online shopping primarily because it is more convenient. This realisation made it compulsory for Next to go for a branding exercise that would ensure that besides surviving, they would have better market growth in this e-commerce world.

The rebranding campaign of the change from Next Directory to Next Online required a huge capital, which is typical for such extensive companies' online transformations. These expenses involved technological improvements, system linkages, and some of the heaviest marketing campaigns needed to convey the new strategic changes in brand image to consumers. After this rebranding campaign, the outcomes were mostly positive. Next PLC had recorded a substantially enhanced and higher figure in the next fiscal year, January 2024 to be precise, where it had recorded £5.49 billion in the overall revenue status of the business and thus, it experienced a comparative growth of more than nine per cent in 2023-2024 from the last fiscal year. This growth was helped by the synchronisation of online and offline orders that concretised Next's strong Omni channel integration of physical stores with online platforms.

Next was well poised to seize this trend more strategically by not only developing more products but also extending the services they offer to other brands, hence increasing the client base. Besides improving Next's market presentation, it also carved out a niche in the market

to enable it to grab market share. Thus, Next's online sales per cent of total sales more than double by 2024 and reach 50%; the figure was 35 % before the rebranding process. It was possible due to strong investor confidence, as the companies' market capitalisation stood at approximately £11.75bn. Thus, the indicated position on the market may be regarded as rather stable. This rebranding campaign of the brand's renewal and the company's shift towards more online operations enabled Next to reach the highest profit margins it has ever recorded, which proves the success of the proposed strategy. Thus, this change met the existing market requirements by creating the foundations for long-term expansion; therefore, it helped Next reveal its aptitude for success in the era of fast retail and online shopping.

5.5 CASE E (H&M)

5.5.1 The Company and its Market

Launched in 1947 in Västerås in Sweden, it now serves as one of the largest fashion retailers in the world. By May 31, 2024, H&M engaged 77 markets and 4,338 stores. By the bonanza season of 2024/2025, H&M will deliver its products to 60 nations, demonstrating its blended sales strategy in both high street and online platforms. This is a part of the company's omnichannel strategy that seeks to harmonise the physical and online shopping processes to provide consumers with more and better shopping points. H&M's aim to increase transparency and sustainability started noticeably in 2019 as it established itself as a pioneer in disclosing material and supply chain information of its clothing products to the public. The company made this decision to increase resistance and transparency in the fashion world and gain a competitive advantage.

In 2017, more precisely in the 'Our Water Approach,' H&M planned specific objectives regarding the use of recycled and sustainably sourced materials, these rebranding strategies have been worthy for H&M. In the year 2023 the net sales of H&M was £20.39 billion (SEK 236,035 million) from the previous year 2022. The gross profit was £10.43 billion (SEK 120,896 million) in 2023, implying an increase in the company's gross margin, which depicts operational efficiency and focuses on sustainable practices at a lower cost.

In this contemporary global market, H&M has a clear focus on online growth and sustainability; these two aspects have been key factors in the company's growth and

increased market share. With the increase in online sales, the internet continues to be a significant driver for the growth of H&M, and e-commerce sales constitute 30% of total net sales. H&M has been strategic in adopting the 'e-commerce first' and 'green' strategies, which have prolonged H&M's competitive advantage in the market by accommodating a wider base of environmentally conscious consumers. The stock market value of the company was around SEK 330 billion (£27 billion) in early 2024 as investors had faith in the rebranding strategy and sustainability activities done by the company.

The management of the company, currently led by CEO Helena Helmersson, focuses on innovation and change so that the company stays relevant in the current fast-changing retail market environment. In regard to the overall value of the company, which reflects how much trust investors have in H&M, the company believed that, this rebranding campaign would give them an advantage over competitors in the fashion industry. Thus, such positioning contributes to the improvement of the company's brand image and strengthens dominance in the market through achieving global goals of creating sustainable and ethical clothing lines.

5.5.2 Rebranding in the company

In early 2019, H&M launched its major campaign "Transparency in Fashion" which is considered as the beginning of a change in the clothing industry. The intention for this campaign was the rise of consumers' concerns with the product's origin and the effects of the production of clothes and other textile products on the environment. The campaign targeted disclosing information to the customers about the particular materials being used and supply chain sources, which can be categorised as business unit rebranding. This campaign made H&M the pioneer of the high-street retail industry for its supply chain transparency. This initiative included stating the production countries, supplier names, factory details, and the actual materials used in every garment, which customers can read on the tags and the online descriptions of the products. Such a type of rebranding at the level of a company was crucial for synchronising H&M's brand image with the company's values regarding sustainability and ethical standards.

The management level of the company took the decision-making regarding this rebranding campaign. Helena Helmersson, H&M CEO and Leyla Ertur, head of sustainability are directing from H&M's head office in Stockholm, Sweden. Nowadays, the company views this campaign as a historical milestone because it introduced comprehensive innovations in terms of transparency and sustainability within the fashion clothing industry. The rebranding

process involved making internal and external changes, including transforming the brand's communication tools and ensuring that all forms of marketing highlighted H&M's shift to the ethical fashion category. Here, the tactical risk involved was the denial of the supply chain partners to share actual information. Furthermore, H&M had to bear a considerable amount of cost in implementing these transparency initiatives. However, the opportunities were incredible, since these steps made H&M a leader in sustainable fashion among customers who care about the environment.

Considering the context and consequences of the rebranding, the following changes were figured out in the case of H&M's campaign. For instance, the company's position in the market had been enhanced and H&M noticed a positive shift in terms of brand image. Through this campaign, the company gained further market share and a positive impact among ethical consumers. The company aimed to source 100% of its raw materials from sustainable sources by 2030. H&M also decided further to create a positive climate by the year 2040 by using recycled and sustainably sourced materials. This campaign not only improved H&M's competitiveness but also strengthened the sustainability-oriented fashion businesses of this company worldwide.

5.5.3 Rebranding Process

The rebranding process was divided into three major phases and took roughly one year to complete; it began in early 2019 and was accomplished by December of the same year. The initial step was the strategic analysis, which aimed to be transparent in supply chain sourcing. The second step involved planning and managing stakeholders, which included aligning rebranding goals and gaining support from key stakeholders. This stage concentrated on what could be achievable, and where each department could understand the key directions and motives of the sustainability campaign. The third phase of this rebranding campaign was implementation and technological integration. This means the creation of tracking systems and disclosure of data of the production countries, the names of the suppliers, the names of the factories involved in product manufacturing, and the materials. This stage entailed a lot of administrative activities and input in terms of technology and infrastructure for data capturing. Here, marketing and brand communications were involved in changing the product tags and online descriptions by incorporating transparent information and launching a global marketing campaign about the initiative. This rebranding campaign focused on establishing the company's sustainable policies and encouraging environmentally conscious consumers to

get connected with the company's supply chain transparency. The final stage of this rebranding campaign process was evaluation. In 2019, H&M was one of the top five brands having 61% Fashion Transparency Index while the highest mark was 65%.

This global change in the brand image identified in this research is an obvious example of the "Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand". This strategy served the purpose of expanding upon H&M's existing brand equity through the adoption of sustainability as a key growth centre while at the same time continuing to appeal to the mass market. Consumer's potential lack of trust and the difficulty of implementing and maintaining detailed and sensitive supply chain information posed strategic threats. Nevertheless, it was equally critical to offer potential benefits such as customer retention, competitive advantage within the fast-fashion segment, and compliance with worldwide environmental standards.

As of the end of December 2023, H&M made considerable progress towards the sustainable strategy; 97% of the supply chain's use of cotton was recycled or sourced sustainably, while 57% of all materials used were produced sustainably. These actions have further solidified the company's image while ensuring ethical business practices; they have also contributed to operational improvements and market expansion. This rebranding campaign has proved successful, thus placing H&M as one of the front-runners in the sustainable fashion market and has been attracting fashion-conscious consumers who are aware of the impacts of clothing buying decisions on the environment.

5.5.4 The Result

H&M is one of the world's largest fashion companies, which has been operating in the high-street retail market with sustainability concerns. The consumers began doubting the transparency of the high-street retailers, pointing out social irresponsibility within the firm's external environmental endeavours. That is why the necessity to respond to these problems and meet the new consumer's demand by acting in a socially responsible and transparent way became the key reason for starting the largest campaign of H&M, "Transparency in Fashion". This was carried out to offer clear specifications of the materials utilised in the supply chain at the product level to attain a higher degree of transparency in comparison with industry rivals in the high-street retail industry.

The rebranding process and commitment to sustainability required a lot of funds in the whole year of 2019. In itself, the rebranding did not reveal total cost expenditure; however, for the

initiative to engulf new technologies, ensure new labelling for products, and do marketing of the idea worldwide, H&M had to involve significant amounts of resources. These expenditures included a larger energy reinvention, which was approximately SEK 10 billion (£823 million) of capital investments.

This rebranding has had its effect as the following discussion will show. H&M became the fourth highest fashion retailer in the Fashion Transparency Index in 2019, while the other retailers are Adidas, Reebok, and Patagonia with 64% and Esprit with 62%. This also led H&M to improve in transparency index by 6% points from 2018 to 2019. According to the company statistics, there was a downward flow of net sales in 2020 because of the COVID-19 pandemic, though net sales and gross profit increased gradually every year from 2020 and in 2023 gross profit increased by 7% from the last year, which is around £10.43 billion (SEK 120,896 million). This ensures better operational efficiency coupled with sustainable methods. The support from all the related parties, such as suppliers, manufacturers, and other stakeholders in sustainability was also vital for the success of the rebranding campaign. All these long-term strategic changes collectively repositioned H&M's brand image, optimised operational efficiencies, and boosted its market performance.

5.6. Individual Case Study Analysis by Propositions

In this section of this business research paper, the case study's findings will be analysis based on the eleven study propositions developed in chapter three earlier. Each research proposition will be stated first with a rationale describing the origin of the propositions in chapters 2 and 3. The main purpose of this section is not to find any conclusion here but to analyse the data according to the research propositions. The next chapter of this research paper will analyse and interpret the findings. Under each proposition, the rebranding campaigns of all five selected companies are analysed here.

5.6.1. The nature of Rebranding

P1: Rebranding is a revolutionary change to the brand name, which differs from evolutionary changes of the branding attributes like; colour, logo, and slogan

5.6.1.1 Rationale:

From the literature review chapter, no clear explanation was found regarding the nature and practices of rebranding. The author likes to distinguish renaming and other brand attributes, including logos and slogans, through brand evolution and brand revolution. Brand evolution is a process by which brands grow gradually and undergo minor changes that are necessary to maintain the state of the brand. In contrast, brand revolution is an action that implies a deliberate transformation of a brand that was not carried out as ordinary updates. The brand name change represents a revolutionary action, whereas the other brand features are incremental and do not align with rebranding. This proposition aims to examine the case study perspective on the prospects of rebranding, brand revolution, and brand evolution.

5.6.1.2 CASE A: ZARA

Case A describes the rebranding campaign of Zara in 2022, known as “Zara Redefined”. Here, the name of the brand remained the same, while everything else changed, including the logo and new store layouts, which were all redesigned to promote luxury and sustainability. In 2023 Gasamán Gesto stated that, “This large-scale change was used to align the brand with a greener and, therefore, more luxurious demographic”. Thus, in light of Proposition P1, which suggests that rebranding is revolutionary only if the company changes its brand name, the rebranding campaign described in Case A is evolutionary. In this regard, Iglesias-Pérez stated in 2024 that, “This rebranding process also eliminated the stereotype that a name change is the only way of rebranding”.

Zara experimented with many changes in its strategy and appearance, thus, the company’s approach to the brand fitted into the concept of evolutionary rebranding as the organisation did not change the brand name. After the evaluation of its market and, Cooke, Nunes, Oliva, and Lazzeretti suggested in 2022 that, “these changes were warmly welcomed” and sales reports also declared that Zara’s e-sales increased from £6.7 billion in 2022 to £7.7 billion in 2023. Evidence refutes the assertion provided by Proposition P1, which contends that the revolutionary change requires a mere change of name, on the other hand, evolutionary changes in the brand positioning and market strategies can make the brand successful under the existing brand name.

5.6.1.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Case B describes Boohoo Group PLC, which retained the Debenhams label through acquisition in 2021 and rebranded Debenhams as an online-only store, 'Debenhams.com'. This strategic move questions Proposition P1 as explained by BBC News in 2021, which expected a change of name as the only revolutionary rebranding. In this case, through the purchase of Debenhams brand, Boohoo was able to take advantage of the existing customers and integrate it with an entirely different business model, substituting the department store model with new beauty, sport, and homeware sections for increased sales.

Based on the theory mentioned in proposition P1, in 2024 Douglass viewed "this rebranding case of Boohoo as an evolution, considering the intermediate to the large level of differentiation in operation without changing the name". However, the author wants to categorise it as a revolution because of the radical change undertaken and the outcome of the rebranding campaign. Boohoo Group PLC's annual report and accounts also validated improved sales in 2023 by 14% from the previous year. It is found here that changing a company's structure and strategies under the existing brand label can align with the rebranding effects of the brand revolution. Therefore, after reviewing case B of Boohoo, it can be said that proposition P1 is not necessarily confined within the conventional definition of rebranding.

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5.6.1.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

CASE C discussed that, in January 2021, M&S bought Jaeger, a move that was followed by the implementation of a rebranding process of the accommodation of a new brand maintaining the brand's existence. This strategy is called Jaeger Relaunched, which aimed at strengthening the company's focus on the use of premium fabrics and British cultural references and integrate it with M&S's current targeted positioning. Proposition P1 defines rebranding as revolutionary when it includes the name of the organisation. For this reason, Carvill described "M&S's rebranding strategy is evolutionary" in 2024. They continued to use the Jaeger name, integrating its image with the M&S retail structure without changing its name, hence implying the evolutionary attributes of brands.

These changes were made progressively by market tests to suit Jaeger's quality and concern for the environment globally. By 2023, this integration was demonstrated in all M&S stores

and improved the company's revenues by 9.6%, which proves the financial growth achieved from this rebranding campaign. This process exemplifies how rebranding can successfully appeal to and expand a brand's market reach, on the primary understanding that rebranding is not a model restricted to name changes, thus questioning the conventional definition of revolutionary rebranding.

5.6.1.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Case D discussed Next, a prominent UK retailer, which renamed its business from 'Next Directory' in 2018 to 'Next Online', which depicted the integrated form of online sales. This rebranding complies with proposition P1 which "focuses on changes that often occur and are characterised by the change of name" as stated by Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria in 2020. Next PLC's decision regarding the change of its name was also considered strategic to mark the company's transition from purely catalogue-based selling to a more contemporary form of selling through online platforms. This change was not only a nominal phenomenon but also required to modify the company's intrinsic and extrinsic business practices to improve its online presence and facilitate more efficient and effective utilisation of the online consumer base.

As stated by Chapman, "The rebranding campaign referred to as Next Online helped Next easily become an online retailer" in 2023, where its presence is largely on online platforms. Specifically, this rebranding led to the enhancement of the competitive advantages of this brand and the adaptation to consumers' shift to online shopping. It is also shown in the case study that Next PLC posted a 9.08% growth in its revenues by the end of the financial year in January 2024. This case shows how a name change can generate an organisational transformation, thus supporting Proposition P1.

5.6.1.6 CASE E: H&M

In Case E, it is discussed how H&M implemented the "Transparency in Fashion" initiative in 2019, which revolutionised the company's approach to sustainability and ethical practices in apparel and clothing. As stated by H&M Group in 2023, "this strategic shift entrenched the new standards into the working of H&M", tagging specific information concerning sources of the material and methods of production on the labels and descriptions of the products. No alteration in the brand name occurred here, but the degree and profoundness of the changes

employed resembled revolutionary changes in business practice and brand identity, similar to the propositions that revolutionary change may imply a complete rebranding.

This rebranding process was considered successful, as in 2024 Robertson found that, “it not only exhibited better financial status but also developed competitive advantages for H&M”. In this regard, ECDB stated in 2024 that, “the promotion of sustainable materials not only helped enhance the organisation’s image but also revolutionised the high-street retail industry by setting an example of transparency in the high-street retail clothing business”. This approach showed that, by applying versatile changes in all aspects of business and brand elements without changing the brand name, it was possible to introduce a brand revolution. Thus, this rebranding campaign met the conceptual and perceptive ideas of rebranding transformation propositions.

5.6.2. Rebranding Use as a Unique Strategy

P2: Rebranding is a strategy that differentiates from other types of marketing techniques such as repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning.

5.6.2.1 Rationale:

It was seen in the Literature Review chapter that the common marketing activities such as repositioning, refreshing, repackaging are often viewed as rebranding. Although these activities can facilitate rebranding and may successfully be integrated with the rebranding process, the researcher of this paper contends that such activities cannot be called rebranding. Also, all these initiatives are just considered as different marketing categories and therefore, should not be categorised under ‘rebranding’ and rebranding should be considered as a separate marketing strategy in addition to these activities. This is a continuation of the earlier assertion that rebranding requires a brand name change; hence, if there is no name change, repositioning, repackaging, and refreshment cannot be deemed as rebranding. Thus, it can be considered that propositions one and two are interrelated.

5.6.2.2 CASE A: ZARA

Case A, Zara Redefined, was a strategic change in 2022 including the change of its logo, the physical rearrangement of stores, the use of sustainable fabrics in apparel, and environmentally friendly processes in the production of Zara’s clothes. Bhute explained in 2023 that, “The rebranding was intended to operate in conjunction with the emerging

generation of consumerism that integrates the aspects of environmental protection and product quality instead of adopting the traditional Zara model of fast fashion”. This campaign is not a mere change in logo, packaging or image, but a careful and thorough rebranding to “reposition Zara in the competitive luxury clothing market and target a new demographic of socially aware consumers” as stated by Nickels and Hugh in 2024.

Based on Proposition P2, rebranding is distinguished from repositioning or repackaging or refreshing, which means that the idea of rebranding implies rather different, top-tier changes in the brand’s strategic map and values. This was accomplished by modifying internal processes as well as external aspects that are visible to the consumer and aimed at reflecting a new, luxurious, and environmentally friendly brand image. Thus, this campaign of Zara can be categorised as rebranding instead of repositioning; rather, repositioning features are used here to facilitate rebranding. Singh stated in 2024 that “these changes have helped Zara to penetrate the luxury segment”. Therefore, Case A supports proposition P2, as significant differentiation is found here among rebranding and other marketing techniques.

5.6.2.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

In Case B, ‘Debenhams.com’ was formed to advance Boohoo’s product range beyond beauty to sports and home appliances via leveraging Debenhams’ customer base and online stores. Douglass stated in 2024 that, “The integration work consisted of incorporating Debenhams’ business into Boohoo’s tech environment, keeping Debenhams as the brand but exclusively for online selling and without any stores or staff”. This move was an effort to boost the companies’ e-commerce capabilities and expand the product range offered at Boohoo in order to get competitive advantages.

Proposition P2 suggests that brand repositioning, repackaging, refreshing are not similar to rebranding, which is also true in Case B. In 2022, Nanji stated that, “In the case of the rebranding of Debenhams, this proposition can be linked to Boohoo’s action” as this was not just a simple revamp of a store and its environment but a whole shift of the company’s approach from retail outlets to online platforms. Changes were made in both the internal and external environment as described in BBC News in 2021 to set Debenhams within the online environment. Here, both repositioning and refreshing activities are done, which facilitated the

rebranding campaign of Boohoo, but Debenhams itself could not become successful by taking these marketing initiatives without rebranding.

5.6.2.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

Case C: The Jaeger campaign of M&S, was very much planned to place Jaeger's quality, classic and British style within the retail arena of M&S through luxury fabrics and responsible sourcing. This rebranding endeavour was not merely a simple effort to make Jaeger's image look different but was a complete change in the brand character to better fit within M&S to meet consumers' expectations. Rigby stated in 2022 that, "This change created a new target market for the Marks and Spencer group to market Jaeger's attire and draw a richer class of customers who are aware of quality and sustainability".

The transformation of M&S is in line with Proposition P2, with which rebranding is defined not in terms of repositioning, repackaging, or refreshing, but as a more comprehensive exercise. This rebranding process ensured "adaptation and transformation inside M&S supply chain management" as stated by Carvill in 2023; M&S's strategy not only implied label modification but also entailed drastic shifts in both its operational vision and organisational values. The process through which Jaeger was integrated into the product line of M&S involved the formulation of product-line strategies and phased introduction of the company's products into the particular market. Therefore, the campaign of Jaeger cannot be said as repositioning or refreshing; rather, this marketing exercise needs to be referred as rebranding.

5.6.2.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

The case of the transformation of Next Directory to Next Online was done to ensure the change of business from catalogue selling method to a more flexible online selling model. The rebranding was not just a switch of the name but included major marketing initiatives aimed at mapping out an online shopping experience. These initiatives included enhancing the front-end graphic design of the website, restructuring all inventory-related processes, and reviewing all the communications to reflect as a young, modern, and technologically advanced company. Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria stated in 2020 that, "This transition was accompanied by multimillion-dollar investments in information technology and

advertising” to recast Next as a company that integrates online purchasing into the company’s operations.

The change in Next PLC responds to Proposition P2, which holds that rebranding does more than simply repositioning, repackaging, or refreshing initiatives. The transformation of the online sales proposition of Next and remodelling of Next’s e-commerce vision and strategy made this a revolutionary rebranding exercise. Though repositioning and refreshing activities are involved here, these merely expedite the rebranding process. Thus, this case study emphasises the nature of rebranding as a separate and distinctive marketing technique by changing the existing brand name, sales platform, and internal organisational structure to relocate online base.

5.6.2.6 CASE E: H&M

The case of ‘Transparency in Fashion’ of H&M was a fundamental transformation, not a mere exercise in repositioning the brand, but in the rebranding of the group in fashion and clothing retail. It was intended to focus on giving data of the origin and sustainability impact of each product, which entailed specifying the countries of production, supplier names, specific factories, and composition of each of the garments. This was done with a view to redesigning its operations to suit emerging trends among consumers, especially in the area of ethics and sustainability in business.

Whereas proposition P2 marks rebranding from some lesser perceptible efforts such as repackaging, repositioning, and refreshing, it also sets down the fact that rebranding is not a simple process. Vaught and Vaught exclaimed in 2024 that, “The mentioned strategic transformation not only changed the sphere of communication and marketing tools but also affected the supply chain management to intensify its focus on the issues of transparency and sustainability”. It is seen in the case study findings that, the rebranding of H&M appropriately proved viable, as H&M’s net sales and gross profit hiked by 2023, which is also supported in the writing of Robertson in 2024. Thus, the implementation of self-reflection on ethical values can be leveraged in the brand communication and proposition strategy of the company with appropriate rebranding technique.

5.6.3. Using Rebranding as an Atypical Strategy

P3: Rebranding is a unique process that can be classified as an atypical activity in comparison with other branding activities.

5.6.3.1 Rationale:

This proposition is based on the scheme that rebranding appears to pose a challenge to major marketing and branding theories and principles. Marketing and brand management theories and literature focus on the formulation of powerful brand equity and brand names through consistent investment over a longer period. Rebranding seems to avoid this long-time investment and goes against conventional practice. Consequently, it is hypothesised to be an unusual one.

5.6.3.2 CASE A: ZARA

Zara's latest advertising effort started in January 2022 by introducing the campaign 'Zara Redefined,' which is a departure from fast fashion to a luxury fashion brand. Zara on its official website showed in 2022 that "These changes were made because of the growing consumers' concern regarding sustainability and gaining competitive advantages. Logo Creator in 2022 stated in contrast to common rebranding approaches where the main goals are aesthetic adjustments, Zara performed a revision of the company's infrastructure, clarified the overall image and vision of the stores by "changing logos, and the layout of stores to make them look more luxurious and elegant, the introduction of more environment-friendly fabrics and production technologies in the supply chain." Mintel in the 2023 explained that "The campaign was carefully done through a range of international advertisements making use of both the print and electronic media to popularise the new brand values that included green and quality".

This unconventional approach 'immeasurably' strengthened Zara's market standing. Inditex's market capitalisation by the end of the year 2023 was about £95bn, which was a right indication of penetrating luxurious sections and improved competitiveness. Washington Post explained in 2024 that, "this change did not only re-locate Zara in the luxurious segment of the market but also placed the company in a position that would suit the changing consumer trends towards 'Green' products". There, this shift also brought considerable revenue differences, as a proven increase in the internet sales of Zara by 16% in 2023.

5.6.3.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

The rebranding operation that Boohoo prepared with Debenhams in January 2021 was atypical because it turned a traditional department store into an online store only. Nanji presented in 2022 that, "this move extended beyond routine branding management by not just

merely purchasing a brand with high brand equity, but more importantly abandoning its offline, physical infrastructure and refashioning it in Boohoo's image". Fashion United showed in 2021 that, the key strategy was to utilise Debenhams' well-established brand equity and large customer base to offer new beauty, sport, and home forms exclusively through the online platforms.

Boohoo Group PLC's annual report and accounts displayed in 2023 that, "this complete change was done under the corporate name and brand restructuring programme with no visible link to physical retail stores, thus cutting down many overheads and catering to an increasing e-consumer market". BBC News showed in 2021 that, "the rebranding process gave Debenhams a much-needed new look, while at the same time protecting its brand image". From the case study findings, it is revealed that this approach also aimed to take advantage of the customer base that Debenhams had built. Douglass, stated in 2024 that, "this change of operations to an all-digitised format was in a broader 'Agenda for Change' campaign" to tackle past drawbacks identified about labour issues putting Boohoo in a competitive position in the growing online fashion market industry.

5.6.3.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

M&S began restructuring the company's marketing strategy in January 2021 with the purchase of the Jaeger brand for £6 million. Rigby stated in 2023 that "this rebranding campaign was special or distinctively christened". The process began in October 2021 and concerned the use of premium fabrics and a more traditional English aesthetic. In 2023, Spanou presented that, "the rebranding campaign of Jaeger included displaying Jaeger products in M&S branded stores, right from beta-testing in selected flagship outlets, thereby allowing M&S to target the higher-end consumer market".

The logic of M&S's acquisition of Jaeger under its brand strategy had been targeted at the proprietary use of Jaeger as a brand that has classy appearances to polarise M&S in the niche of the higher-end fashion market. The success of the rebranding campaign was evident with the improvement in the general awareness of the brand and also the increase in the market capitalisation of M&S.

5.6.3.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

The change in the name was done in early 2018, from Next Directory to Next Online to assert the company's attempt to shift from catalogue sales to a strong online business. This specific

rebranding initiative included internal adjustments like the use of modern e-commerce technologies for product inventory and new UI design, targeting the online customers only and projecting a more technology-oriented company. Marques, da Silva, Davcik, and Faria stated in 2020 that, “this was a strategic shift imperative for Next’s survival in the face of drastic changes in the retail business environment in the UK retail sector”.

Rebranding not only placed Next into a new value system in the online marketplace but also influenced the company’s financial and market business outcomes. Similarly, in 2023, Business Chief explained that “the transition towards online helped Next PLC capture the growing trend of online shopping more effectively, increase the scope of its customers’ base, and improve the efficiency of its operations”. Therefore, Next PLC could effectively compete against competitors, including both traditional retail outlets and the newer breed of pure-play internet-based rivals through this unique rebranding campaign. Thus, Next PLC sustained growth and profitability in the highly competitive environment in the fashion and clothing retail sector.

5.6.3.6 CASE E: H&M

H&M embarked on its ‘Transparency in Fashion’ campaign in 2019 and vowed to make its operations more environment-friendly. In the same year, Rogers explained that, “this campaign put H&M in a position to lead the high-street retail industry being the first to ensure transparency at the sourcing level. H&M released on its website in 2019 that, “making the tag and online description of each item added credibility among the consumers and made the brand more focused on sustainability and ethical standards”.

Robertson presented in 2024 that, “this new campaign created a highly positive shift in H&M’s market situation”. On a year-end basis by 2023, H&M increased its net sales by 6%, reaching £20.39 billion and its gross profit by 7%, to £10.43 billion. These figures demonstrated the improvement of the company’s efficiency in operations and successful implementation of sustainable development at a lower cost at H&M. Specifically, the transparent initiative put H&M as a leader in the industry of sustainable fashion. In this topic, Wren explored in 2022 that, “such strategic repositioning helped H&M further strengthen its competitive advantages”. Therefore, this rebranding technique of H&M was unique compared to other marketing and branding activities.

5.6.4. Different Types of Rebranding

P4: There are three kinds of rebranding often noticed; corporate, business unit, and product rebranding.

5.6.4.1 Rationale:

Three categories of rebranding were available in the literature study; product, business unit, and corporate-level rebranding. This proposition aims to know whether this classification is valid in light of the five companies analysed for this research.

5.6.4.2 CASE A: ZARA

Case A was about Zara redefined, which sought to reposition the brand from fast fashion to luxury and sustainability in 2022. Zara's website showed this change of course was because of increasing consumers' consciousness about the environment and ethical issues in the manufacturing process of apparel, which led Zara to align itself with the new philosophy of consumption that focuses on quality and environmental factors. Singh in 2024 stated that "such a rebranding was necessary to spread the new orientation and corporate objectives of the brand in its organisational structure".

In 2023, Bhute explained that "Zara did not go for product or business unit rebranding because the two strategies would not have worked in achieving the total change of direction as needed". Therefore, Nickels and Hugh stated in 2024 that, Zara made sure that the new brand message was disseminated and communicated to the consumers with the message of luxury and sustainability through corporate rebranding, which supports proposition P4 of this research. Washington Post explained in 2024 that, "this integrated strategy led to the growth of market capitalisation to about £95 billion by early 2024". The campaign helped to strengthen the position of Zara in the sphere of luxury products and sustainable fashion.

5.6.4.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo Group PLC annual report and accounts in 2023 stated that "Boohoo Group PLC 2021 began a strategic rebranding at the corporate level when it purchased Debenhams to convert the company into 'Debenhams.com' an online retailer only". This strategy means leveraging a familiar brand such as Debenhams and diversifying the company into new segments such as beauty, sportswear, and homeware. Fashion United on its website exclaimed in 2021 that, "it was more appropriate for Boohoo to embrace a corporate

rebranding plan that would enable Debenhams to fit well into the Boohoo e-commerce architecture, giving the customers a homogenous brand across the supply chain”.

As per proposition P4, Nanji presented in 2022 that, “rebranding was well coordinated through stakeholder management as well as through well-coordinated marketing strategies”. Another strategy that formed part of the rebranding process was the ‘Agenda for Change’, whose measures aimed at improving the governance and sustainability profiles in the course of the integration process. Douglass stated in 2024 that this corporate rebranding campaign expanded Boohoo’s client base and strengthened its competitive position in the online retail marketplace.

5.6.4.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

January 2021 saw Marks & Spencer’s (M&S) engagement in business unit rebranding through acquiring and subsequently absorbing the Jaeger brand. This move was rationalised to stimulate Jaeger’s classic brand value of fabric quality and sustainability by integrating it with the contemporary retail setting of M&S. Choosing business unit rebranding instead of corporate or individual product rebranding was to keep the spirit of Jaeger fresh while it stayed a part of the group’s brand because too much generalisation from core identity sometimes increases chances of dilution.

Supporting proposition P4 of this research, this business unit rebranding campaign was done systematically with disjointed efforts comprising strategic planning, design changes, proper marketing campaigns, and a step-by-step alteration to main M&S outlets. Jaeger products were incorporated into M&S’s flagship stores so that the company could receive feedback on consumer choices and adjust them to make the integration successful. Besides improving M&S’s brand offering, this strategy also helped in improving the market standing of the company by attracting more value-conscious customers.

5.6.4.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Jones explained in 2023 that, “Next PLC began a massive corporate-level rebranding in the early part of 2018 when it changed its “Next Directory” to “Next Online” to show an altered focus from the traditional catalogue selling methods to modern online selling methods. Next’s business model capitalised on a shift to online consumer purchases and thereby improved the link between the online and physical sales platforms. Business Chief website explained in 2023 that, “choosing the corporate level rebranding enabled Next to establish a

clear image and a coherent brand message across all the aspects of the company's activity which was critical in firming up the company's position in the highly competitive clothing retail sector.

The change was launched to enhance the online customer interface and supply chain systems. This included a massive internal reorganisation, a dramatic move in brand image change of the company, the initiation of the new logo, and other extensive brand promotional strategies. All these initiatives supported the research proposition P4 following corporate rebranding to make Next PLS a progressive retailer. Thus, its market share and investors' confidence significantly increased as proof of the transition to be an online-based product category.

5.6.4.6 CASE E: H&M

In the year 2019, H&M went public with its new campaign 'Transparency in Fashion' at the corporate level. MacCarthy, Ahmed, and Demirel demonstrated in 2022 that, "this rebranding campaign was prompted by an increasing awareness of environmental effects connected with clothing manufacturing and product origin". It raised the bar in the fast-fashion chain by sharing material sources, production country, supplier name, factory information on the garment tags and website descriptions. This was a strategic decision under a general shift towards ethical consumption and to help H&M continue to present itself as a pioneer in sustainable fashion.

Rogers explained in 2019 that, "the rebranding campaign had several corporate aspects and the company went through many internal and external transformations", there, suggesting corporate-level rebranding as per the research proposition P4. It entailed a complete revision of tools for communicating the new brand, with all the marketing activities being linked to H&M for ethical fashion. Vogue Business on its website in 2024 revealed that "the effectiveness of the current campaign can, therefore, be measured by the company's performance". Thus, H&M received even more competitive advantages in the market to address the mass audience for whom the concept of 'sustainability' has become a common concern.

5.6.5. Motivations for Rebranding

P5: The necessity of rebranding originates from one or several of the following stimuli: mergers and acquisitions, standardisation, brand image, simplification, repositioning and retargeting, diversification, and legal prerequisites.

5.6.5.1 Rationale:

The literature review chapter discussed various motivations that prompt organisations to undertake rebranding programmes. Proposition P5 will classify the motivational forces that triggered the rebranding campaigns. The analysis of this proposition P5 produced seven categories; merger and acquisitions, standardisation, brand image or brand identity, simplification, repositioning and retargeting, diversification and finally legal prerequisites. This proposition is designed to establish whether the rebranding campaigns in the five selected brands serve these major driving forces or not.

5.6.5.2 CASE A: ZARA

Mintel explained in 2023 that “Zara redefined was launched in 2022 to tap into a new market segment with customers’ increasing concern of environmental and ethical consciousness for the fashion industry”. Washington Post, on its website, explained in 2024 that, “this corporate-level repositioning was very important not only to set a new identity for Zara in the competitive marketplace but also to adapt to the new global consumer trend towards sustainability. Zara could redesign itself into a more luxurious and environmentally friendly image that targets an even bigger chunk of the population that is made up of those individuals who love fashion and the environment at the same time.

The campaign entailed a general rebranding of Zara, right from its logo, the interior designs of its stores, and the adoption of sustainability strategies across most of its processes. Nickels, and Hugh presented in 2024 that, “Zara made total sense to work this way as all the operations of Zara had to mirror the new brand values”. Beaumont showed in 2022 that, “the current repositioning not only helped Zara to fortify its position on the market but also improved its position as the sustainable fashion pioneer against the background of the competition and in modern consumers’ values”. Thus, the rebranding campaign supported proposition P5, where brand image, repositioning, retargeting, and diversification are the key driving forces for this rebranding campaign of Zara.

5.6.5.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo Group PLC's annual report and accounts displayed in 2023 that, “the major reason for the transformation of Debenhams into ‘Debenhams.com’ was to break into new categories such as beauty, sport, and homeware, leveraging on the established identity and the high online consumer base of Debenhams”. On the website of Fashion United, it is mentioned in

2021 that, “this strategic move was primarily directed by the need to expand the company’s portfolio of stocks and make use of the customer base that Debenhams possessed which Boohoo had not been so effective in reaching”. In addition, Douglass exclaimed in 2024 that, this rebranding campaign sought to improve the position of Boohoo in the sphere of e-shops by adopting a famous retail brand into the company’s portfolio.

Supporting proposition P5, McKinnon explained in 2022 that, “this rebranding exercise was done to integrate the Debenhams’ online operations and brand image to fit with Boohoo”. Moreover, BBC News stated in 2021 that, “Boohoo concentrated on developing online consumer relations and extending product portfolios associated with the Debenhams retail brand to ensure repositioning and diversification. Therefore, this expansion strategy had a significant impact on diversifying Boohoo’s customer base, which consolidated its market position to counter other giants in e-commerce. Thus, Boohoo tried to offset earlier concerns about its labour relations policies through this rebranding program.

5.6.5.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

The key rationale for the M&S acquisition and repositioning of the Jaeger brand was product portfolio extension and the aspiration to target a high-end consumer demographic. Launched in January 2021, the acquisition was aligned with expanding the company’s portfolio in the luxury fashion segment while maintaining Jaeger’s brand image. This was as part of M&S’s agreed plan on the line of brand transformation, enhancement of its market share, and customer perception of quality, ethnicity, and sustainability.

The procedure to bring Jaeger back to the fashion forefront was called “Jaeger Relunched” and it was coordinated down to the last detail to make sure that Jaeger fits like a well-tailored suit into the M&S environment. Marks & Spencer expressed in 2023 that, “this integration entailed alterations of the product designs to reflect the modern fashion trends and retained Jaeger’s conventional appeal of quality and ethnicity. Jaeger clothing ensures the quality materials in clothing like silk, wool, and cashmere to maintain elegance in the brand. Advertising and Branding Timeline website stated on its website in 2023 that, “this strategy assisted M&S in gaining enhanced market exposure while enhancing its business results”. Therefore, it can be said that this rebranding of M&S focused on the acquisition, repositioning, brand image, and diversification, thus supporting the proposition P5.

5.6.5.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

The change of the name of the Next PLC to Next Directory to Next Online at the beginning of 2018 was prompted by the tendency to migrate to online platforms. This adjustment was done with the view to improving the efficiency of its operation in the e-commerce marketplace and taking advantage of the increasing consumers' shift into the online market. The rebranding campaign slogan was Next Online Evolution and entailed major structural transformations at the corporate level, both internal and external.

Considering proposition P5, the statement of Jones in 2023 can be explained here that, "the implementation of this campaign was necessary for Next to establish a brand image, repositioning, retargeting, and diversification. Through this campaign, Next PLC could adapt to the online market and hence improve its market position and investor confidence.

5.6.5.6 CASE E: H&M

H&M's 2019 "Transparency in Fashion" initiative was predicated mainly on the trends in which consumers are demanding detailed information about the sustainability of the manufacturing process of the products. This rebranding of H&M was not only a fallow to market forces but also to become a market leader sustainably. In response, H&M initiated to give specific information on the tags of the products. Moreover, to create an ethical brand image and reposition itself in sustainable clothing, H&M started disclosing the descriptions of the products on the internet about the origins of the materials used.

Many internal adjustments of the company had occurred to ensure that H&M redistributed its functioning processes following the newly proclaimed goals of transparency; tracing systems, as well as an upgraded data supply. This campaign helped H&M to reconstruct and remodel its brand image. Thus, H&M secured its market presence, raised sales, and optimised the organisation's performance towards its commitments to transparency and sustainability.

5.6.6. Rebranding Campaign Strategies

P6: There are six rebranding campaign strategies, such as; Phase-in/phase-out, combined rebranding under one umbrella brand, translucent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding strategies.

5.6.6.1 Rationale:

In the literature review chapter, it is discussed that organisations can take different approaches while undertaking rebranding exercises. All these strategies depend on how the rebranding campaign is initialised and implemented. The utilisation of the rebranding strategy does therefore depend on the branding requirements and goals of the firm. This proposition aims to identify the type of rebranding campaign approach adopted by each of the five brands in this study.

5.6.6.2 CASE A: ZARA

The rebranding campaign known as “Zara Redefined” that started in January 2022 made use of a “Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand.” This approach was used to ensure that the change of the brand image is centralised worldwide under one brand philosophy of luxury and sustainability. Singh exclaimed in 2024 that, “this strategy helped Zara to transition from a value-conscious positioning to more eco-conscious and premium consumers”. The changes were on the micro level with changes to the logo, layout of stores, and most importantly the consensus of sustainable factors through the supply chain.

Blonder presented in 2024 that, “Zara formatted these changes to be global and implanted the company’s brand image to consumers”. This campaign strategy was deemed to be most appropriate because the organisation desired an immediate change in the brand. Washington Post explained in 2024 that, “An abrupt transition was likely to have led to customers to stay connected with the brand”. This campaign helped Zara to reposition itself in the luxury segment, thus establishing Zara as a sustainable fashion clothing brand to meet buyer’s requirements.

5.6.6.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

The ‘Debenhams.com’, a strategy by Boohoo in January 2021, implied a ‘Combined Rebranding Strategy under One Umbrella Brand’. Stobbs stated in 2021 that, “the rebranding campaign of Boohoo involved integrating Debenhams under the Boohoo conglomerate while leaving it with the Debenhams name tag for its identified brand equity, but running it online only. Drapers in 2023 explained that “it enabled Boohoo to tap into newer segments that include beauty, sports, and homeware and reach out to newer customers directly without incurring the expense and overhead of owning high street stores”.

McKinnon explained in 2022 that, “the decision to keep the brand Debenhams as it was successful because of the existing brand image and customer loyalty of Debenhams”. Boohoo oversaw the rebranding process would be effective and paid respect to the Debenhams brand. Thus, following the rebranding campaign under one umbrella brand was effective for Boohoo to get competitive advantages in the fast fashion online retail market of the UK.

5.6.6.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

M&S applied a Combined Rebranding Strategy using One Umbrella Brand in one of its acquisitions, namely Jaeger. M&S ensured to keep Jaeger’s brand image separate from M&S in its high street retail stores. By doing so, M&S was able to capitalise on Jaeger’s premium positioning that aligned the merchandise with high-quality, traditional British clothing that could be placed around M&S stores to target a higher class of consumers. Retail Gazette explored in 2021 that the rebranding was officially launched with the campaign ‘Jaeger Relaunched’ in October 2021, emphasising fabric quality and exclusive styles which were consistent with Jaeger’s historical background.

The use of this rebranding strategy meant to cash on with the already established brand equity of Jaeger without affecting its already set consumer base. Jaeger’s product lines were therefore displayed in M&S stores, which allowed the company to broaden its assortment with minimum risks and costs since it did not have to create a new brand from scratch. Thus, this strategy can be regarded as a successful one for M&S to get competitive advantages in the UK clothing retail market.

5.6.6.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand was used by Next PLC in early 2018 when it changed its brand name from “Next Directory” to “Next Online”. This approach implied the change of the brand image to correspond to the new omnichannel distribution strategy of the company to focus on online presence following the change in consumer buying behaviour towards online platforms. The changing of the brand name was aimed at helping Next PLC improve online adaptation and online shopping experience and enhancing the connection between its online and high street stores.

To ensure a combined rebranding strategy under one umbrella brand, Next PLC just changed the 2nd phase of the name, but did not do anything of the main brand name ‘Next’. Jones explained in 2023 that, “the rebranding campaign of Next PLC attempted to adapt to the

enhanced demand for shopping online among the consumers”. Therefore, the campaign was implemented on the right track at the right time to be a pioneer in the online clothing retail market in the UK.

5.6.6.6 CASE E: H&M

To change the company and align it under one brand without losing the brand image, the campaign “Transparency in Fashion,” which H&M started in early 2019, used “Combined Rebranding Strategy via the One Umbrella Brand.” It was about disclosing information on specific products, specifically, on the materials used in production and supply chains, enhancing tags and online descriptions, which aimed at changing the principles of high-street retail transparency in line with newly emerged consumer expectations of ethical behaviour.

Esri explored in 2019 that, “a decision to use this form of rebranding instead of adopting other forms was deliberately made to allow a gradual shift in strategy to promote greater sustainability at H&M”. This approach reduced the possibility of shifting strategies that would cost the organisation the existing client base. Robertson stated in 2024 that, “this rebranding did not only assist in keeping abreast of its old clients but also in attracting new clients who are more conscious about the environment”. This rebranding strategy of H&M strengthened its position in the market as the pioneer of sustainable fashion and also improved consumer perception and loyalty in the competitive clothing retail market in the UK.

5.6.7. The Process of Rebranding

P7: Rebranding is an ongoing process and follows a systematic manner, such as; renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching.

5.6.7.1 Rationale:

In the case of rebranding, there are different processes, which were described in the previous literature review chapter. The objective of this proposition is to identify the steps in rebranding in each of the five case studies. All these stages have been explained in each of the case study reports; hence, in this section, they will simply be summarised and supported by illustrations. In the next chapter, these processes will be compared with those mentioned in the literature review chapter.

5.6.7.2 CASE A: ZARA

The 'Zara Redefined' campaign was performed by Zara from January to June 2022 following a five-step approach of rebranding. Washington Post in 2024 explained that, "this rebranding was commenced given the shift in consumer consciousness regarding the effects on the environment and sustainability, while the notion of luxury from the fast fashion competitors was also targeted". On the Logo Creator website, it is stated in 2022 that, "the process of establishing sustainable values embraced strategic alliance with other stakeholders and alteration of the production and supply system". Worldwide advertisement for these new brand values and phase-by-phase market introduction was done to refine the strategies according to the responses received from consumers.

Implementation of this strategy required many internal changes in the company, including the redesign of stores and the re-conception of the online sales platform for serving the luxury target market. Mintel explained in 2023 that, "this change helped Zara get a new competitive level in the luxury segment, expand market share, and enhance the share for online sales". Through redesigning and repositioning, this rebranding strategy, thus, made it possible to turn Zara into an even more prominent force in the high street as well as online markets.

5.6.7.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo Group PLC began a major rebranding process and called the site, Debenhams.com, after purchasing the Debenhams brand in January 2021. Fashion United explained in 2021 that, "this deal was specifically targeted to redirect Debenhams to become an e-commerce company under the Boohoo Group to concentrate on beauty, sport, and homeware". Drapers Online stated in 2021 that, "this rebranding process, executed over six months, comprised five phases: strategic leadership and management of stakeholders, product marketing and supply chain, heavy promotion and publicity, entering the market and targeting it, and ongoing evaluation and enhancement".

Through redesigning the sales platform of Debenhams brand, Boohoo also confirmed its repositioning by emphasising online sales. BBC News showed in 2021 that, "the rebranding not only expanded the target customer group for Boohoo, but also incorporated hi-tech solutions for improving customers' engagement and the organisation's performance". Douglass explained in 2024 that, "Boohoo remained competitive in the online retail market

by following practical application of rebranding”. Thus, Boohoo received extensive advantages from the existing customer base of Debenhams.

5.6.7.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

Marks & Spencer acquired the Jaeger brand in January 2021 and launched the ‘Jaeger Relaunched’ campaign in October 2021. This campaign sought to integrate ‘classic’ luxury with Jaeger’s heritage values into M&S’s new retail environment of quality clothing that is affordable yet made from premium material and produced sustainably. The Advertising and Branding Timeline stated in 2023 on its website that, “the rebranding of M&S, namely Jaeger Relaunched, involved five key stages, such as strategic planning, stakeholder identification and management, product development and design, advertising and branding, and evaluation and adaptation.

The rebranding carried out the objectives of integrating Jaeger into the M&S family and improving the position of both brands. M&S progressively introduced Jaeger products in the new concept stores such as Bluewater and Marble Arch to be able to learn consumers’ perceptions towards Jaeger products and adjust to their modern demands for quality and sustainability. This approach provoked the consumers to remain loyal to the company’s brand image and positioned it as a premium brand serving a modern ‘green’ consumer market through redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching.

5.6.7.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Next PLC, a UK-based retail chain company, with an already established direct catalogue business Next Directory, launched a rebranding exercise in early 2018 referred to as Next Online Evolution. This strategic move is meant to help it align its e-commerce structure with the new reality that has been precipitated by the move towards online purchases by consumers. Lim wrote in 2022 that, “the rebranding of Next Online was meticulously executed in three phases namely strategic planning and integration, technology upgrade and system optimisation, and lastly marketing and brand communication”.

This vast plan was put into practice with a focus on the new online brand image of Next. Through relaunching, Next PLC developed an Omni channel retailing strategy, as seen by the integration of online and high street store sales. It proved to be effective for Next in terms of strengthening the company’s position in the competitive retail environment and also

developing a marketplace to grow in the emerging and dynamic online clothing retail environment.

5.6.7.6 CASE E: H&M

The campaign ‘Transparency in Fashion’, started in early 2019 by H&M, demonstrated that sustainability and ethical policies with suppliers and manufacturers become an even more significant part of the H&M brand. Esri explored in 2019 that, “this strategic rebranding was a result of the rising consumer awareness of transparent and sustainable fashion practices”. The campaign was meticulously structured into three phases over the year: identification and analysis of strategies and management of stakeholders, technological infrastructure development related to supply chain transparency, and comprehensive marketing and brand communication that focused on the sustainable development of H&M. This rebranding helped H&M set standards of sustainable fashion, making them a pioneer of the UK clothing retail sector.

According to H&M’s sustainability goals, by the end of 2023, the Company aimed at sourcing its production to be 100% from recycled or sustainably sourced cotton. By the end of 2023, the Company achieved 97% to be used for the same. Therefore, it can be said that, through the implementation of redesigning its supply chain, information disclosure policy to the consumers, and repositioning the brand in the minds of the sustainability-conscious consumers, this rebranding campaign fulfilled proposition P7 of this research.

5.6.8. Rebranding of Names

P8: Rebranding is a form of strategy that suggests the selection of a new brand name.

5.6.8.1 Rationale:

In the literature review chapter, the literature argued that rebranding requires a name change, which must encompass choosing a brand name. Therefore, this proposition aims to understand whether a new brand name was selected in each of the five case studies and the intention of the selection.

5.6.8.2 CASE A: ZARA

During the 2022 “Zara Redefined” rebranding program, Zara did not change the brand name despite making important strategic shifts toward luxury and sustainability. Blonder, in 2024,

stated that “the decision to keep the brand name for Zara was proved to be more deliberate.” Mintel explained in 2024 that, “it eliminated the problems which were associated with the rebranding process”. The strategy of holding the original name served to retain credibility and consistency for consumers and investors conversant with the existing position and services of Zara.

To implement such a decision, Zara improved its logo and store designs and intensified its online media to be in line with luxury and sustainability. Beaumont stated in 2022 that “the involvement of the key stakeholders in the company was very influential in ensuring that these strategies were aligned at all levels of the firm”. The change of the brand’s positioning instead of the brand name was also effective in prompting internal and external marketing campaigns to demonstrate the new brand orientation.

5.6.8.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo Group PLC tactically renamed the Debenhams brand in 2021 and changed it into Debenhams.com, being an online-only retailer. Licensing Source website explained in 2021 that “Boohoo spared the Debenhams brand name and used it to reach a larger audience and customer base of Debenhams to introduce new product niches such as beauty, sport, and homeware under the umbrella of Boohoo. Boohoo Group PLC’s annual report and accounts exclaimed in 2023 that “the decision to retain the Debenhams’ name over having Boohoo was critical to retain Debenhams’ customer base in the market through online platforms”.

The whole rebranding was aimed at aligning Debenhams with Boohoo’s online services while preserving its separate brand image. This strategy entailed vigorous promotion and other awareness campaigns, brand messaging, and embracing all aspects of online sales. Thus, instead of changing the brand name, Boohoo exploited Debenhams’ brand name and brand image to increase market reach in the competitive online retail market in the UK.

5.6.8.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

One of the most important strategic rebranding decisions made by M&S was the acquisition and ownership of the Jaeger brand, which made them retain the Jaeger name but integrate it into the M&S brand framework. Marks & Spencer showed in 2022 that “this decision was based on the idea to capitalise on the respected image of Jaeger as the manufacturer of high-end clothing and the provider of the classical British style, which increased the target audience base among the clients with higher purchasing power”. The retention of the Jaeger

name allowed M&S to leverage an already-discovered market audience and its traditionalism, which was important for maintaining Jaeger's customer base.

The rebranding mission was called Jaeger Relunched, it began in October 2021 and underwent certain steps to combine the traditional style of Jaeger with the modern store experience of M&S. No change in brand names of either M&S or Jaeger was found in this rebranding campaign, as the objective of the campaign was to ensure that Jaeger's products fit into the M&S stores thus making the brand easily noticed and available to the public. The advertising and branding timeline stated in 2023 that "M&S managed to avoid the majority of the negatives usually associated with rebranding such as abandonment by customers or watered-down brand image by ensuring that while the brand change was occurring, the Jaeger name was retained". This allowed M&S to maintain Jaeger's brand, make M&S more relevant in the luxury segment, and gain a drastic improvement in its market capitalisation by early 2024.

5.6.8.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Next PLC changed the name "Next Directory" to "Next Online" in early 2018. Business Live in 2021 explained that "this was not a mere change but a critical one to position the brand correctly amidst the new dynamics of online shopping and improve the online image". This strategic shift to 'Next Online,' as the brand name for the online division, was inevitable in light of the challenges that the firm faced. So, Next PLC decided to operate seamlessly and effectively in an increasingly internet-led retail landscape. Design Mantic explored in 2018 that "the rebranding process was holistic and encompassed strategic mapping, structural integration, technological enhancements, and heavily emphasised the aspects related to marketing and branding." This change was a strategic move to cope with the increasing demand for online shopping among the consumers in the UK.

The benefits of this strategic action can be considered impressive, which increased investors' confidence and market acceptance not only through changing the brand name but also with the above-mentioned initiatives. While preserving the central concept of branding, Next PLC could defend its leadership position with numerous changes to its organisational model, which proved that rebranding can be useful in terms of developing new potential and reconstructing the company's online presence.

5.6.8.6 CASE E: H&M

The ‘‘Transparency in Fashion’’ strategy that H&M had in 2019 advertised sustainability in the fashion industry. Retail Dive showed in 2019 that ‘‘this campaign did not pertain to the re-naming of the company’s brand; rather, it took steps in building up the brand equity by providing complete information about production and the materials used in their products among the consumers.’’ This was achievable through customer awareness of sustainability, which H&M used to market its brand as the leader in sustainable clothing and fashion retail. The decision to retain the name while significantly changing the core concept was a wise move because it preserved the key attribute of brand identity and pulled the plug on the firm’s environmental image.

Opposing proposition P8, H&M decided to include the supply chain information in product labels and descriptions on the product labels and the internet, which changed its brand name. Robertson stated in 2024 that ‘‘this approach helped to enhance consumers’ trust and their repeated shopping at H&M.’’ Therefore, by continuing the practice of keeping a unifying brand identity, the company managed to introduce changes that made H&M a leader in sustainability, thus meeting the customers’ expectations regarding ethical responsibility and sustainability.

5.6.9. Rebranding Concerned Costs and Risks

P9: Rebranding is perceived by firms as a costly and risky strategy.

5.6.9.1 Rationale:

In the literature review chapter, the authors and researchers argued that rebranding is a risky and expensive activity. These include the risk of losing company goodwill, employees, consumers’ trust, and a change in market share, which often calls for a disruption of organisational business processes if changes are not handled properly. Some preparation work will have to be done to secure the acceptance of the new name. This proposition was developed in order to identify the risks or costs of a rebranding campaign when analysed within the context of five companies sampled for the study.

5.6.9.2 CASE A: ZARA

The ‘Zara Redefined’ Campaign in 2022 was a very expensive and high-risk strategic initiative in which Zara attempted major rebranding for a transition from the fast fashion

brand strategy to the branding approach of the luxury sector. Nickels and Hugh presented in 2024 that, “it was not only the change in the visual appearance but a shift in the organisation’s approach at every level, such as using sustainable processes and increasing the brand’s luxury value proposition.” Wider promotional campaigns about this rebranding ranged from £200 million to £300 million. Logo Creator explained in 2022 that, “these costs were not limited to logo changes but include a change in all aspects of the high street stores and online platforms.”

That is why, bearing in mind the high costs and the risks, Zara’s management chose to adhere to dramatic transformations. Zara.com showed in 2022 that, “this decision was made to make Zara unique in a market filled with similar competitors and to follow the existing trend of sustainable and luxurious products.” Bhute explained in 2023 that, “this proved to be a winning strategy because of the achieved market within the luxury segment.” This strategic change, though it was costly, strengthened Zara’s position in implementing sustainability within the luxury fashion segment.

5.6.9.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo acquired the Debenhams brand and rebranded it as “Debenhams.com” in 2021. It is considered as a major but expensive and highly risky strategic change that sought to convert the physical store model to an online-only firm. Fashion United, in 2021, showed the largest cost of this campaign was assumed in the organisation of Debenhams product offerings into the existing Boohoo online network. This was useful in reducing operational interruptions and was in sync with the Boohoo Company, which operated solely on the online platform. Licensing Source explained in 2021 that, “the two major issues were associated with the management of the reputation risks referring to past labour incidents and the second risk was about the dissolving of the Boohoo brand after the integration with the partner”.

McKinnon explained in 2022 that, “despite these challenges, Boohoo did not reduce its exposure, probably because entering into Debenhams’ customer base was strategic and it also opened up an opportunity to offer new product lines such as beauty, sports, and homeware”. BBC News showed in 2021 that, “to avoid costly future risks, Boohoo launched the “Agenda for Change” programme with assistance from KPMG”. It was conceived to improve corporate management and guarantee that sustainable supply chain operations would be promoted to prevent further incidences of reputational loss and to optimise the cost-effectiveness of this rebranding.

5.6.9.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

The strategic investment by M&S in the acquisition of the Jaeger brand and subsequent rebranding in January 2021 was quite large and involved a relatively large risk due to the expense involved and the problems of brand depreciation. Marks & Spencer showed in 2022 that the campaign, “Jaeger Relaunched”, entailed £6m in an attempt to fit Jaeger’s high-quality and traditional British formal wear into the attractive and more up-to-date M&S marketplace.

Some of the major expenses contained in the rebranding were the costs of redesigning product portfolios, marketing, and the launch of these products in M&S outlets. The risks were mainly focused on preserving the luxury and elite status of the Jaeger brand while positioning the brand under M&S. Nevertheless, M&S did not relinquish from this daring process. There were also challenges in product refinement and choice of the right store locations, as well as regional marketing tests to understand consumer sentiments.

5.6.9.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Next PLC shifted from using the name “Next Directory” to “Next Online” as a way of transitioning to improve their e-business, particularly in response to the shift towards online business. Chapman described in 2023 that, “the process of this rebranding, especially initiated in early 2018, was expensive because of the need for investments in e-commerce technology, systems integration, and promotion of the new direction of the brand. Considering the overall capital investment and potential to lose a client base that had always associated the company with a catalogue in hand, this initiative was seen as crucial given the changing world of retail business.

The threats included the disruption of the business model of the company and the risk that it might lose the catalogue customers. However, this investment in the online infrastructure and customer experience was greatly worthwhile, indicating high levels of market acceptance and investment confidence. The successful rebranding overcame not only initial risks but also highlighted Next as a progressive retail company capitalising on online trends to sustain profitability.

5.6.9.6 CASE E: H&M

The rebranding ‘‘Transparency in Fashion’’, which H&M started in 2019, was perhaps one of its most expensive and a planned strategic move aimed at improving sustainability and ethical conduct in business. Retail Dive stated in 2019 that ‘‘this rebranding was done by H&M to respond to consumers’ increasing needs and expectations of ethical and sustainable fashion’’. The campaign was a risky attempt since changing the supply chain communication with the customers to embrace a fuller disclosure of the supply chain information was a major investment in new hardware and software for tracking production information.

Some of the key expenses incurred by this campaign were the creation of new labelling regimes, the implementation of new tracking solutions, and substantial branding to publicise the new green agenda. These were associated with risks such as the threat of supply disruption and the problem of managing suppliers’ compliance with new levels of visibility. In 2024, Robertson announced that ‘‘the company had effectively executed the rebranding direction’’, which was well-received in the international market.

5.6.10. Overcoming Rebranding-Related Risks and Cost Factors

P10: Rebranding cost and risks of name changing can be overcome by, first assessing the need for rebranding and the name change, and following extensive research on overall market situations, as well as a well-planned mass communication strategy for all stakeholders of the name change.

5.6.10.1 Rationale:

From the literature review chapter, the risks involved in rebranding were pointed out. However, methods of mitigating risk and cost were also described. The first was for the identification of the need for rebranding, while the second was for recommending plans and strategies. Thus, the purpose of this proposition is to identify how five companies dealt with risk and mitigated cost to find out if this is done by first identifying the need for rebranding and then coming up with elaborate plans and communication strategies.

5.6.10.2 CASE A: ZARA

Zara’s marketing campaign ‘‘Zara Redefined’’, which was launched in January 2022, risks and costs connected with the campaign were also sufficiently controlled. Beaumont showed in 2022 that, ‘‘the biggest threat of the campaign was to attract the existing consumers of new

clothes who had grown familiar with the quick fashion cycles of stores besides the high costs of changing the store façade, redesigning its logo, and integrating supply chains.” Logo Creator explained in 2022 that “Zara controlled these risks in how this change involved a slow shift of the new luxury image while staying connected to the fast-fashion image which still captured its previous audiences”.

Zara also prevented general contingency risks and most of the costs, since the brand intended a phased marketing strategy, which enabled the brand to establish a trial-and-error process on the different market reactions to the strategy. Mintel explained in 2023 that, “financial risks were minimised this way because the change did not have the potential to cause serious losses.” The emphasis on the e-commerce development minimised expenses by avoiding the use of high street shops. Thus, Zara gained competitive advantages in the luxury fashion segment and expanded its market share in the UK.

5.6.10.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo’s acquisition and subsequent rebranding of Debenhams as ‘Debenhams.com’ was precisely strategic to emphasise an online-only retail platform. McKinnon explained in 2022 that “this rebranding was important since Boohoo could utilise the reputation and customer base of Debenhams without facing the expense of owning high street stores.” The campaign managed to decentralise risks as adjusted towards the online integration agenda, which correlates with the shift in buying behaviour towards online shopping, especially because of the COVID-19 crisis. Fashion United stated in 2021 that “the rebranding was done very systematically that ensured that the organisation did not incur many costs since it did not take physical assets employees.”

Nanji stated in 2022 that, to balance the risks and costs, Boohoo adopted a restructuring/rebranding model, which was specific to the assimilation of Debenhams’ products into Boohoo’s online production line. Thus, Boohoo boosted Debenhams’ brand equity under the new umbrella and reduced the company’s need for a broader high-street store base at a significant cost. Drapers Online in 2023 explained that “the focus on the e-commerce sphere eliminated the risks and increased competitiveness without increasing expenses on the physical presence of high street stores.”

5.6.10.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

This initiative dubbed “Jaeger Relaunched” was not only about integrating Jaeger into M&S but also about reviving it into something, which was more representative of new-age customer’s taste, better quality, sustainability, and British style. Finding ways to lessen risk included a gradual introduction of the product in the market and consulting key consumers to avoid any bad impact on the brand image of both brands. The given strategy allowed M&S to avoid losses incurred when altering an established brand’s image.

With the chosen strategy of the “Combined Rebranding strategy implemented by using One Umbrella Brand,” Jaeger could retain its individuality, at the same time leveraging on M&S’s strong distribution and marketing channels. In 2023, the advertising and branding timeline stated that “the costs of this rebranding were in control since the implementation was done on the existing M&S platforms and infrastructure, as no massive investment was required. Thus, the minimisation strategies of risks and costs enhanced M&S’s position within the luxury retail sector with little investment.

5.6.10.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Next PLC’s strategic change from Next Directory to Next Online had risks and expenses of moving from a disparate catalogue-based selling approach to a rapidly evolving online retail environment. Next PLC had some risks of damaging the existing loyal catalogue customer base by instantly converting them to the new online platform. In addition, huge investment issues were there to develop features including transformation of high-level e-commerce technologies, enriching the graphical interface, and optimising the flow of the supply chain and the process of online shopping.

Business Live, on its website, stated in 2021 that, “to control overall risks and costs, Next employed a strategic three-phase approach including strategic planning and integration, technology upgrade and system optimisation, and marketing and brand communication. This structured approach proved to be cost-effective, which realised improvements in the operation of Next PLC and secured a dominant position in online retail.

5.6.10.6 CASE E: H&M

H&M’s rebranding was a strategic move considering the needs and demands of fashion-oriented consumers regarding transparency and sustainability. Retail Dive stated in 2019 that

“the risks and costs were not much of a problem for the campaign because it adopted a gradual and systematic approach towards the integration of transparency practices in the entire business”. H&M, thus, tried to minimise the threats connected with the violation of consumers’ trust and subsequent sanctions by indicating the information on the supply chain and production on tags and descriptions of the products.

To minimise such risks and costs in the rebranding campaign of H&M, the company employed a multi-step strategy, which emphasised the company’s goals of transparency and sustainability, this not only acted as protection but also as a source of competitive advantage in the high-street clothing industry. Such a rebranding policy was expensive but helpful in improving the company’s position in the market and stabilising its brand image as one of the leaders in the sustainable fashion industry.

5.6.11. Various Effects of Rebranding

P11: Rebranding can negatively or positively affect a company's brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationship, brand loyalty, brand identity, and brand positioning.

5.6.11.1 Rationale:

This proposition was set here to give a hypothesis on the effects of rebranding. The five brand concepts that have a strong link with rebranding are brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationship, brand loyalty, brand identity, and brand positioning. Based on the above literature and theories of these brand concepts, further inferences were made to find out the possible impacts of rebranding. The objective of this last proposition is, therefore, to understand the impact of rebranding on the experience of each of the five companies analysed in this research.

5.6.11.2 CASE A: ZARA

Zara, the Spanish garment brand, launched its campaign named “Zara Redefined” in January 2022, in which it tried to shed its fast-fashion image in favour of luxurious and environmentally friendly fashion. Zara.com showed in 2022 that, “this shift brought positive outcomes such as the improved brand image among the consumers who are conscious of the environment and financially wealthy. Nickels and Hugh presented in 2024 that, “this process was critical in the application of sustainable strategy in the entire production and supply

chain, which made Zara successful in terms of its positioning in the market and improving its profitability. Inditex in 2023 had a net sale of £30.5 billion and this year Zara has a major role to play with an increase in sales by 13.1% to £10.7 billion.

Singh, in 2024, stated that, “management focused on a dual brand strategy that would satisfy the loyal customers who do not have the luxury to spend much on fashion and the new consumers who are more conscious of the price they are willing to pay for sustainable environment, even it is higher than usual.” This approach helped in reducing the chances of losing existing customers while targeting the new market segment. Beaumont, in 2022, stated that, “through the campaign, online sales and retailing portals were improved and a new brand image of Zara was developed as a luxury brand.”

5.6.11.3 CASE B: BOOHOO GROUP PLC

Boohoo’s decision to buy out the Debenhams brand and then rename it to “Debenhams.com” signalled the management’s conscious attempt to leverage the goodwill of the Debenhams brand while completely moving the brand online. It created new opportunities to expand the offering with beauty, sport, and homeware apart from clothing. Drapers Online, in 2023, explained that, “the acquisition of Debenhams under the Boohoo umbrella without its physical stores was another success that pointed to selective online operations”. Thus, this campaign helped to minimise overheads in this company and increase its profitability.

Boohoo: Racking up sales explained in 2023 that “this rebranding brought great benefits for Boohoo as it saw a 14% rise in revenue to £1982.8 million in February 2022.” Douglass, in 2024, stated that “After the rebranding campaign, Boohoo could improve its brand image which was affected because of labour issues.” McKinnon, in 2022, explained that “this strategic response, complemented by the rebranding campaign, aimed at protecting and building upon Boohoo’s strong brand image and brand positioning in the market.

5.6.11.4 CASE C: MARKS AND SPENCER

Through Marks & Spencer’s acquisition and rebranding of the Jaeger brand in 2021, the company achieved a key milestone of an increase in its overall revenue. Red Online explained in 2021 that the “Jaeger Relaunched” campaign saved the pure Britishness of Jaeger in the company’s clothes yet seamlessly incorporated them into M&S's new selling atmosphere. This strategy not only opened up the company to a clientele of more affluence

but also brought in its agenda of sustainability, where the clothing of Jaeger included silk, wool, and cashmere.

M&S achieved a key milestone of overall revenue increases by 9.6% to £11.93 billion by April 2023. Fashion United stated in 2021 that “based on feedback from clients and the customers, M&S improved the integration process to ensure that they offered the right products to the consumers. Marks & Spencer showed that rebranding facilitated a brand image appealing to the new generation of quality-conscious customers.

5.6.11.5 CASE D: NEXT PLC

Next PLC’s rebranding campaign, called Next Online Evolution, transitioned Next Directory into Next Online at the beginning of 2018, bearing in mind that e-commerce was rapidly becoming crucial for any business focusing on retail. This was not just a rebranding exercise, as it positioned the business for growth and enabled Next to leverage e-commerce to increase its revenue by 9.08% to £5.49 billion by January 2024. It also doubled Next’s internet sales as a percentage of total sales to 50% by 2024.

Chapman described in 2023 that, “the role of the management of Next PLC initiated this rebranding process with the core emphasis on technology factors and marketing communication to ensure the organisational change, create a separate online brand personality, and enhance existing brand image”. Thus, this rebranding campaign brought the best of Next’s position in the new markets and charted a new growth path for the firm in the progressive, high-street retail clothing industry.

5.6.11.6 CASE E: H&M

The “Transparency in Fashion” campaign, begun in early 2019 by H&M, improved the company’s market position concerning sustainability in the production of clothing. This rebranding exercise resulted in improvements in net sales which were up by 6% to £20.39 billion in the last quarter of the year 2023 while gross profit had improved by 7% to £10.43 billion. The campaign also helped H&M to establish itself as a company that focused on the idea of sustainability because it aimed at sourcing 97% of the used cotton back and using 57% of sustainable materials by the end of 2023. This concentration not only provided a positive impact on overall performance, but also enhanced the company’s competitive advantage in environmental awareness clients in the retail sector of the international fashion market.

H&M invested in developing the brand's online and sustainability plan which worked well in maintaining H&M's competitive edge and thus seeing the firm's market capitalisation touch £27 billion by early 2024. This way, H&M managed to implement the strategic leadership of the company to stay apace with the change that the fashion industry needed, making the company the leader to be followed by other organisations in the high-street clothing industry.

5.7. Chapter Summary

This chapter was designed for individual cases analysis of the five selected case studies including Zara (CASE A), Boohoo (CASE B), M&S (CASE C), Next PLC (CASE D), and H&M (CASE E). Initially, the case study findings are illustrated in each case and then individual case analysis is done through each proposition. As highlighted in this chapter, the analysis of strategic rebranding campaign within the high-street clothing sector of UK market corresponds well to the study's overall objective of identifying and describing the right rebranding strategies for achieving competitive advantages.

The above individual case study analysis presented that there are similarities in the nature of rebranding of the case studies, where all four except Next have done evolutionary rebranding. The extensive case studies helped in assessing that rebranding is not merely a change in the outlook but has to be a profound and tactical work that is sensitive to the online purchases and competition. All five cases used the Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand as rebranding campaign. In the case of renaming, only Next PLC changed its name from Next Direct to Next Online, but all other brands keep the same brand name as they are. For instance, Boohoo kept the same name of Debenhams after purchasing it and M&S did the same with Jaeger.

These findings are consistent with the research questions of this study that aimed at understanding the nature of rebranding strategies and whether they are used as strategic tactics to improve competitive advantage and market standing for the UK clothing brands. Through the systematic evaluation of the factors that influenced these brands' rebranding endeavours, this research has adopted a conceptual framework, though no conclusions have been made in this chapter. The next chapter will be collective case analysis, where the researcher has analyses by the themes (3) across all the five case studies based on the theoretical propositions of this research.

CHAPTER SIX: COLLECTIVE CASE STUDY ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.0 Introduction

This chapter sets off on a complex collective case study analysis to map the findings and insights gathered in chapter 5 based on the literature review in chapter 2 and theoretical propositions provided in Chapter 3. Collective case study analysis is needed because such a comparison goes beyond listing similarities and differences and attempts a critical analysis of how different theoretical constructs hold up when applied in practice across different contexts (Yin, 2017). The key objective is to analyse the competitive advantages described by each of the theoretical statements when examined in terms of real information.

To methodically approach collective case study analysis, the researcher attempts to identify the similarities among the themes and to analyse the data thoroughly as suggested by Eisenhardt (1989). The data is then compared among the case study findings. Here, the researcher selects eleven key propositions. In order to analyse the findings, the researcher grouped these propositions into three themes. Through these collective case studies analyses, the researcher will then critically evaluate the theories and develop new theories for understanding and predicting competitiveness in the UK high street clothing retail industry.

Table 6.1: 3 main themes for inferring discussion and conclusion

Case Study Propositions	Themes
P1. The nature of Rebranding	Nature of Rebranding and Its Application as a Strategic Management Tool for Gaining Competitive Advantages in the UK Market
P2. Rebranding Use as a Unique Strategy	
P3. Using Rebranding as an Atypical Strategy	
P4. Different Types of Rebranding	
P5. Motivations for Rebranding	
P6. Rebranding Campaign Strategies	
P7. The Process of Rebranding	The Process of Rebranding and Renaming for Becoming More Competitive in the UK Market
P8. Rebranding of Names	
P9. Rebranding Concerned Costs and Risks	The Risks Associated with Rebranding and Their Effects for Gaining or Sustain Current Market Share
P10. Overcoming Rebranding-Related Risks and Cost Factors	
P11. Various Effects of Rebranding	

To analyse collective case studies, and how the five retailers; Boohoo, Marks & Spencer (M&S), Next Plc, Zara and H&M, have engaged in rebranding within the UK market as proposed in this research question, the following section must define how firms engaged in the aspect of rebranding within the theoretical framework outlined in chapter 3. The intention is to assess whether these rebranding initiatives have been instrumental in realising these objectives as strategic management tools for enhancing competitive advantages. The analysis also tries to answer the research question of how well the theoretical propositions on rebranding fit the actual real-life examples of these companies.

6.1. Nature of Rebranding and Its Application as a Strategic Management Tool for Gaining Competitive Advantages in the UK Market

The first proposition is the idea that rebranding is not evolutionary but revolutionary regarding the brand name. In support of the proposition that change in a brand involves

revolution, Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) opined that rebranding should be a natural change as it pertains to the market positioning of the brand. In contrast, Knox and Bickerton (2003) argued that even a slight change in branding attributes like colour, logo and slogan may greatly affect perception and brand equity. The authors' views support that rebranding bears the characteristics of evolutionary and revolutionary processes supporting the proposition.

The changes in images of different companies also prove that rebranding can reposition a company drastically in the market and reconstruct its image. Examining Marks & Spencer's full-scale acquisition of Jaeger and its subsequent rebranding, it was evident that the hope was to create a more classic identity into M&S's up-to-date, reward-focused business strategy with a focus on quality and sustainability. The transition from a catalogue business to an online one was initiated with a change of the name from Next Directory to Next Online in line with other trends like e-commerce and Omnichannel. Zara's 'Zara Redefined' was a corporate campaign through which the brand attempted to move from the 'fast-fashion' category into luxury clothes deemed environmentally conscious and possessing a superior brand image. After the acquisition of Debenhams, Boohoo immediately repositioned Debenhams as an online-only brand and tapped into Boohoo's treasure trove of higher growth, new categories such as beauty, sport and homewares to increase Debenhams' reach alongside the famed department store's name. Finally, the "Transparency in Fashion" campaign recasts the company as a fitting example of the sustainable and ethical fashion brands that customers of the modern world expect. These cases support the proposition that rebranding is a revolutionary change when it comes to brand name change, not such as those branding alterations like colour, logo or slogan. The examples of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M showed that, whether revolutionary or evolutionary, rebranding can significantly change the company and its offerings on the market. Therefore, there is good evidence from the literature and from practical examples for the proposition supporting that rebranding is a revolutionary process, especially as it applies to the brand name.

The second proposition is that rebranding should be considered as a unique instrument of marketing and it should not be identified with repackaging or refreshing. Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer, (2021) pointed out that rebranding cannot be overestimated as it fundamentally alters customers' perceptions of a brand and their loyalty to it, which is why it is a pivotal initiative for organisations that seek to update their brand image and stand out from the competition. Kapferer (2012) added that rebranding can act as a way of reinventing the brand in a particular country with a view to making the brand relevant to current

consumers. With their statements, these authors have profoundly supported the statement of the proposition that rebranding is not a similar activity to other popular marketing techniques.

The above-rooted ideas correspond with reality observed at Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M where rebranding entailed major strategic changes. Five examples of rebranding show that there is a need for a separate category for rebranding that is different from other promotional tactics like repackaging, refreshing, and repositioning. All of them entailed a brand, a market, and a business model reorientation and thus cannot be discussed merely in terms of repackaging or rejuvenation. For instance, the acquisition by Marks & Spencer means that, the purchase of Jaeger consisted of far more than simply redesign and repositioning; it became aligned with the Values of M&S, which need to be recognised as differentiation by quality and concern with sustainability. Next Directory to Next Online is a strategic move, and not just a repositioning as it is a major change in the company's operations, moving online. The "Zara Redefined" was a transformation in the overall concept to enter a new segment differentiating itself as a luxury store from the 'house of junk' clearly a rebranding not just about a refreshed brand. Boohoo's takeover of Debenhams is into a pure-play online brand can be seen as a change in position and business model, it is not merely an image overhaul. The "Transparency in Fashion" campaign that H&M undertook may not be considered a simple marketing technique of the organisation but was a rebranding exercise to try and associate the brand with sustainability. Indeed, these cases go well in support of the proposition that rebranding is a concept that is different from packaging, refreshing and repositioning.

The third proposition proposes that rebranding is an atypical approach, contrary to typical branding processes. Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach (2018) noted that rebranding can act as a critical strategic move meant to achieve digital transformation goals, as the examples of these strategies combined with digital trends contribute to the enhancement of brand awareness and customers' interest in the targeted brand. On this matter, the literature supports Merrilees and Miller (2008), who acknowledged that rebranding can assist firms in altering their positioning strategies in markets that are increasing in competitiveness. The opinion of these authors paves the path to the statement that the claim of the third proposition is mostly justified.

The five cases namely Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M provide strong supporting evidence for the argument in supporting the proposition that rebranding is a completely diverse branding process, which is highly different from the other branding

processes. Each of these cases targeted more than mere branding, which could entail redesigning a logo, repackaging a product, or tweaking a slogan. For example, the acquisition of Jaeger for M&S was not simply the process of assimilation of a new brand but the reconceptualisation of Jaeger within the M&S vision and strategy by regarding only the quality and sustainability of the clothes. In the same way, Next Plc rebranded from Next Directory to Next Online, thus undertaking a seismic shift towards digital operations that actually transformed the brand at its core. The marketing effort of Zara was ‘Zara Redefined’ which was not a simple branding exercise but a shift from mass market segmentation to luxury segment, with a special focus on sustainability and quality, which is way beyond simple branding. Boohoo’s rebranding Debenhams and ‘Transparency in Fashion’ by H&M has clearly explained two profound strategic shifts that had operational and perceptual implications. These cases show that rebranding is an unconventional activity pegged in a certain strategic firmness that is difficult to achieve and sets the activity apart from other conventional branding activities. Thus, these examples indicate that rebranding is indeed different, unique, and atypical which strengthens the proposition that rebranding is different from typical branding activities. Hence, the proposition that rebranding is an independent and exceptional activity is beyond doubt.

The fourth proposition is concerned with a theoretical framework for rebranding categorisations which include the product, business unit and corporate-level rebranding, and the usefulness of such classifications in the case of five selected companies. These rebranding exercises can be said to support the idea that various forms of rebranding can help organisations achieve different strategic goals. In their study on the communication implications of rebranding, Merrilees and Miller (2008) noted that sometimes rebranding decisions are aimed at an attempt to align the organisational image to their new business model as a way of retaining competitiveness or a share of the market that has been lost in a very competitive market. In contrast, Kapferer (2012) noted that rebranding of products helps to extend the life cycle of the product, and as such, helps to lengthen the life of the product in the market. On the other hand, Muzellec and Lambkin in their publication of 2006 defined business unit rebranding as the selective rebranding of specific segments of the business venture in order to bring about a new image not directly affecting the general corporate image. The authors’ viewpoints also support the standpoint of this proposition.

The five cases support the argument stating that rebranding has three categories of corporate, business unit, and product rebranding which can be a source of competitive business

advantage. All the cases depict a form of rebranding, where the company's positioning strategy and market competitiveness are essential for rebranding. Another type of rebranding is business unit rebranding integration of Jaeger into M&S portfolio improved its appeal to affluent customers and reflected on its business sustainability. Next Plc changed its business from Next Directory to Next Online; this is an example of corporate rebranding because the company refocused the identification of the company to correspond to the rise in significance of electronic business hence providing the company with an added advantage in the electronic business market. Zara's global campaign 'Zara Redefined', which transformed Zara from a 'fast fashion' retail brand into a 'luxury fashion brand' is another type of rebranding that also seeks to attain brand prestige and appeal to a new consumer group. Also under acquisition and brand revival, another aspect of corporate rebranding is highlighted where Debenhams has been bought by Boohoo and remodelled as purely online clothing brand extending the Boohoo Corporation into new categories. H&M's "Transparency in Fashion" campaign is all about sustainability and refers to product rebranding that further strengthens the company's position on the market among eco-friendly consumers. All these examples show that various sorts of rebranding can create powerful benefits in the competitors' struggle, thus proving the suggestion. That is why the five cases under consideration provide solid evidence for stating that there are three types of rebranding corporate, business unit and product rebranding that could be a source of competitive advantage for companies.

The fifth proposition postulates that rebranding may be driven by several reasons which include; merger and acquisition, brand simplification, positioning and legal compliance. Hatch and Schultz (2003) showed that standardisation is another reason whereby, especially in the international markets, the firms can sustain the brand exposure and image across different countries, which also helps to reduce the complexities of marketing communication campaigns. The most frequent stimulus is mergers and acquisitions because the merging and acquisition of two companies necessarily demands one unified image in terms of the brand. Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) showed that developing a consistent standard of brand elements across different markets augments operational effectiveness and makes the brand as well as brand personality familiar to customers across the globe and hence developing brand loyalty. From these, it can be assured that the authors also confirmed different motivations working behind the decision of rebranding.

The five cases also fully support the proposition that rebranding is normally the result of external and internal triggers such as mergers and acquisitions, brand image, re-positioning, and diversification. The process through which Jaeger has drifted towards its current brand image resulted from Marks & Spencer's acquisition of the business and its subsequent attempt to fashion the brand within its grander vision. The need to change Next Plc to Next Online was a result of changes in market trends which made the company rebrand and downplay its online presence. In the "Zara Redefined" strategy, the company aimed a reposition that brand and retarget it towards the luxury business, which indicates a change in brand association. Boohoo changed Debenhams into a web-only retailer and the strategy was dictated by acquisition and the need to expand market share. H&M's "The Transparency in Fashion", was an attempt by the company to work on achieving brand equity and in the process it stuck to legal and ethical parameters of sustainability. The above-discussed cases suggest that more specifically, rebranding can be said to stem from these key stimuli, thus establishing the proposition.

The sixth proposition states that there are some key strategies for executing a rebranding campaign. Kaikati and Kaikati (2003) outlined the proposition with six essential strategies including phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand or one umbrella brand, heavily transparent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding. These strategies afford companies with another way of how they manage brand change dependent on objectives and the business environment.

The five cases of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M also confirm this proposition that the rebranding campaign can be delivered with different approaches. Marks & Spencer's rebranding of Jaeger is also in line with the brands' merger or one-brand strategy, through the assimilation of Jaeger into M&S. Next Plc's move to Next Online marks a swift to one brand strategy, it changed its platform from a catalogue company to an online company, though the mother name 'Next' remains the same. The Zara "Redefined" campaign completely avoided any dramatic changes in the brand image; instead, it slowly replaced all aspects of the previously used mass-market image with new characteristics of a luxury brand. Boohoo's rebranding of Debenhams as a pure-play online retailer under one umbrella brand to M&S. A good example is H&M's "Transparency in Fashion"; the combined brand strategy under one umbrella brand is visibly evident since it slowly introduced sustainability into its brand. These cases show that different approaches may be used for rebranding taking into consideration the goals of the company, which in return substantiate the proposition.

6.2. The Process of Rebranding and Renaming for Becoming More Competitive in the UK market

According to Proposition seven, rebranding is an ongoing and systematic process that involves several key stages including renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching. According to Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill (2020) talked about how these visual changes are crucial in communicating to the consumers and altering their behaviour towards the brand. This is followed by redesigning whereby the brand's graphics such as the logo and the packaging are altered to enhance the new message that has to be passed on to the customers (Wigley, 2011). Repositioning then moves the brand's market position to focus on other markets or change its positioning offering. The systematic approach for the revitalisation of the brand raises the competitiveness level and increases the solidity of positions in the market and consumers' loyalty.

The five cases expounded in this paper provide concrete support towards the proposition that rebranding is a continuous, strategic process of renaming, redesigning, repositioning and relaunching. Such a change in branding is illustrated by Next Plc when renamed from Next Directory to Next Online to signify an e-commerce strategy, redesigned its web interface navigation, repositioned itself in the e-commerce marketplace and rebranded with a new focus on the market. Likewise, Boohoo's acquisition of Debenhams entailed a process of rebaptism, the change of the appearance of the brand's web store, the shift of the product offerings to more segments, and the subsequent strategic re-introduction of Debenhams to the audience. Rebranding was also implemented systematically, step by step, starting and finishing with the Zara Redefined 'campaign' that moved Zara from the mass market to luxury. Another campaign that followed this process was the 'Transparency in Fashion' by H&M which followed the pathway of redesigning and repositioning. All these cases taken together prove the proposition in question rebranding is indeed systematic and continuous work. Indeed, the authors' notion of rebranding as a sequential move, making an organisation rebrand through renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching is illustrated by the five cases of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M. In sum, the cases provide overwhelming support for the contention that rebranding is a systematic process that promotes competition and consumer loyalty.

The eighth proposition shows that rebranding is often associated with the deliberate choosing of a new brand name, which in itself can also be associated with the general objectives of the positioning and rejuvenation of the brand in the market. According to Balmer and Gray (2003), it has to be an integrated strategic corporate branding process, which must be communicated internally and externally. In the context of rebranding efforts, the process of renaming can bring several benefits, including better differentiation on the market, increased brand values, and more loyal customers. Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova (2014) opined that the use of a new brand name can assist a firm in distancing itself from any negatives associated with the previous name or market trends, or increase appeal in new market or extended markets. Rebranding is not a veneer; rather, it is one of the fundamental moves of the branding shifts to new heights that reflect more profound changes in companies' image and positioning. In the researcher's opinion, the choice of a new name always has a deeper significance as to new directions in key strategies, but that does not necessarily mean that changing the name will create a competitive advantage.

Now, it is needed to see how organisations have strategically incorporated the action of brand name changes within their rebranding process. Next Plc has used the rebranding of "Next Directory" to "Next Online" to indicate the deliberate switch to the firm's online store strategy which is in line with the increased online shopping. This was more than simply a change of the company's name; it was a careful shift that reaffirmed Next's determination to become a major player in e-commerce economy. In the same respect, Boohoo's transformation of Debenhams into "Debenhams.com" illustrates how great value is placed on a name change in rebranding initiatives. Subsequently, by shifting to an online selling model, not only did Boohoo retain Debenhams as a distinct brand, but also managed to reinvent its niche into online sales to suit contemporary consumers. These also infer that changing the name alone would not have a significant impact if they did not go bricks and clicks; to their online presence.

Choosing a new brand name cannot be of that much effect unless it changes its operations, presence, and strategies according to the market demand, industry trend and benchmarks. Therefore, changing names might be of some attraction to a number of customers or target market that will not have any positive impact unless they do not accompany with new strategies, value propositions, and service quality. This proposition is not fully supported by the cases and the authors.

6.3. The Risks Associated with Rebranding and Their Effects for Gaining or Sustain Current Market Share

The ninth proposition holds that rebranding is a costly and risky strategy in which a firm has to spend a lot of money. Actual costs are not associated with the creation of a new brand and a new brand image in a given site; there are also others which are incidental to the rebranding process and these include the cost of redesigning logos, packs, ads, and so on. As noted by Balmer and Gray (2003), like any other exercise, rebranding also has negative attributes and these include the need to undertake a market survey, and the need to train employees. On the other hand, according to Doyle and Stern (2006), the problem of risks is especially topical in case rebranding does not resonate with the target consumer, then rebranding will not be effective to gain competitive advantages for the brand. Some of the issues mentioned by Balmer and Gray (2003) include the problems of achieving market research and staff education, and by Doyle and Stern (2006), the problem of what happens if rebranding is not well received by the public. So, the author's view seems to be uniform to the statement of the proposition.

The five cases of M&S, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M tend to support the proposition. While rebranding each of these firms incurred large monetary costs and the results were uncertain, thus implying risks. For instance, while acquiring Jaeger, Marks & Spencer later incurred several expenses it had to bear to integrate the company into its portfolio; yet the move was capable of encouraging the brand loyal customers. Next Plc's move to Next Online incurred the cost of a large amount of capital to support a social transformation of the company and there was the danger that it could alienate its core customers. Zara, in an attempt to adopt luxury branding, incurred high costs in terms of reorganisation and redesigning of stores and this was highly likely to affect its mass-market clientele. The rebranding has successfully positioned Zara in the market. Boohoo's decision to reposition Debenhams as a purely online retailer was expensive and unwise, as Debenhams has always been an offline retailer. For the specific case of H&M's "Transparency in Fashion", this means that a lot of money has to be invested in sustainability projects, bearing in mind that consumers can easily doubt the mantra. These examples clearly show that while changing the brand may indeed make strategic sense, it is rightly seen by firms as a costly and risky exercise.

The tenth proposition states that though rebranding process is associated with certain risks and costs, these challenges can be avoided over time by proper analysis on the need to re-brand, research on the market and undertaking a proper communication strategy in place. Kapferer (2012) proposed that different strategies can turn the rebranding challenge into an opportunity and paraphrase the company's brand by revitalising its market position and the customers' relationships. This shows an initial support to the proposition from the author.

From the precedent of five cases of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo and H&M it is seen that the thesis is valid that one can avoid costs and risks inherent in the rebranding strategy, especially in name-change, by making a best assessment of the same, thorough market research and by formulating an analytically developed communication strategy. All these companies initiated the rebranding processes with pre-existing knowledge of the market situation and the planned goals to achieve. For instance, Next Plc had to move from Next to Next Online and this was done after analysing the online market properly and also after putting a proper communication channel to ease customers into the change. This move by Zara to reposition itself to concentrate on the luxury market segment was clearly after research and not driven by a mere fad. In the case of Boohoo's acquisition of Debenhams, the rebranding process involved communication to utilise the pre-existing brand, whilst bringing the transition into the digital sphere. The authors' observations and the real-life examples of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M show how true authors' statements about rebranding can turn challenges into opportunities to revitalise the market position and customer relationships. These cases show that if research precedes the rebranding process and if the new brand image is supported by the proper communication strategies, the costs and risks are predictable and can be avoided which makes the proposition valid.

The eleventh proposition shows how rebranding affects issues such as brand equity, personality, consumer associations, relationships, loyalty, identity, and position. Cankurtaran and Beverland (2020) stated that, depending on the case, rebranding is a phenomenon which benefits the brand in the sense that it gives it a new life, makes it modern and timely or can be a way to raise its 'value', in the financial sense. Previously, Lee and Bourne (2017) provided a note on the same assertion that rebranding can strengthen the perceived brand personality and consumers' relationship with the brand because rebranding brings it closer to clients and culture. The authors' statements show clear support for the proposition regarding the effect of rebranding on brand equity, personality, consumer associations, relationships and so on.

The five cases of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M support the assertion of this study that rebranding has both benefits and costs on a brand and its brand equity, brand personality, consumer-brand relationship, brand loyalty, brand identity and brand position. For example, Marks & Spencer gained brand equity by rebranding Jaeger a prestigious brand into its company, but it lost its existing customers. Rebranding made the position of Zara brands better and attracted a new client base of luxury segment; Inditex's market capitalisation was increased to about £95 billion by early 2024. Thus, Next's internet sales per cent of total sales became more than double by 2024 and reached 50%; the figure was 35% before the rebranding process. This was marked by strong investor confidence, as the company's market capitalisation stood at approximately £11.75bn. By acquiring and overhauling Debenhams, Boohoo has revived the label's online standing. After the rebranding process, the variable results showed that the company generated an annual figure of £1,982.8 million in sales for the year to February 2022; further, the market capitalisation worth was roughly £4.2 billion in early 2024.

H&M's transition to focus on its sustainability practices enhanced its brand image, but to do so consumer perception had to be well handled. H&M was also able to record a net sale increase of 6% for the year ending on November 31st 2023 about £20.39 billion. All in all, these cases provide evidence of the proposition arguing that branding has multiple effects on different characteristics of a brand. Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo and H&M are such examples that rebranding activities helped these companies to give a new look to their brands, enhanced the worth of their brands, and repaired client associations.

6.4 Theoretical Propositions and Outcomes of Collective Case Analysis

In accordance with the discussions in the collective case analysis the existing propositions have been tested in this section and modified where needed in the following section. The propositions from individual case analysis have also been evaluated through collective case analysis. The similarities and differences have been examined and linked to the existing arguments based on the theories described in chapter 3 (table 3.1). Here in Table 6.5, the researcher examines whether each case supports the theoretical proposition of the research or not. The effects of the propositions on each case study are described on the basis of the strength of the presence of the proposition.

Table 6.2: Theoretical Propositions and collective case Studies Outcomes

Proposition No	Theoretical Association	CASE A	CASE B	CASE C	CASE D	CASE E	collective case Studies Outcomes
P1	The nature of Rebranding strategies and competitive advantages	✘	✘	✘	✓✓✓	✘	A- not supported B- not supported C- not supported D- supported E- not supported
P2	Rebranding Use as an Unique Strategy and competitive advantages	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P3	Using Rebranding as an Atypical Strategy and competitive advantages	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P4	Different Types of Rebranding and competitive advantage	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✘	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- not supported D- supported E- supported
P5	Motivations for Rebranding and competitive advantages	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P6	Rebranding Campaign Strategies and competitive advantages	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P7	The Process of Rebranding and competitive advantages	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P8	Rebranding of Names and competitive advantages	✓✘	✘	✘	✓✓✓	✘	A- not supported B- not supported C- not supported D- supported E- not supported
P9	Rebranding Concerned Costs and Risks and competitive advantages	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P10	Overcoming Rebranding Related Risks, Cost Factors and competitive advantages	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported
P11	Various Effects of Rebranding and competitive advantages	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	A- supported B- supported C- supported D- supported E- supported

✓✓✓ Strong presence; ✓✓ Moderately Strong presence; ✓ Weak presence; ✓✘ Very Weak presence; ✘ No presence and little or no evidence

6.5. Revised Framework on Rebranding Strategies for High-street retailers

The proposed conceptual framework prepared in chapter 3 (figure 3.1) discussed the implementation of rebranding strategies as a strategic management tool to gain competitive advantages in the UK high street retail industry. By mitigating possible risks, reducing costs, and taking appropriate rebranding campaign and processes, both rebranding and renaming can ensure competitive advantages. On the basis of analysis of collective case studies findings, a revised conceptual framework is proposed in this section, which includes both the current and new themes. This theoretical framework describes the themes that are primarily proposed and the evolving themes in the rebranding strategies. Thus, the revised framework attempts to answer the research questions and expands the understanding of how rebranding campaign strategies can ensure significant impact on the UK high street retailers through an appropriate rebranding process.

For using a strategic management tool, the research focused on the specific clothing brand's rebranding and then found out the motivations from the rebranding decision. After that, campaign strategies for the particular brand were used to do the rebranding process. This is evident in the case study findings that the clothing retailer's rebranding is different. Here, in this sector, name changing is not mandatory for rebranding, though name changing might be significant for other retail industries' high street brands. If the nature, motivations, and campaign strategies are selected wisely, then the rebranding process will go smoothly, the success rates of rebranding will be higher, and the effects will be helpful for the brand to get competitive advantages in the market.

Figure 6.1 proposed the nature of rebranding in case of a successful rebranding campaign. The understanding of rebranding as a revolutionary rather than an evolutionary process is well grounded in theory and empirics (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). That is why, rebranding should be viewed not as an evolution but as a complete transformation of a brand's market position (Knox and Bickerton, 2003). Minor changes in branding attributes such as colour, logotype and slogan have a powerful influence over the brand image and brand capital. Thus, the author proposed that renaming is revolutionary, but rebranding is both evolutionary and revolutionary.

Rebranding is indeed a separate and distinct process as compared to repackaging, refreshing, repositioning, and so on (Kapferer, 2012). Thus, rebranding is not a simple change of the logo or name of the brand, but a complex business process which can establish new brand value, and renovate the position of the brand on the market (Joseph, Gupta, Wang, and Schoefer, 2021). Even the rebranding is unique which can offer the opportunity to recreate a brand within a specific market and make it suitable for the prevailing market (Tarnovskaya and Biedenbach, 2018). The decisions about rebranding seem to be an attempt at matching the organisational image with the new business model, to remain competitive in a specific market environment. In particular, product rebranding enables the organisation to prolong a product's life cycle (Kapferer, 2012); where business unit rebrands aim to develop a new image for a specific area of the organisation's operations (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006), while corporate rebranding changes the general image of the entire company (Merrilees and Miller, 2008).

Different motivations drive organisations to the decision to rebrand whatever type it is. Therefore, all the discussions support the proposition that different stimuli work behind the decision of rebranding (Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020). There is indeed a set of systematic approaches through which organisations can shape the processes of brand transition, or rebranding: these include, specifically, phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand, and sudden eradication (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003). Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M use these strategies in their operations, as a result of which the authors' views with regard to strategic rebranding are substantiated. On the other hand, it can be said that, changing brand name can assist an organisation to expand the market (Miller, Merrilees, and Yakimova, 2014), but it is not the only way of rebranding as there are more ways of rebranding strategies to gain competitive advantages in the market.

It can be discussed that rebranding is regarded by the firms as a costly and risky exercise is true. These concerns are illustrated through the cases of Marks & Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, Boohoo, and H&M, all of which have expended large sums of capital on rebranding and experienced considerable risks, including the increasing of potentially losing existing consumers (Balmer and Gray, 2003), or inability to appeal to new consumers (Doyle and Stern, 2006). Consequently, there is clear supporting evidence that rebranding is costly and risky. Through appropriate research and communication, rebranding can be successful (Kapferer, 2012)

Rebranding process can help to upgrade the brand equity because rebranding can give new stimuli to the brand and make it more contemporary (Cankurtaran and Beverland, 2020). Moreover, successful rebranding deepens brand persona and make the brand consumer relationships stronger, which has a positive effect on brand equity (Lee and Bourne, 2017). Thus, rebranding can benefit brand equity for the high street retailers in the UK to get competitive advantages in the market.

Figure 6 1: Revised conceptual framework designed by the author

6.7. Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a comprehensive analysis of the rebranding strategies employed by five major retail companies: Some of leading retailers are Zara, Boohoo, Marks & Spencer (M&S), Next Plc and H&M. Consequently, the propositions established in Chapter 3 were vigorously discussed cross-sectionally with the practical experiences of these organisations. It also helped in determining the extent to which authors’ theoretical papers on rebranding are relevant to practical scenarios: their level of convergence or divergence to real-life practice in the cut-throat context of the UK market.

Among them, the ability to apply the rebranding approaches can be pointed as one of the major themes, as every firm was focused on its particular conditions and objectives in the market. For example, Zara and M&S undertook the Combined Rebranding or One Umbrella Brand Strategy, thereby managing to incorporate new brand values successfully with less or

minimal disruption to their existing brand equity. Still, Boohoo's strategy of rebranding Debenhams demonstrated the advantages and disadvantages of the Sudden Eradication Strategy, in which changes are sharp and radical to adjust the brand to Boohoo's fully e-commerce-based model. H&M with the help of the Translucent Warning Strategy in its initiative "Transparency in Fashion" also added the gradual diffusion of change to the concept of slowly introducing new brand values as a way to prevent consumer rejection.

The chapter also brought a reminder of the fact that systematic rebranding triggers indeed play crucial roles, as asserted in Proposition 7. The cases of Zara, Next Plc, and Boohoo make two points clear: rebranding is a long-term process of renaming, redesigning, repositioning, and relaunching. These are some of the crucial steps to ascertain that the particular brand still has its competitive advantages and its niche secure in the presence of intense market challenges arising from increased innovation. Moreover, the examination of Proposition 9 focused on the high costs and potential dangers of rebranding especially in case when it involves a change of the name or the major shift in position. Nevertheless, these cases have also shown that if sufficient heed is paid to the nature and type of business to be created and developed; enough market research is conducted; and adequate strategies are worked out and implemented, particularly with reference to communication, management risks can be well contained thus resulting in long-run gains and sustainable competitive advantage.

Thus, the research conclusions drawn from the case studies confirm the theoretical assumptions described in Chapter 3, but, at the same time, reveal the details of rebranding efforts which may not be easily addressed within the strict frameworks of the theory. Using rebranding as a case series, the chapter concludes that, when properly planned and executed, it is a potent weapon for the attainment of competitive advantage. It has the same prospects as the above four, but it also underscores some risks coming with the market environment and stakeholder expectations as well as the overall strategic goals of the organisation. In the next chapter, all these insights will be presented to the managers and future research in the form of recommendations and implications.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

7.1 Conclusions

The findings of the five selected case studies assisted the researcher to answer the research questions and supported the related literature on rebranding. Through qualitative case study analysis, this research has explained in detail the nature and application of rebranding in the UK's high-street retail industry. Based on the research, this study reveals how UK retailers strategically rebrand as a reaction to shifting market environments and changing customer demands. The analysis in the light of detailed case studies of popular UK retailers' experiences such as Boohoo, Marks and Spencer, Next Plc, Zara, and H&M has suggested that rebranding is much more than a marketing strategy. Both revolutionary and evolutionary rebranding are applicable in the high-street retail industry.

Rebranding is one of the most strategic business decisions, which defines all the further activities of the organisation and its position in the market (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). Through corporate level, business unit, and product level rebranding, high street retailers can choose any of the six rebranding campaign strategies including phase-in/phase-out, combined rebrand, one umbrella brand, heavily transparent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding.

It was established in the study that rebranding and renaming strategies are well aligned with the firm's strategic objectives. Through proper consumer research and effective communication, rebranding and renaming can help the high street retailers gain competitive advantages and market share. In addition, by mitigating the associated risks and reducing the concerned costs, rebranding can avoid any negative impact on the market of the retailers, thus ensuring that the high-street retailers can improve their brand image to gain or sustain their existing market share.

To sum up, this research presents a deeper understanding of how rebranding can be implemented to be effective. From the case study findings and analysis, it can be concluded that a rebranding strategy may take more than 1 year to be processed based on the

motivations of the rebranding. It is also evident that the effects of rebranding will be seen after 2-3 years of the implementation of rebranding.

7.2 Answering the Research Questions and Objectives

The investigation of rebranding strategies among high-street retailers has given concrete avenues about the nature and effect of rebranding procedures among the high-street retailers in a volatile and continuously shifting environment primarily controlled by online sales. This section summarises the results regarding the identified research questions to demonstrate that strategic rebranding activities are necessary to achieve competitive advantages and obtain market share (Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, 2019; Nana, Tobias, and Chilya, 2019; Roy and Sarkar, 2015).

Research Question 1, therefore, attempts to identify the nature of rebranding campaign strategies and their use as strategic options in the high street retail market based on the case studies of 5 renowned clothing brands. From the case study findings and analysis, it is evident that rebranding is unique and atypical; it is a strategic change at the organisational level for anything that requires a shift in methods of consumer interaction to fit modern consumer trends and standards (Balmer and Gray, 2003). From the six key rebranding campaign strategies (Kaikati, and Kaikati, 2003), a high-street retailer can choose the suitable one for gaining competitive advantages and increasing market share. From the case study findings, it is seen that high-street clothing retailers applied rebranding campaign in corporate level and business unit level, though retailers can also perform product level rebranding.

Research Question 2 focuses on how the brands in the UK high-street retail market change their brand and brand name and the fact that the brands are systematic in their approach to ensure that they get competitive advantages (Merrilees and Miller, 2008). From the case study findings, it is obvious that high-street retailers use different processes for various rebranding strategies, which can be summarised in research, conceptualisation, and execution stages. First, primary marketing research is conducted across the existing markets to understand the trends likely to be favoured by the customers to guide decision-making. This is then succeeded by the concept creation phase, in which new brand names and graphical logos are created to capture new market position strategies and new brand values. After conceptualisation, detailed execution ensures that the new branding is done systematically across the available platforms. During this phase, several departments from the company, for

instance, the marketing department, design department, and the operations department come on board to execute the rebranding campaign.

Research Question 3 seeks to demonstrate the associated risks and effects of rebranding in high-street retail brands of the UK for to gain or sustain existing market share. From the case study analysis, it is evident that rebranding has risks like; diluting the company's brands and ignoring the existing customer base which can erode the brand value in the market. Also, the financial aspect which includes expenses incurred in rebranding efforts and the questionable returns on investment are main challenges to rebranding. Yet, rebranding initiatives, if conceptually well-coordinated and operationally well-planned, may serve to strengthen the position of the brand in the market (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006). When rebranding campaign is done perfectly, the risks associated with it are mitigated easily and it can upgrade consumer perception towards the brand which in turn preserves or even gains the market share of the brand.

To meet the research objectives, the research comprehensively examined how effectively rebranding can become a strategic marketing tool that the UK's high-street retail brands would like to employ to increase their market competitiveness. 'Name change' was also mentioned at the stages of these rebranding campaigns; thus, proving that rebranding initiatives assist in sustaining brand equity and enhancing consumers' association. It was similarly established that without changing the brand name, rebranding efforts can also increase competitiveness and market presence to address objectives set in this research that offer an applied understanding of the strategic management of brand change in the dynamic high-street retail industry.

7.3. Contributions

This research expects to explain how rebranding can be a vital strategic orientation for the high-street retail chains in the UK, to isolate and regain market share, within the continually growing dominance of the e-retailing environment.

Previous research studies and scholarly articles have emphasised other sectors, while this research has chosen only high-street clothing retailers for case study analysis. In this sense, the contribution of this research in the topic of rebranding can be said as unique. At the same time, this research will also facilitate the literature review in terms of identifying those research areas that are underdeveloped and therefore find the basis for future investigations.

Moreover, the study hopes to offer useful information that may assist brands to fully implement rebranding as a tool through which they can strengthen their position and enlarge their customer base within a highly competitive high-street retail market. The contributions of this research in the literary world and the high-street retail industry regarding rebranding strategies are discussed in the following.

7.3.1 Theoretical Contributions

This research contributes significantly to the current understanding and knowledge of rebranding theory. A few studies discussed about the rebranding nature (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006), process (Kapferer, 2012), campaign strategies (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003) for better brand image (Roy and Sarkar, 2015) brand equity (Merrilees and Miller, 2008), and brand perception to gain competitive advantage and market share (Nana, Tobias, and Chilya, 2019). However, not enough research has been found regarding the rebranding strategies employed by the high-street clothing brands, which can be implemented in other retail sectors to make rebranding and renaming successful.

Six strategic options have been presented by Kaikati and Kaikati (2003) within the context of the evolution of the high-street retail market in the UK towards online sales. In addition, phase-in/phase-out, combined branding under one umbrella, translucent warning, sudden eradication, counter-takeover, and retrobranding have been discussed to analyse them by considering what effect they could have in the market with the increasing usage of e-commerce. This approach will not only confirm the applicability of Kaikati and Kaikati's strategies in the current markets but also expand the scope of a particular research question that is missing in the current literature. In doing so, this research presents qualitative data on the effectiveness and implementation issues of each strategy in today's context and will inform future rebranding efforts by contributing to the theoretical and practical literature on this topic in the context of the UK's high-street retail environment.

This research also offers a rich theoretical contribution to the literature on rebranding, and analyses strategically the use of rebranding within the UK's high-street retail industry, all of which is pertinent given the growth of online sales. Thus, this study enriches the management knowledge about the interactions of renaming and rebranding through collective case analyses, which is valuable to the study of competitive strategy and brand management, especially in the context of online sales (Blazquez, Mattich, Henninger, and Helberger, 2019).

This research describes how high-street brands have managed all the opportunities and threats posed by e-commerce, changing rebranding from the post-scrutiny activity for brands to the valuable strategy.

The explanation given here extends beyond the mere cosmetic-level changes and looks at the socio-economic essences that make rebranding necessary and force brands to rethink their strategies (Armstrong, Niinimäki, Kujala, Karell, and Lang, 2015). By dissecting the various renaming processes and their effects on the market perception of a brand, the study provides a deeper view of how rebranding affects consumers' loyalty and brand identity—two pivotal components affecting the growth of a brand's market share as well as its performance.

Furthermore, this research aims to examine rebranding as a threat and challenge in the context of the high-street retail sector. The work looks at the risks of rebranding, including brand erosion and consumers' hostility, and outlines the strategic opportunities that flow from rebranding provided it is done properly (Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Aaker and Joachimsthaler, 2012).

Also, this research contributes to the theoretical framework by proposing the influence of the nature of rebranding, motivations of rebranding, and campaign strategies on strategic management tool (see figure 6.1). Moreover, based on the significance of the impact of rebranding strategies, the effects of rebranding and renaming process are also shown into two sub categories including significant and non-significant in the revised conceptual framework designed in this research. The conclusion that has been made from this research not only contributes to the theories of strategic brand management but also provides framework guidelines that can be helpful to sectors that experience similar online transformations.

7.3.2 Policy Contributions

The case study findings of this research are specific to rebranding strategy, which contribute to the policy development for rebranding. Therefore, this research emphasises the need for policy development that will focus on high-street retailers in the UK because they are major players in the retail industry as they seek to transform their business from a traditional physical appearance to an online approach while redesigning their brand image. So, the policy must result in the development of a system for the implementation of rebranding strategies through input, process, and output.

As shown in the revised conceptual framework (see figure 6.1), the system will start with input. Here, input means the nature of rebranding, motivations for rebranding, and strategic management tool of rebranding campaign strategies. The revolutionary and evolutionary rebranding can serve the need of the high-street retail firms to initiate better market position in response to the continuously changing consumer perception through any of the six rebranding strategies.

The process stage in the newly developed system includes rebranding and renaming processes. The high-street retailers can attempt both or one of the strategies to cope with the existing market demand for gaining or sustaining market position. Rebranding or renaming processes include market research, campaign strategy deployment, and continuous evaluation. This stage calls for the formulation of broad strategies that will compel retailers to embrace new online platforms and other e-commerce systems. This should entail funding for the upgrade of online platforms, funding for smaller businesses to adopt e-commerce technologies, and the funding of education and training of the workforce to cope with the demands of the e-commerce based economy. Such measures will assist in overcoming the differences between conventional store management and customer requirements.

The output stage of the system will be the impacts of rebranding whether significant or non-significant. Based on the case study findings, it is evident that renaming also needs to follow the rebranding process in order to get significant results, otherwise only a name change cannot affect much in brand perception; rather, the result of only name change without following proper marketing tools will go in vain.

So, by establishing such policy, this research provides insights into the potential factor of how strategic rebranding can be facilitated through government and industry support to improve the positioning of high-street retailers.

7.4. Industry/Market Implications

This research contributes to the managerial understanding of how to carry out rebranding strategies in the UK's high-street retail market. It is for sure that rebranding is a long lasting process, so managers should not expect instant results from the implementation of rebranding strategy. Instead, the management of the high-street retailers need to emphasise ongoing evaluation of the rebranding strategy for cognitive understanding of the success or failure of the specific marketing strategy. The implications of the rebranding strategies are more clearly

figured out in the revised conceptual framework in Figure 6.1, from where the managers can get insights of how a rebranding strategy can impact significantly in gaining competitive advantage in the high-street retail market.

As the study shows, managerial implication is essential to be discussed in rebranding strategies that do not only act as a result of a change in the market conditions but are also focused on changes in the consumers' behaviour, as well as the development of the technology. For industry leaders and marketers, the insights derived can be used in the formulation of more elaborate rebranding strategies that capture the potency of the use of online media in boosting the sustainability of brand visibility and brand image. However, the research also raises the question of whether or not high-street retailers must connect the rebranding initiatives to a wide-ranging modern market policy. This entails a synchronisation of the e-commerce functionalities with the general retail systems, a factor that is assuming the status of necessity as a result of the growth in e-business. As a result, consumers will be provided with a convenient Omni channel journey, which will enhance the rate of customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Moreover, the study calls for changing how brands in the industry approach and undertake rebranding strategies. While rebranding is often seen as a marketing tool, it should be seen as a business tool that is to be employed in all business activities, from procurement to customer relations. Thus, it is necessary to follow a more effective and detailed strategy that will have a longer-term effect and allow brands to remain an important factor and keep competitive during the constant changes in the retail world. Thus, by answering these implications the study not only offers practical recommendations for contemporary participants of the market but also contributes to the accumulation of the primary historical analysis for subsequent research in retail management and relevant modern marketing approaches.

7.4.1. Rebranding campaign strategies for gaining competitive advantages

This research concludes that, in the UK high-street retail market, rebranding campaigns need to be employed carefully to gain competitiveness in the market. The six strategies discussed in this research can ensure competitive advantages for the high-street retailers through maintaining appropriate rebranding processes. There is the phase-in/phase-out technique, which essentially aims at controlling changeover – the migration from the old brand image to a new brand image. This approach is less invasive and does not cut off the consumer trust, which cannot be said of brands that wish to change direction while retaining customers. It

means consistency as the branding process advances, which in turn cements the company's place in the highly saturated market. Through translucent warning, the brands acknowledge customers before the implementation of the rebranding campaign.

The combined branding strategy under one umbrella brand is another strategic approach that may be applied when there are multiple brands which may be after mergers or acquisitions. Combined Rebranding Strategy via One Umbrella Brand was used in the rebranding of Zara, Boohoo, Marks and Spencer, Next, and H&M. This strategy thus centralises many brands making the brand structure less complex and a more robust brand image. It allows for bringing more effective and consistent promotional campaigns within the different segments of the market and makes the brand more attractive (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003). Sudden eradication is meant as the closing of the brand in the market, while counter takeover is also used to control the 'brand' image in ways that are defensive against competitive threats, thus making it a measure of defence in a very competitive industry. Retrobranding, on the other hand, takes advantage of the fact that earlier brand initiatives are normally received positively by the consumer, although in a new way, thus appealing to the largest market segment with the help of the fulfilment of the familiar and new at the same time.

These six categories of strategies that can be used by brands act as a strong resource in the contemporary structure of the retail industry. Through such strategies, many organisations are able to work towards fulfilling the market provisions and trends, and even embrace the advancement in technology and sustainability. This strategic flexibility is crucial for brand development, increase of market share, and the preservation of a competitive position in the market (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2003).

7.4.2. Rebranding process framework

Several processes have been found in literature review and theoretical proposition and conceptual framework chapters (Muzellec and Lambkin, 2006; Merrilees and Miller, 2008; Kapferer 2012; Kumar and Pansari, 2016; Goworek, Oxborrow, Claxton, McLaren, Cooper, and Hill, 2020) and also in the case study findings. Rebranding is thus a deliberate, rational course of action that is divided into several mandatory steps to effect a change in a brand image. The first activity is renaming, in which the brand's name is changed due to a change in strategic direction or due to a major change in the strategic focus of the organisation. In the aftermath of renaming, the redesign phase is the modification of the logo symbol as well as the brand's colouring range accompanying the packaging. The next process is repositioning, which entails moving the brand to a more suitable position in the market, to accommodate the change. The last process entails relaunching that will create awareness among the consumers of a brand. From the review of the literature and case study findings and analysis, the researcher proposed here below 4 processes for rebranding framework.

The proposed rebranding process framework consists of four stages namely preparation, planning, implementation, and post-implementation. Preparation involves the evaluation of whether rebranding is necessary, the examination of research material, and the establishment of goals and objectives to be met during rebranding, and last but not least giving consideration to the extent of production capability that the rebranding entails. In planning, the management deals with the creation of the new brand name, consumer research, and legal as well as design aspects such as logo and packaging. Implementation involves actualisation of all brand strategies with new packages manufactured and put in circulation while communication translated into reflecting the new brand. Last of all, post-implementation is the feedback step, which is the assessment of the whole rebranding process to determine whether or not the process met specific goals while forming the future strategies by means of audits and market reviews.

Figure 7 1: Rebranding process framework proposed by the researcher for high street retailers

7.4.3. Rebranding effects on market share

The impacts of rebranding are shown evident through the findings and analysis of the case studies. However, in the literature review chapter and the theoretical propositions and conceptual framework chapter it is found that rebranding can impact both positively and negatively. However, in all five case studies, it is found that rebranding can improve brand image, as well as respond better to the target consumer, thus positively affecting a brand's market share. Successful rebranding wears a new look on the brand and makes the product attractive to the customers. Through the improvement of brand image and better consumer perception, rebranding affects the competitiveness of the high-street retailers, thus helping the retailers sustain or gain market share.

7.5. Recommendations

Based on the propositions, a few recommendations have been developed here in this research for the high-street retailers as discussed in the following;

- Rebranding should not be considered only revolutionary; brand evolution sometimes makes a huge impact on the high-street retailers. For instance, Boohoo, M&S, and H&M performed evolutionary rebranding, thus becoming successful.
- Rebranding cannot be considered as a general marketing tool, rather a specific strategy should be maintained while implementing rebranding as all five case studies proved the same.
- Rebranding should be considered unique and cannot be evaluated the same as repackaging, refreshing, or repositioning. For instance, Zara redefined or H&M's transparency in fashion shows rebranding as unique strategy.
- Any type of rebranding can be taken for implementation from corporate, business unit, and product. However, it is suggested to focus on corporate and business unit rebranding to get the best output from rebranding. For instance, Zara, Boohoo, Next PLC, and H&M did corporate rebranding, while M&S did business unit rebranding.
- The management of the high-street retailers should be clear about the factors that may necessitate a rebranding including changes in the market environment, changes in the consumers' preferences, or the emergence of new technologies. For instance, Next PLC focuses on online sales considering consumers' preferences.

- Though rebranding campaign strategies largely depend on the necessity and area of rebranding, this research suggested to emphasise combined branding under one umbrella in the clothing retail sector as it proved successful in all the five case studies in this research.
- Rebranding process should be systematic as already advised in the process framework in Figure 7.1. These stages are also followed in Next PLC or Zara.
- Renaming should not be considered as the only process in rebranding, rather it is only a step of the total rebranding strategy, where renaming involves other marketing activities such as market research, internal strategy and infrastructure adjustment, employee training and change management, and external communication to acknowledge consumers about the change. For instance, Next PLC had to change all its catalogue-based infrastructure and train employees to move online.
- Rebranding campaign should consider the associated risks and costs before implementation. For instance, the cost of promotional campaigns for Zara redefined in 2022 ranged from £200 million to £300 million.
- Appropriate consideration should be given to mitigating risks and reducing costs of the rebranding strategy. For instance, Boohoo did not take physical stores and employees of Debenhams to ensure as little investment as possible.
- There must be quarterly, half yearly, and yearly review system of the impact of the rebranding strategies to analyse the impact of rebranding on the high-street retailers. For instance, all five case studies show yearly increases in sales and profit. Boohoo's sales increased by 14% in 2022 from the previous year after the purchase and rebranding of Debenhams.

7.6. Limitations and Future Research

Researchers using the case study research design are most likely to suffer from the shortcomings of this research because most of the shortcomings are related to the nature of the research strategies used. In these studies, one major weakness is the utilisation of secondary data collected from academic and industry journals, newspapers, and company websites and hence, it may not include all the dynamics of rebranding strategies in different markets. Secondary data is useful but could be insufficiently detailed to reveal the difficulties that specific brands in the course of rebranding face. Further, case study research is quite useful in the examination of details, as well as in validating propositions, but it is not very

helpful when it comes to the generalisation of the results for the analysis of the rest of the retail business. This is especially so since the analysis is on high-street retailers, where even factors such as brand, target market and industry environment may differ considerably from one company to another.

One of the areas that can be used for future research is to carry out cross-cultural comparisons of rebranding activities. The research is therefore based on the UK high-street retail market although this may limit the appreciation of cultural factors that reign on rebranding. Lifestyle is another critical facet when it comes to understanding customers' reaction to brand alterations since; this aspect is also influenced by the region. Future research could make a cross-cultural comparison to analyse the effects of culture on rebranding communications campaigns. This could involve exploring examples of how different countries' consumer and business environments have been managed with rebranding by brands.

It is also possible to suggest to future studies to consider sustainability in the study of rebranding. With the rise of people's environmental awareness, sustainability has become yet another factor that brands introduce into the process of rebranding. However, using sustainability in a brand identity can be problematic and offer challenges such as being labelled as a hypocrite if not genuine. Other research can be made on the strategies used by brands in implementing sustainability in the rebranding process, the issues encountered, and its effects on consumer trust and brand loyalty. This would be quite useful for brand strategists who need pointers on how to get to grips with sustainability and brand image.

In future research, it will be necessary to avoid limitations such as the lack of primary data collected by interviews and questionnaires. Primary data collection and analysis can enable the researchers to study the factors that affect rebranding choices, and the effects of such choices on organisational stakeholders, such as employees, customers and shareholders. Further research can also use a comparison of rebranding cases either by industry or geographical area to discuss similarities and differences. Studies of this sort would give a differential understanding of the rebranding processes as the strategic instrument and might contribute to further elaboration of the existing theoretical models.

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APPENDIX A: Various Other Data Sources were Reviewed for Different Case Study

Case Study Zara (Case A)

- Internal documents on the "Zara Redefined" campaign and strategic changes
- Company website, particularly sections on sustainability and luxury rebranding
- Observations of store redesigns and product adjustments in line with luxury positioning
- Annual reports, Market research Firms, and Reputed news sources
- External marketing campaigns promoting the new Zara brand values
- Supply chain reports on sustainable material sourcing

Case Study Boohoo (Case B)

- Strategic reports on the acquisition and rebranding of Debenhams
- Company website, focusing on Debenhams.com launch and related changes
- Annual reports, Market research Firms and Reputed news sources
- Observations of Boohoo's online strategy, and product diversification
- Media coverage on Boohoo's rebranding and corporate governance improvements
- Analysis of customer feedback and market response to the rebranding

Case Study Marks & Spencer (M&S) (Case C)

- Strategic documents related to the acquisition and rebranding of Jaeger

- Company website and online press releases
- Internal reports on the integration of Jaeger into M&S's brand portfolio
- Annual reports, Market research Firms, and Reputed news sources
- Observations of Jaeger's product display and promotional strategies in M&S stores
- Market analysis reports on the impact of the Jaeger brand integration

Case Study Next Plc (Case D)

- Company website detailing the transition from Next Directory to Next Online
- Internal multimedia presentations on the Next Online Evolution strategy
- Annual reports, Market research Firms, and Reputed news sources
- Observations of changes in digital and physical store strategies
- Industry reports on the impact of Next's omnichannel strategy
- Strategic planning documents from the CEO's office

Case Study H&M (Case E)

- Sustainability reports and transparency initiatives documentation
- Company website, especially sections on sustainability and ethical practices
- Internal presentations on the "Transparency in Fashion" campaign
- Annual reports, Market research Firms, and Reputed news sources
- Observations of in-store changes, including new product tags and store layouts
- Media coverage of H&M's sustainability efforts